

Department of Physics
The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda

Topological Insulating Phase In Some Bulk And Low Dimensional Materials

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A Doctoral Thesis, Submitted for PhD in Physics

Topological Insulating Phase In Some Bulk And Low Dimensional Materials

A thesis submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the Degree of

Doctor of Philosophy

by

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June 2022

DECLARATION

I, **Raghottam Manoj Sattigeri**, hereby declare that, the work incorporated in the present thesis is original and has not been submitted to any other University/Institution for the award of a Diploma or Degree.

I further declare that, the results presented in the thesis and considerations made therein contribute in general to the advancement of knowledge in topological insulating phase in some bulk and low dimensional materials and their application as energy materials.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that, the thesis entitled, ‘**Topological Insulating Phase In Some Bulk And Low Dimensional Materials**’ being submitted to, The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda, Vadodara; by **Raghottam Manoj Sattigeri** for the award of Doctoral degree in Physics. The thesis is a report of original research work and has been carried out by the candidate under my guidance and supervision.

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*I dedicate this work to my beloved parents,
Dr. Manoj and Dr. Bhagya*

Preface

*If I have seen further it is by
standing on the shoulders of
Giants.*

Sir Issac Newton

The work presented in this thesis builds up on the seminal discoveries made by, Prof. David Thouless, Prof. Duncan Haldane and, Prof. Michael Kosterlitz in the field of condensed matter theory for which they were honoured with the prestigious Nobel Prize in Physics in the year 2016. It is based on their work that, the condensed matter physics community got deeper insights into the ordered phase and phase transitions of materials. Thus, pioneering a branch of Topological materials. For the first time, mathematical concept of Topology transcended into the quantum realm of periodic systems; unravelling unconventional physical properties.

The physical property unique to these class of materials is primarily, the insulating character in D dimensions and conducting character in $(D-1)$ dimensions. This translates into, ultra-high carrier mobilities, charge densities, dissipationless transport of Fermions etc. In this thesis, we embark on a journey wherein, we employ, state-of-the-art Density Functional Theory based *first-principles* calculations to investigate the Topological properties and phase transitions in bulk (3D) and low-dimensional (2D and 1D) materials followed by the investigation of their potential applications in the field of Thermoelectrics and Quantum Catalysis. We discover materials as potential candidates for, spintronic, valleytronic, quantum computation and energy applications.

Overall, the thesis is divided into six chapters with three working chapters. We begin by establishing the concept of Topological materials and discuss about the tools used in their investigations thereof. We begin with investigations of Topological characters of half-heusler

compounds LiMgX ($X = \text{Bi, Sb, As}$) and binary compound AuI in their bulk phase. This is followed by investigation of the low-dimensional phase of the half-Heusler and binary compound, along with functionalization techniques to realize unconventional physics. These are then followed by the investigations from applications point of view. Finally, the entire thesis is concluded by discussing some future prospects which would proliferate from the present work.

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Finally, I would like to pour my heart out with acknowledgement towards my family, especially my parents and sister, *Dr. Manoj Sattigeri*, *Dr. Bhagya Sattigeri* and *Mrs. Gouri Kulkarni* for their immense support, guidance, encouragement and blessings throughout my life. I would also like to acknowledge the blessings bestowed upon me by my grandparents, *(Late) Shri. Mohanrao Sattigeri*, *Smt. Meenaxi Sattigeri*, *(Late) Shri. Gurunath Hullur* and *(Late) Smt. Girijadevi Hullur*. It was they who nurtured the spirit of enquiry and scientific temperament in me since my childhood by encouraging my amateur experiments/investigations I used to do at home, in school and today as a part of my PhD. I fondly remember that, in spite of the mess I used to create during my amateur explorations at home, my parents always encouraged me and were never annoyed. Finally I would like to acknowledge the latest addition to our family, my niece; *Miss Kaveri Kulkarni*. Looking at the naughty and curious explorations of the world around her, I always realised that, one should have the curiosity of a toddler throughout their life, it makes science and research even more fun and scintillating experience. At last, I would like to acknowledge my wife, *Dr. Soumya Sattigeri* and my brother-in-law, *Mr. Suhas Kulkarni* for their indirect support.

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CHAPTER 1

Introduction

This chapter begins with the introduction to concept of topology and its link to periodic systems in condensed matter theory. This is followed by thorough discussions highlighting the development of the subject and its contemporary status in terms of research and development. This chapter will clearly establish the motivation and objectives (which govern chapters 3, 4 and 5 of the thesis) with focus on the bulk and low dimensional materials, emphasising and identifying the existing caveats from the literature.

1.1 Concepts of Topology

Topological Insulators are a class of unconventional materials in condensed matter physics governed by the mathematical principles of Topology. Before we dwell deep into the thesis with our investigations of the topological materials, we would like to briefly introduce the concepts of Topology and how it translates into a governing principle in the investigation and exploration of topological materials.

Topology; is a branch of mathematics wherein objects are classified into spaces which are equivalent depending on the presence or absence of a *smooth* and *continuous* deformation between them.^{1,2} From mathematical perspective, ‘Homeomorphism’ is one of the most common types of topological equivalence where, two spaces can transform into each other without abrupt changes.² A trivial example is provided below (in illustrations 1.1, 1.2 and 1.3)

1. Introduction

where, the english alphabets (A-Z) and different geometric shapes are grouped into equivalence sets/spaces based on the presence or absence of a continuous deformation amongst them.

$$\{A, R\} \{B\} \{C, G, I, J, L, M, N, S, U, V, W, Z\} \{D, O\} \dots \quad (1.1)$$

$$\left\{ \bigcirc \quad \square \quad \triangle \quad \diamond \quad \hexagon \quad \dots \right\} \quad (1.2)$$

$$\left\{ \odot \quad \blacksquare \quad \triangle \quad \diamond \quad \hexagon \quad \dots \right\} \quad (1.3)$$

For example, it is evident from illustration 1.1 that, the alphabets ‘A’ and ‘R’ can be transformed into each other through a smooth and continuous deformation making them topologically equivalent. However, ‘A’ or ‘R’ cannot be transformed under a smooth and continuous transformation into the alphabet ‘B’. Similarly, we can observe the equivalence classes of different solid geometries presented in illustration 1.2 such as, circle, square, triangle etc. which can be transformed into each other by varying the number of edges i.e., through smooth and continuous deformation. Such transformation is not possible between the solid objects (presented in illustration 1.2) and objects with hole (presented in illustration 1.3) which makes the two spaces topologically distinct.

This advanced mathematical method of topological distinction was implemented by David Thouless, Duncan Haldane, and Michael Kosterlitz to understand the physics in unconventional phases of matter such as, superconductivity, superfluidity and ultra-thin magnetic films.³ This has had huge ramifications in the field of condensed matter physics opening up new avenues to explore matter in strange states for innovative applications, eventually earning them a Nobel prize in 2016.⁴

1.2 Topology in Condensed Matter

Explorations by Kosterlitz and Thouless were focused on the flat-lands so thin that they can be treated as two-dimensional matter whereas, Haldane focused on the edges where matter assumes the form of a thin thread which can be treated as one-dimensional.⁴ Due to quantum confinement effects, the dynamics in these low-dimensional regimes is quite unusual. These regimes are quite unique, in the sense that, at macroscopic scales we are well versed with the phase transitions in matter as a function of temperature (for example,

phase transition of ice from solid > liquid > gas > plasma) however, in low-dimensional regimes these phase transitions were unexplored with matter assuming strange phases and unconventional behaviour (see Fig. 1.1 below).

For example, at absolute zero condition in low-dimensional regimes, unusual phenomena such as, unintrupted motion of particles and perpetually spinning vortices in fluid with zero viscosity crop-up which are associated with phenomena such as superconductivity and superfluidity respectively.⁵⁻⁷ It was believed that, in low-dimensional matter even under conditions such as, ultra-cold temperatures of absolute zero, thermal fluctuations can give rise to disordered systems indicating towards the absence of phase transitions.⁸ This understanding of matter and phase transition was challenged by Thouless and Kosterlitz in 1970s when they invented the *Kosterlitz-Thouless* (KT) transition which earned tremendous reputation for its novelty in the field of condensed matter physics.^{9,10} This is a type of topological phase transition which is quite unique as compared to traditional phase transition observed in matter at macroscopic scales. Applying the concepts of topology to vortices in a thin layer of matter at ultra-cold temperatures, Kosterlitz and Thouless described a new phase transition. Under ultra-cold conditions, the vortices in a thin layer of matter form strongly correlated pairs and as the temperature increases, beyond certain critical temperature, these vortices drift apart from eachother in different directions (see Fig. 1.2 below). Such a phase transition in low-dimensional systems is known as the KT transition.^{9,10} The underlying theory (which has been confirmed experimentally as well) is so versatile that it is applied in atomic and statistical physics as well making it a universal phenomena.

Figure 1.1: A schematic representation of phase transitions in matter at macroscopic scales as compared to the low-dimensional regimes as a function of temperature. *Adopted from The Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences, illustration by Johan Jarnestad.*

Figure 1.2: A schematic representation of the Kosterlitz-Thouless topological phase transitions as a function of temperature in thin layer of matter under ultra-cold conditions. *Adopted from The Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences, illustration by Johan Jarnestad.*

1.3 Topology and Quantum Hall Effect

Thouless and Haldane came together to developed a quantum mechanical theory which could be applied to determine the electrical conductivity of materials and understand phases of matter which cannot be identified by their pattern of symmetry breaking.¹¹⁻¹⁴ By mid 20th century the scientific community in the field of condensed matter physics had a thorough understanding of the material properties such as electrical conductivity and its origin. However, there were certain unusual scanarios wherein the existing theories failed to provide a valid and logical explanation. For example, the discovery of quantum Hall effect by Klaus von Klitzing in 1980 generated a lot of curiosity amongst the physics community to understand the origin of the observed phenomena.¹⁵ Klitzing investigated a sandwich of thin conducting material between two semiconductors placed at ~ 2 K temperature and in a high magnetic field of the order of ~ 15 T. In such an arrangement, the electrical conductance assumed certain discrete integer values (n) with precision of the order of 10^{-9} , making it the most precise physical phenomena (as evident from Eq. 1.4).¹⁵ The riddle was that, this phenomena existed irrespective of the variations in temperature, magnetic field and the impurities in semiconductor layers. Such physical phenomena could not be explained by the contemporary theories in 1980s.

$$\sigma_H = n \frac{e^2}{h} \tag{1.4}$$

Thouless applied the concepts of topology to address the unconventional phenomena of step-wise variation of electric conductivity at ultra-cold temperatures and under high magnetic

Figure 1.3: A schematic representation of the analogy between the mathematical concept of topology and quantum Hall conductance where, the geometrical classification of object depends on the number of holes (which is necessarily an integer) and the electrical conductance which has integer dependence as evident from Eq. 1.4. *Adopted from The Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences, illustration by Johan Jarnestad.*

field observed in quantum Hall effect.^{16–18} As discussed previously in section 1.1, topology pertains to equivalence between spaces wherein a smooth and continuous deformation persists amongst them. This analogy was applied to the experimentally observed quantum Hall effect which is schematically presented in Fig. 1.3 where the conductivity has integer variance. In other words, the topological quantum fluid of freely moving fermions in thin layer of material (which is sandwiched between two semiconductors) is quantised due to topology with unconventional behaviour along the boundaries. Eventually in 1988, Haldane proposed a model for graphene and discovered that, similar scenarios of topological quantum fluid can arise in thin layers of semiconductors even in the absence of magnetic field.¹³

Haldane investigated magnetic chain of atoms in certain materials and concluded that, these chains had distinct properties depending on the nature of atomic magnets i.e., odd or even depending on the spin.^{12–14} He proposed and showed that, even and odd magnetic chains are topological and non-topological respectively. Similar to the topological quantum fluid, these properties exist along the edges where the terminals of a topological chain are governed by the spin along those sites which can be integer or half-integer in nature. This unraveled a novel phase of matter grouped as topological materials which were eventually observed not only in chains but also along the thin border layers and surfaces of bulk materials.

Over the years, collective efforts to investigate quantum flat-lands by Thouless, Haldane and Kosterlitz have led to the discovery and proliferation of topological materials into; topolo-

gical insulators, topological semi-metals, topological metals, topological superconductors etc.³

1.4 Topological Invariant

The highly precise nature of integer quantum hall effect motivated Robert Laughlin to explain the phenomena by using gauge invariance.¹⁹ However, this did not give the complete understanding of the observed phenomena in real materials due to paradoxical results which was addressed by Thouless and colleagues.¹¹ This approach clearly established the role of topology in the observed physical phenomena. In case of quantum Hall effect, we have charged particles moving in a uniform magnetic field which is interpreted by neglecting the electron-electron interactions and by replacing the lattice potential with background positive charge. This scenario in materials was addressed by Landau who showed that, for a particular cyclotron frequency (as presented in Eq. 1.5), the energy of the system is quantized (as presented in Eq. 1.6) into degenerate states on macroscopic scales known as Landau levels such that, each state depends on the magnetic flux given in Eq. 1.7.^{20,21} These Landau degeneracies are labelled in terms of crystal momentum since the translation symmetry in homogenous magnetic field is that of magnetic translations rather than the conventional translational symmetry which breaks in a magnetic field. The resulting unit magnetic flux (presented in Eq. 1.7) persists in every lattice cell spanning the entire lattice of the material. Similar labelling can be done for eigenfunctions of an eigen state in the bandstructure i.e., the Landau levels can be associated with a vector in reciprocal lattice space. Therefore, the eigenfunction of n^{th} Landau state is presented as $u_{\vec{k},n}(\vec{r})$ in terms of the crystal momentum \vec{k} in the irreducible Brillouin zone.

$$\omega_c = \frac{eB}{m} \quad (1.5)$$

$$E_n = \left(n + \frac{1}{2}\right) \hbar\omega_c \quad (1.6)$$

$$\phi_0 = \frac{h}{e} = \frac{2\pi}{e} \quad (1.7)$$

By using linear response theory an expression for conductance in terms of eigenfunctions can be obtained (as presented in Eq. 1.8) which depends on the *Berry* field strength (\mathcal{B}) (which can be expressed in terms of the *Berry* potential presented in Eq. 1.9 in terms of

eigenfunctions) with the integration being performed over the momentum space (\vec{k}) spanning the entire Brillouin zone.

$$\sigma_H = \frac{e^2}{2\pi h} \sum_n \int_{\vec{k} \in BZ} d^2k \mathcal{B}(\vec{k}, n) \quad (1.8)$$

$$\mathcal{A}_i(\vec{k}, n) = i \langle u_{\vec{k},n}^- | \partial_{k_i} | u_{\vec{k},n}^- \rangle \quad (1.9)$$

Based on conventional theory of electromagnetism, such a vector potential (as in Eq. 1.9 above) is related to the *Berry* field strength as follows;

$$\mathcal{B}(\vec{k}, n) = \partial_{k_x} \mathcal{A}_y(\vec{k}, n) - \partial_{k_y} \mathcal{A}_x(\vec{k}, n) \quad (1.10)$$

Therefore, the integral presented in Eq. 1.8 represents a pseudo magnetic field over an enclosed geometry analogous to the case of a quantized magnetic monopole in electromagnetism. Eventually, it can be shown that, this *Berry* field strength has a finite value C_1 as presented in Eq. 1.11 which is known as the *first* Chern number (which happens to be an integer).²²

$$\frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{\vec{k} \in BZ} \mathcal{B}(\vec{k}, n) = C_1(n) \quad (1.11)$$

This explicitly established the fact that, the extremely precise and robust nature of conductance observed in experiments originates from the mathematical condition presented in Eq. 1.11 which is independent of any sorts of perturbations, particle-particle interactions, magnetic impurities etc. This makes the Chern number a *topological invariant* which can only assume integer values owing to the mathematical constraints. As an extension to this, Thouless and his colleagues included the effects of lattice potential which was otherwise replaced by a smeared-out positive background charge. As a consequence, splitting of the Landau levels into sub-bands was observed which results in conductance same as that presented in Eq. 1.4. The major result of this effort by Thouless indicated towards the possibility of a quantum Hall effect in the absence of external magnetic field.¹⁸

Such a system was proposed by Haldane who realized that, on breaking the invariance under time-reversal symmetry can give rise to energy bands without Landau levels which are characterized by a non-zero *Chern* number.¹³ This was implemented in graphene as a toy model where, the tight-binding approximation of fermions on a hexagonal lattice arrangement was

considered with inclusion of hopping between both; nearest and next-nearest neighbours of a sub-lattice position. In such a model, the magnetic flux is incorporated by making the hopping matrix elements complex in each unit cell. This breaks the invariance under time-reversal symmetry facilitating quantum Hall effect. This new phase of matter is known as *Chern* insulator wherein the quantized Hall effect was observed in absence of an external magnetic field. The first system to practically exhibit such a behaviour was Cr-doped $(\text{Bi,Sb})_2\text{Te}_3$ wherein a plateau of Hall resistance ρ_{yx} was observed at a density corresponding to occupied bands.²³ One of the most important consequences of these investigations was the quantum spin Hall effect which is said to be akin to the quantum Hall effect because it does not require external magnetic field and, obeys charge-conservation and spin- S_z conservation symmetries.

1.5 Quantum Spin Hall Effect and Beyond

Figure 1.4: Spin filtered edge conducting energy bands in graphene (shown in inset). Adopted from Ref. *Phys Rev. Letts.*, **95**, 226801 (2005).

In case of graphene it was observed that the conducting states are non-chiral and insensitive to lattice disorders owing to their directional correlation with fermionic spin.

This model is now famously known as the Kane-Mele model which is a combination of two versions of Haldane's model with one version relevant to the spin-up fermions with chiral quantum spin Hall effect and the other version relevant to the spin-down fermions with anti-chiral quantum spin Hall effect. Based on the relativistic version of quantum spin Hall effect developed by Kaplan and colleagues (to perform numerical simulations of the

Inspired by Haldane's graphene model, Kane and Mele proposed the existence of quantum spin Hall effect in materials.²⁴ They investigated the effects of spin-orbit interactions in low energy electronic structures of graphene which could be experimentally realized (under cryogenic conditions) to exhibit symmetry protected transformation from an ideal semi-metallic nature to a quantum spin Hall insulator. Such a system would be insulating in D dimensions and conducting in $(D-1)$ dimensions (as presented in Fig. 1.4). In

chiral gauge theories), it was observed that, quantum spin Hall systems consist, bulk fermions of opposite mass, massless Dirac mode and bulk currents which carry chirality rather than charge in a spin Hall current analogue.^{25,26} These features are governed by the parity and time-reversal symmetry $U(1)$ gauge theory. This implies that the Kane-Mele model exhibits zero charge Hall conductance and non-zero spin Hall conductance (σ_{xy}^{spin}) in units of $\left(\frac{e}{4\pi}\right)$.

Similar investigations were performed independently by Bernevig and Zhang wherein, the spin-orbit interactions induced a momentum dependent magnetic field vector pointing upwards and downwards for spin-up and spin-down fermions respectively due to strong correlations under a strain configuration (as presented in Fig. 1.5).²⁷ Since the spin up and down fermions are not correlated,

the Hall state remains invariant when the spin-spin scattering is introduced which otherwise destroys the quantum spin Hall effect.²⁸ This fact was established by Kane-Mele when they introduced a topological invariant (\mathbb{Z}_2) which is used to identify and classify trivial and non-trivial band insulators irrespective of the quantum spin Hall effects in the system.²⁸ This new phase of matter where, the edge conducting liquid is robust due to quantum spin Hall effect irrespective of the spin-spin and spin-orbital interactions is known as topological insulator. This exotic phase of matter is a type of symmetry protected topological order governed by the charge conservation and time-reversal symmetry. Hence, topological insulators and quantum spin Hall states are distinct states of matter owing to the symmetry protected topological order.

Figure 1.5: Spin-up and spin-down fermions with opposite chirality under opposite spin-orbit interaction force with the lattice displaced due to strain configuration. The net charge Hall conductance zero while the net spin Hall conductance is non-zero and quantized. Adopted from *Phys Rev. Letts.*, **96**, 106802 (2006).

Since the spin-orbit interactions induced splitting has a dependence on the effective nuclear charge Z as, $\Delta_{SO} \propto Z^4$, it implied that graphene would exhibit extremely weak spin-orbit effects; making it quite tough to realise quantum spin Hall effect experimentally. This was addressed by Bernevig, Hughes and Zhang who proposed that, the two-dimensional topological insulators can be realised in quantum wells made up of HgTe sandwiched between CdTe;

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which was eventually observed in experimental conditions by the Molenkamp group.^{29,30} When the thickness of HgTe in CdTe/HgTe/CdTe quantum well is small, the sandwich system behaves as an trivial insulator. However, when the thickness of the HgTe quantum well is increased beyond certain critical thickness the system CdTe/HgTe/CdTe undergoes a Lifshitz phase transition.^{31,32} Such phase transitions correspond to change in the sign of gradient term in the Ginzburg-Landau free energy functional. This drives the quantum well system into a non-trivial topological phase transition wherein the bulk gap closes forming a Dirac cone at the critical point and then reopens into a quantum spin Hall insulator.

Figure 1.6: (left) Energy of sub-bands E_1 (blue) and H_1 (red) at Γ point in the momentum space as a function of the HgTe quantum well thickness (d). (right) Schematic energy dispersion relations of the energy sub-bands E_1 and H_1 at different HgTe quantum well thickness; $d = 40, 63.5,$ and 70 Å (from left to right) indicating a Lifshitz phase transition. Illustrations adopted from *Science*, **314**, 1757-1761 (2006).

Figure 1.6(right) represents schematic energy dispersion relation $E(k_x, k_y)$ of the energy sub-bands E_1 and H_1 for different thickness of HgTe quantum well in momentum space. The red regions indicate dominant H_1 sub-band and the blue regions indicate dominant E_1 sub-band whereas the violet region indicates a uniform mixture of these sub-bands. At $d = 40$ Å the valence band is dominated by the H_1 sub-band and the conduction band is dominated by the E_1 sub-band (also evident from Fig. 1.6(left)). As the quantum well thickness is varied, at critical thickness (d_c) the sub-bands get mixed equally around the band crossings and beyond this critical thickness, the sub-band characters are reversed. The experimental success then led to the exploration of similar phenomena in bulk materials.

1.6 Topological Phenomena in Bulk Regime

Following the Lifshitz phase transitions and consequent measurement of edge channel dominant conductance (see Fig. 1.7) in the quantum Hall state of the CdTe/HgTe/CdTe

quantum wells; led to extensive research to realize similar phenomena in bulk materials. Prior to these investigations of quantum wells, in 1985-87, three dimensional topological insulators were predicted by Volkov, Pankratov and Pakhomov to exhibit Dirac fermions along the band inverted interface heterostructures of PbTe/SnTe and HgTe/CdTe.^{33,34} However, the emphasis on topological character and the relevance of time-reversal symmetry was only realised in the early 21st century.

Figure 1.7: Longitudinal four-terminal resistance ($R_{14,23}$), when HgTe quantum well has thickness (d); 5.5 nm (I) before transition and 7.3 nm (II, III, IV) when the sub-band order is inverted, as a function of gate voltage in the absence of magnetic field and at 30 mK temperature. Adopted from *Science*, **318**, 766-770 (2007).

Three dimensional *strong* topological insulators were predicted to exist in binary compounds of Bismuth which would exhibit robust surface states which won't decay into multiple quantum spin Hall states.³⁵⁻³⁷ The first three dimensional system to exhibit non-trivial topological insulating nature was an alloy of Bismuth and Antimony. Primarily, Bismuth (which natively exhibits a semi-metallic character with narrow band gap which results in high conductivity) is doped with varying concentrations of Antimony driving the system through a phase transition leading to an inverted band order similar to the one observed in the CdTe/HgTe/CdTe quantum wells.^{36,38,39}

The energy difference between the valence band and conduction band of pure Bismuth reduces as the concentration 'x' of Antimony increases forming an alloy of the form $\text{Bi}_{(1-x)}\text{Sb}_x$. At a critical concentration of 4% (in this case) the valence band and conduction band intersect each other forming a Dirac cone. Beyond this critical point, the energy of valence band increases and the energy of conduction band decreases resulting into an inverted band order (also known as band inversion) at a particular time-reversal invariant momenta (as presented schematically in Fig. 1.8). For concentrations of Antimony from 7% to 22% the inverted band order is retained wherein the alloy exhibits strong topological insulator nature with vanishing band gap on the surfaces leading to the robust surface states. Experimentally, through angle resolved photoemission

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spectroscopy it was observed that, these surface states cross the Kramer degenerate points odd number of times featuring massive Dirac fermions hosting three dimensional Dirac particles which explains the observation of quantum Hall fractionalization in Bismuth.^{24,38,40}

This was followed by similar experimental observations in Bismuth and Antimony chalcogenides (which exhibit quintuple layered structures) as well as pure Antimony wherein robust surface states were observed protected by particle number conservation and time-reversal symmetries.⁴¹⁻⁴⁵

These were narrow gap semiconductors with strong spin-orbit interaction owing to the heavy elements such as Bismuth, Tellurium etc. Motivated by the non-trivial phenomena in these binary compounds, the focus of research moved onto a huge and diverse family of semiconductors known as the Heusler compounds.⁴⁸⁻⁵¹

Figure 1.8: Schematic representation of band inversion as the concentration 'x' of Antimony is varied in Bismuth forming the alloy $\text{Bi}_{(1-x)}\text{Sb}_x$. Adopted from *Phys. Rev. B*, **76**, 045302 (2007).

Figure 1.9: Structure of a Heusler compound, in full-Heusler; X_2 atoms form L2_1 structure and in half-Heusler with a vacant sublattice the structure is C1_b . Adopted from wikipedia.

These are compounds of type XYZ (half-Heusler) or X_2YZ (full-Heusler) which provide a large number of potential topological compounds hosting metallic surface states (also known as ideal two dimensional electron gas with spin-momentum locking and suppressed Umklapp scattering) due to different permutation and combinations of the elements occupying sites X, Y and Z.^{42,46,47} Typically, the X and Y sites are occupied by the s-block/transition metal elements and the Z site is occupied by the p-block element forming a face centered cubic lattice arrangement. Natively, in some of these materials the Fermi level falls within the conduction

or valence band owing to the intrinsic impurities which needs to be eliminated (pushing the Fermi level into the bulk gap) by employing methods such as, doping, gating, application of pressure/strain etc.⁵²⁻⁵⁴ Also, some materials such as, $(\text{Bi}_{1-x}\text{Sb}_x)_2\text{Te}_3$ with mild Sn doping exhibit *intrinsic* topological insulator phenomena with the Fermi level and the surface Dirac cone lying in the bulk gap which has been verified experimentally.⁵⁵

1.7 Current Status

In real materials under practical conditions, things are a bit complicated and often deviate from the ideal scenario such as, homogenous crystals. However, in spite of such variations in practical scenarios, several physical phenomena have been explained theoretically by considering crystalline arrangement with the presence of minor impurities or defects. Branching out from such simple theories, especially the electronic band structure of materials gives us insights into the transport of electronic charge (which has led to the classification of materials into insulators, semi-conductors and conductors) and the material response under different temperatures and external magnetic field. This was revolutionized with discovery of the quantum Hall and spin Hall effect which led to the development of the topological band theory of materials giving deeper insights into the unexplored exotic quantum phases of matter.^{41,57} This has led to experimental discovery of topological insulators in two and three dimensional materials.^{36,38,56} These phases of matter and also the topological superconductors are protected by symmetries; similar to those in Haldane's model. Recently, the 'Kitaev chain' has gained a lot of attention since they host Majorana modes which have applications as qubits, indicating towards the possibility of a topological quantum computer.^{58,59} Also, it has been demonstrated that, topological insulators can be used to manipulate spin-torque computer memories due to metal-insulator transitions.⁶⁰ It was suggested that, topological insulators when placed in a magnetic field would behave as magnetoelectric materials with quantized magnetoelectric effect rather than surface conductors which was verified experimentally in 2016.⁶¹⁻⁶³ In 2010, the Kondo effect (i.e., minima in electrical resistance as a function of temperature) was observed in Samarium Hexaboride (SmB_6) which led to the discovery of the topological Kondo insulators.^{64,65} Guided by the proximity effects, superconductivity can be induced in topological insulators which would host symmetry protected and spin-momentum locked surface states made up of Majorana particles along the

interface.^{66,67} The latest additions to the family of symmetry protected topological phases of matter are, Weyl semi-metals, Nodal-line semi-metals etc., which have been discovered experimentally in 2015.^{68,69} This indicates that, topological materials can have several potential applications for example in, spintronics, valleytronics, dissipationless transistors, advanced magnetoelectronics, optoelectronics etc. Apart from these general applications, bulk topological insulators are known to exhibit excellent thermoelectric properties due to ultra-high mobility of the Dirac fermions on the surfaces and negligible scattering.^{70,71} Recently a new field of topological quantum catalysis has been introduced wherein, the Fermi-arcs in topological semi-metals and surface/edge conducting Fermi liquids in topological insulators facilitate excellent catalytic reactions for applications in hydrogen evolution, oxygen evolution etc.⁷²

1.8 Scope of the Thesis

Several methods (such as, application of strain/pressure, electric field etc.) to induce and enhance spin-orbit interactions in materials have been proposed to realise non-trivial topological insulators in bulk materials. These techniques were applied to a large number of bulk materials to realise the non-trivial topological phase transitions. Of these, half/full-Heusler compounds (introduced in section 1.6) stand out due to their multifunctional properties which involve; unconventional topologies, magnetic order, thermal transport properties, superconductivity etc. This is due to the unique valency (which is characteristic feature of Heusler compounds) which can be tuned by varying the chemical compositions under different permutations and combinations of elements from the *s*, *p* and *d* block of the periodic table. With an emphasis on strong spin-orbit interactions, the search for unconventional topologies has also extended to Heusler compounds with elements from the *f* block of the periodic table. Apart from ternary/quaternary Heusler compounds, binary compounds (which have inverted band order and are adiabatically connected to bulk HgTe) are also known to exhibit potential topological insulator nature subject to quantum topological phase transitions under strain/pressure.

From the perspective of two dimensional (low dimensional) materials, topological insulators are identified by the insulating bulk and conducting edges which lead to spin-charge accumulation along the edges giving rise to the quantum spin Hall effect. As established

in section 1.4, the magnetic field analogue governing two dimensional materials is the *Berry* curvature which exhibits sharp changes in the Brillouin zone along the time-reversal invariant momenta which hosts the bulk gap. Due to promising room temperature applications (spintronic/valleytronic devices, ultra-fast switch etc.) two dimensional topological insulators have gained a lot of interest. However, a major criteria is the existence of a large non-trivial gap along a time-reversal momenta which is quite tough to be realised experimentally. To this effect, several efforts have been carried out to realise such materials at room temperature by, application of strain/pressure, electric field, hetero/homo-structures governed by interlayer van der Waals hybridizations, partial/complete functionalization etc.

With this background, we were motivated to explore the non-trivial topological phases and quantum phase transitions in some bulk and low-dimensional materials. We present a thorough and extensive investigation of the topological insulating nature in bulk and low dimensional materials alongwith their applications as thermoelectric and catalytic materials. We explored and predicted ternary half-Heusler compounds such as, LiMgX (X = Bi,Sb,As) and binary compound such as zincblende AuI for their potential applications as strong bulk topological insulators. Their non-trivial topological insulating nature are characterised in terms of band and orbital inversions (similar to those discussed in section 1.6) leading to topological phase transitions followed by classification of the topological class in terms of the \mathbb{Z}_2 invariants and angle resolved photoemission spectroscopy like surface plots. Low dimensional systems such as, LiMgAs (which is dimensionally engineered from the bulk half-Heusler parent LiMgAs), partially functionalized Tellurium and Selenium and AuI monolayer were explored and predicted for the first time. We found that, these low dimensional materials are large-gap topological insulators with potential room temperature applications. Finally, from multifunctional perspectives we explored, bulk AuI for thermoelectric applications at room temperature, low dimensional AuI for basal catalytic activity and low dimensional LiMgAs for topological quantum catalysis.

1.9 Objectives and Thesis Outline

With the scope of the thesis defined in previous section, we present the major objectives guiding the thesis and the computational investigations carried out thereof. Following are the major objectives addressed in this thesis:

1. Introduction

1. To investigate Half-Heusler compounds; LiMgX (X = Bi, Sb, As) for non-trivial topological insulating properties.
2. To investigate non-trivial topological conducting and insulating nature in binary zincblende compound AuI.
3. To investigate dimensionally engineered two dimensional topological insulator from trivial bulk Half-Heusler compound.
4. To investigate dimensionally engineered AuI monolayer for non-trivial topological insulating nature.
5. To explore and investigate the effects of partial functionalization of two dimensional monolayers of Tellurium and Selenium on non-trivial topological insulating nature.
6. To investigate the thermoelectric properties of bulk topological insulator AuI.
7. To investigate the catalytic activity of basal plane of dimensionally engineered AuI monolayer towards hydrogen evolution reaction.
8. To investigate two dimensional topological insulator LiMgAs for topological quantum catalysis.

Overall, the thesis is divided into six chapters with three working chapters. With the objectives in place, we briefly discuss the thesis outline in terms of the three working chapters.

With **CHAPTER 1** setting the background motivation and objectives governing the thesis, we move onto **CHAPTER 2** wherein, we describe the computational formalisms employed as methods in the investigations carried out as part of this thesis. We begin with the description of the origin and various formalism which played a vital role in the development of density functional theory i.e., we present the eigen function based approximations and density based approximations which are used to solve the many-body time independent Schrödinger equation describing a periodic system. We then present various exchange correlations approximations and electronic approximations which govern the accuracy of the computational investigations carried out in this thesis. We then present, the formalisms defining lattice dynamics, elastic constants and ab-initio molecular dynamics simulations which are used to describe the structural stability of the proposed materials in this thesis. Also, we briefly discuss about the semi-classical approach of Boltzmann transport equations which are employed to compute

the thermoelectric transport properties of the bulk materials. We establish the methods such as, maximally localised wannier functions and tight-binding model which are used to compute the topological properties of various bulk and low dimensional materials. Finally, we discuss in short the codes used in our computational investigation of the bulk and low dimensional topological insulators.

In **CHAPTER 3**, we present our investigations on the topological quantum phase transitions in bulk materials. We begin with the description of our investigations on Half-Heusler family LiMgX ($X = \text{Bi, Sb, As}$) in the backdrop of existing relevant literature. We then present our computations on pressure induced topological quantum phase transitions; driving the system from a trivial insulator to a non-trivial topological insulator. We point out the necessary and sufficient condition in realising a non-trivial topological insulator. We then present our work on bulk binary compound AuI wherein, on breaking the crystal cubic symmetry we find a transition from non-trivial topological conducting to topological insulating state. Prior to the discussions of non-trivial topological quantum phase transitions we discuss about structural stability. This is then followed by the qualitative (in terms of electronic band structures, density of states, orbital projected density of states etc.) and quantitative (in terms of surface states and \mathbb{Z}_2 invariants) investigations necessary to confirm the non-trivial topological properties.

In **CHAPTER 4**, we present our investigations on the topological quantum phase transitions in low dimensional materials. We begin with dimensional engineering of non-trivial low dimensional topological insulators from trivial bulk materials such as, Half-Heusler LiMgAs . We then present similar results wherein, the low dimensional AuI monolayer is dimensionally designed from bulk zincblende parent. In both the cases i.e., in LiMgAs and AuI monolayers we present non-trivial topological quantum phase transitions. We then present our investigations on the effects of partial functionalization on the topological properties of elemental monolayers made up of Tellurium and Selenium. Apart from the qualitative and quantitative analysis, we also study and present the Berry curvatures in these low dimensional materials which give further insights into the origin of the non-trivial topological character. All the investigations in this chapter are presented with proper analysis of the structural stability of the proposed low dimensional materials in term of phonon dispersion curves and ab-initio molecular dynamics simulations.

In **CHAPTER 5**, we focus on the possibility of using topological insulators for potential

energy applications such as in, thermoelectrics and catalysis. We present the thermoelectric applications of bulk topological insulator AuI with an emphasis on the effects of band topologies on thermal transport properties. We then present our investigations on the catalytic activity of the basal plane of AuI monolayer (which was dimensionally engineered for non-trivial topological behaviour) towards hydrogen evolution reaction. This work further motivated us to explore the possibilities of highly efficient catalytic activity along the non-trivial edge states in a two dimensional topological insulator. We therefore present our computational investigations on the potential; topological quantum catalysis hosted by two dimensional topological insulator LiMgAs. The thermoelectric properties are analysed in terms of the thermoelectric transport parameters and the overall figure of merit. Whereas, the catalytic activity towards hydrogen evolution reaction is analysed in terms of various reaction mechanisms such as, Volmer, Volmer-Tafel and Volmer-Heyrovsky along with the computation of exchange current densities.

Finally, in **CHAPTER 6**, we present the summary of all the investigations presented in the working chapters. Along with this, we also discuss the future scope of further research and exploration in topological materials.

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CHAPTER 2

Methods and Formalisms

This chapter discusses the origin and development of density functional theory based first-principles method which is the primary tool of investigation employed in this thesis. We begin with the fundamental formulations pertaining to the Kohn-Sham approach which are at the heart of density functional theory and employed in our computations using Quantum ESPRESSO code. We also discuss in brief other methods and codes such as, density functional perturbation theory, ab-initio molecular dynamics simulations (AIMD), ElaStic, BoltzTrap and the ShengBTE code. Followed by methods like, maximally localised wannier functions in Wannier90 and the implementation of tight-binding model in WannierTools code.

2.1 Many-body Problem

The development of quantum theory with theoretical tools such as time-independent Schrödinger equation (presented in Eq. 2.1 where, \hat{H} is the hamiltonian of the system, $\psi(\vec{r})$ is the single particle eigen function and E is the corresponding eigen value), has emerged as an efficient method to describe *simple* quantum systems such as Hydrogen atom.¹ The system of Hydrogen atom is the most simplistic toy model (two-body system with one proton and one electron) wherein the exact solution of Schrödinger equation can be numerically computed by variable separable techniques to obtain the ground state energy of -13.6 eV. However, as the size of system increases for example, the case of Helium atom, the process of solving the Schrödinger equation gets complicated due to higher number of variables involved

in such many-body systems which makes finding the exact numerical solution a challenging task which can be addressed by reducing the system to a two-body system with reduced mass.

$$\hat{H}\psi(\vec{r}) = E\psi(\vec{r}) \quad (2.1)$$

However, the complexity scales-up exponentially as we consider the periodic arrangement of atoms in solids which are regarded as many-electron systems with indistinguishable mutual interactions in a smeared-out background positive nuclear charge. Such a system is described by the ‘ N ’ particle eigen function $\psi(\vec{r}_1, \vec{r}_2, \vec{r}_3, \dots, \vec{r}_N)$.² It is next to impossible; to find the exact solution (as in the case of Hydrogen atom) of such a complex many-body system. To add to this, in such big systems, we also come across complex interactions between electron-electron, electron-ion and ion-ion making the Hamiltonian of the system quite complex as presented in Eq. 2.2. Here, \hat{T}_e , \hat{T}_n , $\hat{V}_{e,e}$, $\hat{V}_{e,n}$ and $\hat{V}_{n,n}$ are, the kinetic and potential energy operators (accounting for electron-electron, electron-ion and ion-ion interactions) respectively.^{3,4}

$$\hat{H} = \hat{T}_e + \hat{T}_n + \hat{V}_{e,e} + \hat{V}_{e,n} + \hat{V}_{n,n} \quad (2.2)$$

Then, the many-body time-independent version of Schrödinger equation reduces to Eq. 2.3 where, the indices i and k run over the electrons and ions, m_e and m_n are mass of electrons and ions, Z_k and $Z_{k'}$ are the nuclear charge on ions, $|\vec{r}_{n,k} - \vec{r}_{n,k'}|$, $|\vec{r}_i - \vec{r}_j|$ and $|\vec{r}_i - \vec{r}_{n,k}|$ are the radial distances between ion-ion, electron-electron and electron-ion respectively.

$$\hat{H}\psi(\vec{r}) = \left(-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m_e} \sum_i \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \vec{r}_i^2} - \frac{\hbar^2}{2m_n} \sum_k \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \vec{r}_{n,k}^2} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\substack{k,k' \\ k \neq k'}} \frac{e^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{Z_k Z_{k'}}{|\vec{r}_{n,k} - \vec{r}_{n,k'}|} + \right. \\ \left. \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\substack{i,j \\ i \neq j}} \frac{e^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{1}{|\vec{r}_i - \vec{r}_j|} - \sum_i \sum_k \frac{e^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{Z_k}{|\vec{r}_i - \vec{r}_{n,k}|} \right) \psi(\vec{r}) = E\psi(\vec{r}) \quad (2.3)$$

Solving Eq. 2.3 gives the information regarding the ground state of the system in terms of the energy eigen values and since this equation depends on the atomic mass and charge of the electrons and ions, the method is termed as *first-principles* as it does not require parametric fitting to obtain the solution as in the case of empirical problem. However, the associated complexities persist making it impossible to solve Eq. 2.3 for a many body system. An attempt by Born and Oppenheimer was made to address this issue and make the equation solvable.

2.2 Eigen Function Based Approximations

Born-Oppenheimer Approach

As an analogy, imagine you are driving down a four-lane highway in a car, you can travel faster and overtake several heavy vehicles such as trucks, rollers etc. So, when we want to study the speed of vehicles travelling in such a scenario, we can neglect the effect of slow moving heavy vehicles. Similarly, when the electrons and ions are confined in a momentum space, by the virtue of mass, the electrons would possess higher momentum as compared to the ions. Hence, we can neglect the ionic contribution in the Hamiltonian presented in Eq. 2.2, this is known as the Born-Oppenheimer approximation.⁵ Based on this, the electrons are assumed to move in a smeared-out background positive charge originating from the relatively static ions. Then, the eigen functions can be presented as a combination of the electronic and ionic eigen functions as evident from Eq. 2.4 where, $\chi_k(\vec{r}_n)$ and $\phi_i(\vec{r}_i, \vec{r}_n)$ are the ionic and electronic eigen functions respectively.

$$\psi(\vec{r}) = \chi_k(\vec{r}_n)\phi_i(\vec{r}_i, \vec{r}_n) \quad (2.4)$$

Then, the variable separated form of Eq. 2.3 can be presented as Eq. 2.5 and Eq. 2.6 below.

$$\left(-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m_n} \sum_k \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \vec{r}_{n,k}^2} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\substack{k,k' \\ k \neq k'}} \frac{e^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{Z_k Z_{k'}}{|\vec{r}_{n,k} - \vec{r}_{n,k'}|} \right) \chi_k(\vec{r}_n) = E \chi_k(\vec{r}_n) \quad (2.5)$$

$$\left(-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m_e} \sum_i \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \vec{r}_i^2} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\substack{i,j \\ i \neq j}} \frac{e^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{1}{|\vec{r}_i - \vec{r}_j|} - \sum_i \sum_k \frac{e^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{Z_k}{|\vec{r}_i - \vec{r}_{n,k}|} \right) \phi_i(\vec{r}_i, \vec{r}_n) = E \phi_i(\vec{r}_i, \vec{r}_n) \quad (2.6)$$

Under the Born-Oppenheimer approximation, the first term of Eq. 2.5 vanishes resulting in a constant (β).⁶ Then the modified Hamiltonian can be rewritten as in Eq. 2.7 where, $\hat{T}_e = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m_e} \sum_i \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \vec{r}_i^2}$ is the electron kinetic energy operator, $\hat{V}_{e,e} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\substack{i,j \\ i \neq j}} \frac{e^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{1}{|\vec{r}_i - \vec{r}_j|}$ is the electron-electron interaction potential, $\hat{V}_{e,n} = -\sum_i \sum_k \frac{e^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{Z_k}{|\vec{r}_i - \vec{r}_{n,k}|}$ is the electron-ion interaction potential and $\beta = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\substack{k,k' \\ k \neq k'}} \frac{e^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{Z_k Z_{k'}}{|\vec{r}_{n,k} - \vec{r}_{n,k'}|}$ is an external potential (\hat{V}_{ext}). The reduced form of Schrodinger equation can then be presented as in Eq. 2.8

$$\hat{H} = \hat{T}_e + \hat{V}_{e,e} + \hat{V}_{e,n} + \beta \quad (2.7)$$

$$\hat{H}\phi(\vec{r}) = \left(-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m_e} \sum_i \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \vec{r}_i^2} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\substack{i,j \\ i \neq j}} \frac{e^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 |\vec{r}_i - \vec{r}_j|} + \hat{V}_{e,n} + \hat{V}_{ext} \right) \phi(\vec{r}) = E\phi(\vec{r}) \quad (2.8)$$

This approximation partly solves the complexity of many-body Schrödinger equation since, it does not address the electron-electron interactions and the asymmetry and correlations which govern Fermions like electrons. This was addressed by the, Hartree and Hartree-Fock approximations.

Hartree Approach

The coulomb interactions between electrons governed by classical electrostatics had to be addressed in order to further simplify the many-body problem. This was done by Hartree who, modified the many-body problem to one-electron problem which is known as the independent electron approximation.⁷⁻¹⁰ The electron-electron interaction potential (independent of the self-interactions) contributing to the Hamiltonian presented in Eq. 2.7 can be written in terms of the charge density $\rho(r)$ as in Eq. 2.9.

$$\hat{V}_{e,e}(r) = \int \frac{[\rho(r') - \rho_i(r')]}{|r - r'|} dr' \quad (2.9)$$

According to classical electrostatics, the distribution of electronic charge density in space $\rho(r)$ gives rise to an electrostatic potential $V_l(r)$ which is governed by the Poisson's relation presented in Eq. 2.10. The electrons in such an electrostatic potential would have a potential energy known as the Hartree potential $V_H(r)$ which obeys the Poisson's relation and transforms in Hartree units as, $V_H(r) = -V_l(r)$.

$$\nabla^2 V_l(r) = \frac{\rho(r)}{\epsilon_0} \quad (2.10)$$

Then, the electronic charge distribution corresponding to the Hartree potential can be constructed by summing the individual eigen states as below with the summation running over all the occupied eigen states;

$$\rho(r) = \sum_m |\psi_m(r)|^2 \quad (2.11)$$

With this, the electron-electron interaction potential gets converted to a single electron potential as presented in Eq. 2.13 (by using Eq. 2.11 in Eq. 2.9) which is also known as the Hartree potential.

$$\hat{V}_{e,e}(r) = V_l(r) = \sum_{m \neq l} \int \frac{|\psi_m(r)|^2}{|r - r'|} dr' \quad (2.12)$$

Hartree also suggested to present many-body eigen function as the product of eigen functions of individual electrons comprising the system as presented in Eq. 2.13 below.

$$\psi(\vec{r}_1, \vec{r}_2, \dots, \vec{r}_N) = \prod_{m=1}^N \psi(\vec{r}_m) \quad (2.13)$$

Then, by introducing the Hartree potential presented in Eq. 2.12 in Eq. 2.8 we get the modified Schrödinger equation as follows (Eq. 2.14) which is known as the Hartree equation.

$$\left(-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m_e} \sum_i \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \vec{r}_i^2} + \sum_{m \neq l} \int \frac{|\psi_m(r)|^2}{|r - r'|} dr' + \hat{V}_{e,n} + \hat{V}_{ext} \right) \psi(\vec{r}) = E\psi(\vec{r}) \quad (2.14)$$

However, the missing piece was that, Hartree did not include the electronic correlations which led to the Hartree-Fock approximations.^{11,12}

Hartree-Fock Approach

The major problem with Hartree approach was that, (i) the eigen functions of electrons were not anti-symmetric with respect to exchange of electrons and, (ii) the electron-electron interactions were averaged. Hartree-Fock method addresses the former problem (which was pointed out by Slater and Fock independently).^{13,14}

They began with anti-symmetric eigen function as a function of the position and spin (presented in Eq. 2.15 below) which satisfies the Pauli exclusion principles which mandates that, under particle exchange, the eigen functions would be anti-symmetric. As a consequence, no two electrons can have the same set of quantum numbers i.e., electrons with same spin cannot simultaneously occupy the same eigen state.

$$\psi_{HF}[(\vec{r}_1, \sigma_1), (\vec{r}_2, \sigma_2), \dots, (\vec{r}_N, \sigma_N)] = -\psi_{HF}[(\vec{r}_1, \sigma_1), (\vec{r}_2, \sigma_2), \dots, (\vec{r}_N, \sigma_N)] \quad (2.15)$$

Also, instead of using the product of eigen functions presented in Eq. 2.13, we use a Slater determinant eigen function which satisfies anti-symmetry and is presented in Eq. 2.16 where, $\psi_r(\vec{r}_s, \sigma_s)$ are one electron eigen functions.¹⁵

$$S = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N!}} \begin{vmatrix} \psi_1(\vec{r}_1, \sigma_1) & \psi_1(\vec{r}_2, \sigma_2) & \dots & \psi_1(\vec{r}_N, \sigma_N) \\ \psi_2(\vec{r}_1, \sigma_1) & \psi_2(\vec{r}_2, \sigma_2) & \dots & \psi_2(\vec{r}_N, \sigma_N) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ \psi_N(\vec{r}_1, \sigma_1) & \psi_N(\vec{r}_2, \sigma_2) & \dots & \psi_N(\vec{r}_N, \sigma_N) \end{vmatrix} \quad (2.16)$$

Then using the Lagrangian multiplier method to minimize the expectation value of the Hamiltonian as done to obtain Eq. 2.14 we arrive at the set of Hartree-Fock equations presented in Eq. 2.17 where, s_m and s_l are spin labels. Although the electron exchange is addressed but this approach is computationally expensive, since, the total energy of the system E in Eq. 2.17 requires minimization of the ‘N’ particle Slater determinant.

$$\left(-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m_e} \sum_i \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \vec{r}_i^2} + \hat{V}_{e,n} + \hat{V}_{ext} + \sum_{m \neq l} \int \frac{|\psi_m(r)|^2}{|r - r'|} dr' - \sum_m \delta_{s_m, s_l} \int \frac{\psi_m^*(r') \psi_l(r')}{|r - r'|} dr' \right) \psi(\vec{r}) = E \psi(\vec{r}) \quad (2.17)$$

The complexity of many-body Schrödinger equation is that, for a system with ‘N’ electrons, there would be $3N$ degrees of freedom which increases the number of variable in the problem. Density Functional Theory resolves this issue by apprxomating the many-body problem to a single electronic density which is computationally viable.

2.3 Density Based Approximations

Thomas-Fermi Approach

Thomas and Fermi proposed that, the total energy of a system can be written as a functional of the electron density rather than considering the single particle eigen functions proposed by Hartree and Hartree-Fock approaches.^{16,17} Therefore, the kinetic energy of an ‘N’ interacting electrons can be expressed in terms of the electron density ($n(\vec{r})$) as in Eq. 2.18. Then the total energy (E) can be expressed as a functional of electron density as in Eq. 2.19 where, the kinetic energy, electrostatic energy and external potential are expressed as a functional of electron density.

$$T_{TF} = C_k \int n(\vec{r})^{5/3} d^3r \quad (2.18)$$

$$E = C_k \int n(\vec{r})^{5/3} d^3r + \int \hat{V}_{ext}(\vec{r})n(\vec{r}) + \frac{1}{2} \iint \frac{e^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{n(\vec{r}')n(\vec{r})}{|r - r'|} d^3r d^3r' \quad (2.19)$$

Then by proceeding with the Lagrangian multiplier method, the above equation can be minimized.¹⁸ However a drawback is that, this approach does not include the electron exchange. Although it was addressed by Dirac by including the exchange interaction and correlation functional but, the shell structure and behaviour of atoms in complex systems could not be established.^{19,20}

Hohenberg-Kohn Approach

Hohenberg and Kohn devised two theorems which are at the core of Density Functional Theory.²¹ The two theorems are stated below.

Theorem I:

“The external potential $\hat{V}_{ext}(\vec{r})$, and hence the total energy, is a unique functional of the electron density $n(\vec{r})$.”

The energy functional as established in the theorem above can be expressed in terms of the external potential as in Eq. 2.20 where, $F[n(\vec{r})]$ is an unknown universal functional of the electron density $n(\vec{r})$.

$$E[n(\vec{r})] = \int \hat{V}_{ext}(\vec{r})n(\vec{r})dr + F[n(\vec{r})] \quad (2.20)$$

$$E[n(\vec{r})] = \langle \psi | \hat{H} | \psi \rangle \quad (2.21)$$

Assuming that a non-degenerate ground state exists, a Hamiltonian (presented in Eq. 2.22) can be designed corresponding to the total energy functional (presented in Eq. 2.20) such that, the eigen function minimizes the expectation value (presented in Eq. 2.21) giving the ground state of the system.

$$\hat{H} = \hat{F} + \hat{V}_{ext} \quad (2.22)$$

$$\hat{F} = \hat{T}_e + \hat{V}_{e,e} \quad (2.23)$$

Where, the electronic Hamiltonian \hat{F} consists the kinetic energy and electron-electron interaction potential as presented in Eq. 2.23. This is identical to every ‘ N ’ electron system such that, the Hamiltonian is completely described by ‘ N ’ electrons and external potential $\hat{V}_{ext}(\vec{r})$.

Consider two unique external potentials, ${}^1\hat{V}_{ext}(\vec{r})$ and ${}^2\hat{V}_{ext}(\vec{r})$ which would result into identical electron density $n(\vec{r})$. Then, the corresponding Hamiltonians ${}^1\hat{H}$ and ${}^2\hat{H}$ would lead to unique ground states ${}^1\psi$ and ${}^2\psi$ respectively such that the corresponding electron density is $n(\vec{r})$. Then by applying variational principle and using Eq. 2.23 we get;

$$\begin{aligned} {}^1E_0 < \langle {}^2\psi | {}^1\hat{H} | {}^2\psi \rangle &= \langle {}^2\psi | {}^2\hat{H} | {}^2\psi \rangle + \langle {}^2\psi | {}^1\hat{H} - {}^2\hat{H} | {}^2\psi \rangle \\ &= {}^2E_0 + \int n(\vec{r}) [{}^1\hat{V}_{ext}(\vec{r}) - {}^2\hat{V}_{ext}(\vec{r})] dr \end{aligned} \quad (2.24)$$

$${}^2E_0 < {}^1E_0 + \int n(\vec{r}) [{}^1\hat{V}_{ext}(\vec{r}) - {}^2\hat{V}_{ext}(\vec{r})] dr \quad (2.25)$$

$${}^1E_0 + {}^2E_0 < {}^2E_0 + {}^1E_0 \quad (2.26)$$

Where, 1E_0 and 2E_0 are the ground state energies corresponding to the Hamiltonians ${}^1\hat{H}$ and ${}^2\hat{H}$ respectively. Adding Eq. 2.24 and Eq. 2.25 we get Eq. 2.26 which contradicts our assumptions and proves that, there can be only one external potential \hat{V}_{ext} which uniquely determines the ground state density $n(\vec{r})$ and vice-versa.

Theorem II:

“The groundstate energy can be obtained variationally: the density that minimises the total energy is the exact groundstate density.”

The eigen functions of ‘ N ’ particle system is governed by the Hamiltonian \hat{H} which is governed by the external potential \hat{V}_{ext} and the number of particles, off which the external potential is governed by the electron density $n(\vec{r})$ as evident from Theorem I. This indicates that, the eigen function is a functional of the electron density $n(\vec{r})$, this implies that the expectation value of \hat{F} is also a functional of the electron density $n(\vec{r})$ as evident from Eq. 2.27.

$$F[n(\vec{r})] = \langle \psi | \hat{F} | \psi \rangle \quad (2.27)$$

Consider an energy functional $E_x[n(\vec{r})]$ (presented in Eq. 2.28) wherein the external potential \hat{V}_{ext} is independent of an unknown electron density $n'(\vec{r})$.

$$E_x[n(\vec{r})] = \int \hat{V}_{ext}(\vec{r})n'(\vec{r})dr + F[n'(\vec{r})] \quad (2.28)$$

Then according to the variational principle,

$$\langle \psi' | \hat{F} | \psi' \rangle + \langle \psi' | \hat{V}_{ext}(\vec{r}) | \psi' \rangle > \langle \psi | \hat{F} | \psi \rangle + \langle \psi | \hat{V}_{ext}(\vec{r}) | \psi \rangle \quad (2.29)$$

Where, ψ is the eigen function corresponding to the correct ground state electron density $n(\vec{r})$. This gives us;

$$\int n'(\vec{r})\hat{V}_{ext}(\vec{r})dr + F[n'(\vec{r})] > \int n(\vec{r})\hat{V}_{ext}(\vec{r})dr + F[n(\vec{r})] \quad (2.30)$$

Then, following the variational principle we arrive at;

$$E_x[n'(\vec{r})] > E_x[n(\vec{r})] \quad (2.31)$$

This implies that, the ground state energy and the corresponding electron density $n(\vec{r})$ is lower than any other electron density $n'(\vec{r})$. The above variational principle is known as the Hohenberg-Kohn theorem wherein, The universal functional $\hat{F}[n(\vec{r})]$ yields the lowest energy state if and only if the input electron density is the true ground state electron density $n(\vec{r})$.

Kohn-Sham Approach

The Kohn-Sham approach established Density Functional Theory as a practical tool to obtain the ground state of a system.²² In this approach, the electron density $n(\vec{r})$ is parametrized into one electron orbital $\zeta_i(\vec{r})$ (where summation is over all the occupied states) as in Eq. 2.32 with the total energy functional expressed as in Eq. 2.33.

$$n(\vec{r}) = \sum_i \zeta_i^*(\vec{r})\zeta_i(\vec{r}) \quad (2.32)$$

$$E[n(\vec{r})] = T[n(\vec{r})] + E_H[n(\vec{r})] + E_{xc}[n(\vec{r})] + E_{ext}[n(\vec{r})] \quad (2.33)$$

Here, E_H is the electron-electron interaction under Hartree approximation, E_{ext} is the external potential and the kinetic energy of the non-interacting electrons in $\zeta_i(\vec{r})$ are given as follows;

$$E_H[n(\vec{r})] = \iint \frac{n(\vec{r})n(\vec{r}')}{|\vec{r} - \vec{r}'|} d\vec{r}d\vec{r}' \quad (2.34)$$

$$E_{ext}[n(\vec{r})] = \int \hat{V}_{ext}n(\vec{r})d\vec{r} \quad (2.35)$$

$$T[n(\vec{r})] = \sum_i \int \zeta_i^*(\vec{r}) \left(-\frac{1}{2}\nabla^2 \right) \zeta_i(\vec{r}) d^3r \quad (2.36)$$

The remaining quantity in Eq. 2.33 is known as the exchange-correlation energy $E_{xc}[n(\vec{r})]$. As the single electron orbitals $\zeta_i(\vec{r})$ are variational quantities, the variation of the total energy functional with respect to these orbitals $\zeta_i^*(\vec{r})$ would result into an effective single electron equation known as the Kohn-Sham equation, presented in Eq. 2.37 below.

$$\left(-\frac{1}{2}\nabla^2 + \int \frac{n(\vec{r}')}{|\vec{r} - \vec{r}'|} d\vec{r}' + \hat{V}_{ext}[n(\vec{r})] + \frac{\delta E_{xc}[n(\vec{r})]}{\delta n(\vec{r})} \right) \zeta_i(\vec{r}) = \epsilon_i \zeta_i(\vec{r}) \quad (2.37)$$

The Kohn-Sham equation for electrons in a potential are given by Eq. 2.38 where, the exchange-correlation potential is obtained by the variation of exchange-correlation energy as presented in Eq. 2.39.

$$V_{eff}(\vec{r}) = V_{ext}(\vec{r}) + \int \frac{n(\vec{r}')}{|\vec{r} - \vec{r}'|} d^3r' + V_{xc}[n(\vec{r})] \quad (2.38)$$

$$V_{xc}[n(\vec{r})] = \frac{\delta E_{xc}[n(\vec{r})]}{\delta n(\vec{r})} \quad (2.39)$$

Therefore, the modified form of the Kohn-Sham equation is as follows;

$$\left(-\frac{1}{2}\nabla^2 + V_{eff}(\vec{r}) \right) \zeta_i(\vec{r}) = \epsilon_i \zeta_i(\vec{r}) \quad (2.40)$$

Here, ϵ_i are the Lagrange parameters introduced to retain the orthogonality of the single-particle Kohn-Sham orbitals as follows;

$$\int \zeta_i^*(\vec{r}) \zeta_j(\vec{r}) d^3r = \delta_{ij} \quad (2.41)$$

2.4 Exchange and Correlation Functionals

The exchange and correlation functionals in Kohn-Sham approach define the accuracy of calculations and outcomes. Since the theory was established, several functionals have been developed with a goal to predict chemically accurate results. Broadly, they can be classified and understood in terms of the Jacob's ladder wherein the computational cost increases as we move up the rungs towards a chemically accurate picture of the system under investigation. The exchange and correlation functionals are required to follow certain constraints i.e., (i) these functionals show be slow varying densities and should reduce to homogenous two dimensional electron gas limit, (ii) they should be asymptotic for atoms/molecules (i.e., $V_{xc}[n(\vec{r})] \rightarrow -\frac{1}{\vec{r}}$ for $\vec{r} \rightarrow \infty$) and (iii) they should not be self-interacting. These functionals can be classified as, local, semi-local and non-local functionals.

Local Density Approximation

Local density approximation and local spin-density approximations are presented in Eq. 2.42 and 2.43 respectively.²¹ These are known as local functionals since, the exchange energy functional depends on the electron density and spin at some point \vec{r} in the electron cloud of the atom.

$$E_{xc}^{LDA}[n(\vec{r})] = \int \epsilon_{xc}[n(\vec{r})]n(\vec{r})d^3r \quad (2.42)$$

$$E_{xc}^{LSDA}[n_{\uparrow}(\vec{r}), n_{\downarrow}(\vec{r})] = \int \epsilon_{xc}[n_{\uparrow}(\vec{r}), n_{\downarrow}(\vec{r})]n(\vec{r})d^3r \quad (2.43)$$

Generalized Gradient Approximation

Generalised gradient approximation and generalised spin-gradient approximations are presented in Eq. 2.44 and 2.45 respectively.^{23,24} These functionals are known as semi-local functionals since, the energy functional depends on the electron density and their gradients at some point \vec{r} and its neighbourhood. One of the well known and most widely used semi-local functional is PBE.

$$E_{xc}^{GGA}[n(\vec{r})] = \int \epsilon_{xc}[n(\vec{r}), \nabla n(\vec{r})]n(\vec{r})d^3r \quad (2.44)$$

$$E_{xc}^{GSGA}[n_{\uparrow}(\vec{r}), n_{\downarrow}(\vec{r})] = \int \epsilon_{xc}[n_{\uparrow}(\vec{r}), n_{\downarrow}(\vec{r}), \nabla n_{\uparrow}(\vec{r}), \nabla n_{\downarrow}(\vec{r})]n(\vec{r})d^3r \quad (2.45)$$

When the kinetic energy densities (presented in Eq. 2.36) are included, we arrive at another semi-local functional, the meta-generalised gradient approximation (presented generally as in Eq. 2.46).^{25,26} In such functionals, apart from the gradients, we also consider the Laplacians of density. Although, these functionals exhibit divergent nature when applied on diatomic systems but, they are useful to identify the type of bond in the system i.e., covalent or metallic. Some of the frequently used functionals are TPSS and SCAN.

$$E_{xc}^{meta-GGA}[n_{\uparrow}(\vec{r}), n_{\downarrow}(\vec{r})] = \int \epsilon_{xc}[n_{\uparrow}(\vec{r}), n_{\downarrow}(\vec{r}), \nabla n_{\uparrow}(\vec{r}), \nabla n_{\downarrow}(\vec{r}), \nabla^2 n_{\uparrow}(\vec{r}), \nabla^2 n_{\downarrow}(\vec{r})]n(\vec{r})d^3r \quad (2.46)$$

Hybrid Approximation

Hybrid functionals are a class of non-local functionals which are computationally quite expensive but, preferred over other approximations since they provide chemically accurate results.²⁷ In such functionals the energy functional depends on the density or orbitals everywhere in the electron cloud of the atom. The advantage of such functionals are; (i) we can get rid of the self-interaction term and (ii) we can get correct asymptotic form i.e., $-\frac{1}{\vec{r}}$ for large \vec{r} . The simple solution is to establish a exchange correlation energy functional as in Eq. 2.47. But, this has mathematical problem of error cancellation in LDA and GGA i.e., the error of exchange in LDA and correlation in LDA cancel each other with the errors in LDA correlation being quite large as compared to the exact exchange. So the solution is achieved by introducing a mixing parameter ($\alpha; 0 < \alpha < 1$) which modifies Eq. 2.47 into Eq. 2.48 which takes the form of Eq. 2.49 for the PBE0 functional (one of the first hybrid functionals).

$$E_{xc}^{hybrid}[n(\vec{r})] = E_x^{exact}[n(\vec{r})] + E_c^{LDA/GGA}[n(\vec{r})] \quad (2.47)$$

$$E_{xc}^{hybrid}[n(\vec{r})] = \alpha E_x^{exact}[n(\vec{r})] + (1 - \alpha)E_x^{GGA}[n(\vec{r})] + E_c^{GGA}[n(\vec{r})] \quad (2.48)$$

$$E_{xc}^{hybrid}[n(\vec{r})] = \frac{1}{4}E_x^{exact}[n(\vec{r})] + \frac{3}{4}E_x^{GGA}[n(\vec{r})] + E_c^{GGA}[n(\vec{r})] \quad (2.49)$$

2.5 Electronic Approximations

Pseudopotentials

The Kohn-Sham orbitals used to express the single particle density can be expanded into a basis set such as a plane wave basis set based on the Bloch theorem (as in Eq. 2.50 below) which is appropriate to describe the electrons in a periodic potential observed in solids.²⁸ Also, as the kinetic energy operator is diagonal in a plane wave basis set and the potential in real space, we can utilize fast Fourier transforms for switching between the representations which reduces the computational cost.²⁹

$$\psi_k^n(\vec{r}) = \sum_{\vec{K}} c_{\vec{K}}^{n,k} e^{i(\vec{k}+\vec{K})\vec{r}} \quad (2.50)$$

However, the major disadvantage of a plane wave basis set is its inefficiency since, the number of basis sets required to describe atomic eigen functions close to nucleus would be enormous. This difficulty is addressed by the implementation of pseudopotentials representing the potential of ionic core and the core electrons since, the materials properties (physical or chemical) are governed largely by the valence electrons only. This is subject to certain criteria such as, (i) valence eigen functions should remain unchanged outside the core region r_c , (ii) pseudo eigen function within the core should match exactly at the boundary, (iii) pseudo eigen function and its first derivative should

Figure 2.1: A schematic representation of pseudopotential. Adopted from *Phys. Rev. B.*, **50**, 17953-17979, (1994).

be continuous at the boundary and (iv) the pseudo eigen function is nodeless within the core region. These conditions are graphically presented in Fig. 2.1 where, the eigen function of a coulomb potential of the nucleus is presented in blue and the pseudo eigen function in red.³⁰ The real and pseudo eigen functions along with the potentials match beyond certain cut-off radius known as the core radius r_c .

$$\psi = \tilde{\psi} + \sum_i^n c_i \phi_i - \sum_i^n c_i \tilde{\phi}_i \quad (2.51)$$

Pseudopotentials of different classes have been developed over the years, for example, norm-conserving, ultra-soft, projector-augmented wave method etc.^{31–33} Especially, the projector-augmented wave method is a significant improvement over the original techniques since it is an all-electron eigen function which consists of three parts as presented in Eq. 2.51 where, $\tilde{\psi}$ is the pseudo eigen function, ϕ_i is the all electron partial eigen function, $\tilde{\phi}_i$ is pseudo partial eigen function. Here, the pseudo eigen functions are represented by the plane waves which provide a good description of the eigen functions in regions far away from the ion core but deviates significantly from the all electron eigen functions near the ionic core. Thus, the all electron eigen functions in Eq. 2.51 are introduced to account for this error.

van der Waals Corrections

Under the standard framework of local density approximation or the generalised gradient approximation in density functional theory, the description of long-range dispersion forces are not accurately incorporated. This is necessary to compute the adsorption properties of molecules over surfaces and interfaces. To solve this issue, Grimme proposed a semi-empirical van der Waals correction method famously known as the D2 and D3 correction which accurately incorporate the long-range dispersion forces into the standard density functional theory.^{34–36} The total energy of the Kohn-Sham system (E_{KS}) solved under the self-consistent field theory is corrected by incorporating the van der Waals correction term (E_{disp}) as presented in Eq. 2.52.

$$E_{DFT+D2/D3} = E_{KS} + E_{disp} \quad (2.52)$$

In the D2 scheme; a semi-empirical dispersion potential ($C_6 R^{-6}$) and damping function (f_{damp} , at small atomic distances) are added to the Kohn-Sham energy in the form of a correction term presented in Eq. 2.53.

$$E_{disp} = -S_6 \sum_{i=1}^{N_{at}-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^{N_{at}} \frac{C_6^{ij}}{R_{ij}^6} f_{damp}(R_{ij}) \quad (2.53)$$

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Whereas, in the D3 scheme, two-body ($E^{(2)}$) and three-body ($E^{(3)}$) energies sum-up forming the dispersion correction term E_{disp} which is incorporated into the Kohn-Sham energy wherein the terms ($E^{(2)}$) and ($E^{(3)}$) are presented in Eq. 2.54 and 2.55 respectively.

$$E^{(2)} = \sum_{AB} \sum_{\substack{n=2m \\ m=1,2,3,\dots}} S_n \frac{C_n^{AB}}{r_{AB}^n} f_{d,n}(r_{AB}) \quad (2.54)$$

$$E^{(3)} = \sum_{ABC} f_{d,(3)}(r_{ABC}) E^{(ABC)} \quad (2.55)$$

The global scaling factors S_n and S_6 in Eq. 2.53 and 2.54 depends explicitly on the exchange-correlation functional (i.e., for generalised gradient approximation functional such as PBE; $S_6 = 1.00$ and $S_8 = 0.72$). In equations above, C_6^{ij} and C_n^{AB} represent the n^{th} order dispersion coefficients for each ‘ ij ’ and ‘ AB ’ pair of atoms with interatomic distances R_{ij} and r_{AB} respectively. The damping functions (f_{damp} and $f_{d,n}$) are included to avoid singularities at small distances R_{ij} and r_{AB} with r_{ABC} as the average radii of a triple atom system ‘ ABC ’ with $E^{(ABC)}$ representing a non-additive triple dipole dispersion term.

2.6 Lattice Dynamics, Elastic Constants and AIMD

Density Functional Perturbation Theory

To understand the structure, binding of atoms and ultimately the dynamical stability of a system, it is necessary to understand the vibrational energies and the displacement patterns which are known as the electronically excited states. Experimentally this is achieved by performing IR and Raman spectroscopy. Hence, theoretically these phenomena can be addressed by the density functional perturbation theory wherein, the lattice dynamics of a material are investigated which governs, polarizability, phonons, IR and Raman spectra, superconductivity etc.^{37–41} This is done by slightly perturbing the system from its ground state. Mathematically, this is achieved by taking the derivatives of the density functional theory electronic energies with respect to different perturbations.

$$V_{\lambda,ext}(\vec{r}) = V_{ext}(\vec{r}) + \lambda \frac{\partial V_{ext}(\vec{r})}{\partial \lambda} + \frac{1}{2} \lambda^2 \frac{\partial^2 V_{ext}(\vec{r})}{\partial \lambda^2} + \dots \quad (2.56)$$

$$n_{\lambda}(\vec{r}) = n(\vec{r}) + \lambda \frac{\partial n(\vec{r})}{\partial \lambda} + \frac{1}{2} \lambda^2 \frac{\partial^2 n(\vec{r})}{\partial \lambda^2} + \dots \quad (2.57)$$

$$E_\lambda(\vec{r}) = E(\vec{r}) + \lambda \frac{\partial E(\vec{r})}{\partial \lambda} + \frac{1}{2} \lambda^2 \frac{\partial^2 E(\vec{r})}{\partial \lambda^2} + \dots \quad (2.58)$$

In principle, we apply linear response theory to Kohn-Sham equations and observe the corresponding changes in the solution of electron densities under small perturbations. Therefore, V_{ext} , E , $n(\vec{r})$ etc. are subjected to perturbations in density functional perturbation theory. We can expand the external potential into a Taylor series in terms of some parameter γ as presented in Eq. 2.56. Similarly, we can expand the electron density $n(\vec{r})$ and the energy functional E as presented in Eq. 2.57 and 2.58 respectively.

In Eq. 2.58, $\frac{\partial E(\vec{r})}{\partial \lambda} = \int n(\vec{r}) \frac{\partial V_{ext}(\vec{r})}{\partial \lambda}$ indicates that, the first order term in the expansion of the energy functional does not depend on the derivative of the electron density $n(\vec{r})$. However, the second order term has an explicit dependence on the first order derivative of the electron density. Hence, we proceed with the second order term of the energy functional expansion to compute the dynamical matrices for phonon frequencies and effective Born charges.³⁷⁻⁴¹ The energy functional in terms of the electron density is presented in Eq. 2.59. Then the second order term of the energy functional is obtained by variational principle (presented in Eq. 2.60) with respect to the first order eigen functions provided, the first order eigen functions are orthogonal to the ground state eigen functions (as presented in Eq. 2.61).

$$E[\psi] = \psi_{min}^{(1)} \sum_{i \in occ} \langle \psi_i | T + V_{ext} | \psi_i \rangle + E_{H,xc}[n] \quad (2.59)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^2 E(\vec{r})}{\partial \lambda^2} = \psi_{min}^{(1)} \sum_{i \in occ} & \left[\langle \psi_i^{(1)} | H^{(0)} - \epsilon_i^{(0)} | \psi_i^{(1)} \rangle + \langle \psi_i^{(1)} | V_{ext}^{(1)} | \psi_i^{(0)} \rangle + \langle \psi_i^{(0)} | V_{ext}^{(1)} | \psi_i^{(1)} \rangle + \right. \\ & \left. \langle \psi_i^{(0)} | V_{ext}^{(2)} | \psi_i^{(0)} \rangle \right] + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\delta^2 E_{H,xc}}{\delta n(\vec{r}) \delta n(\vec{r}')} \Big|_{n^{(0)}} n^{(1)}(\vec{r}) n^{(1)}(\vec{r}') d^3 \vec{r} d^3 \vec{r}' \\ & + \int \left(\frac{d}{d\lambda} \frac{\delta E_{H,xc}}{\delta n(\vec{r})} \Big|_{n^{(0)}} n^{(1)}(\vec{r}) d^3 \vec{r} \right) \frac{1}{2} \frac{d^2 E_{H,xc}}{d\lambda^2} \Big|_{n^{(0)}} \end{aligned} \quad (2.60)$$

$$\langle \psi_i^{(0)} | \psi_j^{(j)} \rangle = 0 \quad (2.61)$$

The resulting dynamical matrices are Hermitian i.e., the constituent eigen values $\omega_j^2(\vec{q})$ and eigen vectors/functions $\xi_j(\vec{q})$ would be real and orthonormal respectively. In such scenarios, the phonon dispersions correspond to the phonon density of states which gives information about the entire brillouin zone.

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The whole phonon dispersion spectra can be obtained by matrix diagonalization ($D_{\alpha\beta}$) spanning over the three dimensional space of the wave vector \vec{q} in the entire brillouin zone.³⁸⁻⁴¹ The resultant phonon density of states is determined by summation over every phonon state and is given as in Eq. 2.62 below where, D' is the normalization constant such that, $\int g(\omega)d\omega = 1$; with $g(\omega)d\omega$ as a fraction of phonons with energies in the range ω to $\omega + d\omega$.³⁷⁻⁴¹

$$g(\omega) = D' \int_{BZ} \sum_j \delta(\omega - \omega_j(q))dq = D' \int_{BZ} \sum_{j,p} \delta(\omega - \omega_j(q))dq_p \quad (2.62)$$

Here, the mesh indices ' p ' are characterized by the wave vectors ' \vec{q} ' in the discrete irreducible brillouin zone where, dq_p gives the weight factor corresponding to the volume of the p^{th} mesh in the \vec{q} space.

Elastic Properties

Apart from the spectral properties (which can be computed under the density functional perturbation theory) the mechanical properties of materials are of great relevance since they give information regarding the nature of the material and its practical applicability. This is achieved by computing the elastic constants of materials which can be performed when the ground state structure in equilibrium configuration is known.

The system is perturbed from its equilibrium position by application of discrete strain fields and the corresponding atomic positions are relaxed. The numerical derivative of energy with respect to such strain gives the stress corresponding to the strained lattice. Therefore, stress as a function of strain is obtained, through which the elastic properties of a material can be determined by Birch-Murnaghan curve fitting.^{42,43} The elastic constants corresponding to the second derivative of energy with respect to the strain tensor for a unit volume are presented in Eq. 2.63 where, ϵ_{kl} and σ_{ij} are the components of strain and stress tensors respectively.

$$C_{ijkl} = \frac{\sigma_{ij}}{\epsilon_{kl}} \quad (2.63)$$

The tensor C_{ijkl} is a 6×6 matrix comprising of the independent elastic constants, C_{ij} which is determined by the crystal symmetry. Therefore, the bulk, shear and, young's modulus can be calculated by applying different averaging approaches such as the one proposed by, Reuss, Voigt and Hill. Under the Voigt and Reuss averaging approach we can compute the bulk and shear modulus as presented in Eq. 2.64, 2.65 and 2.66, 2.67 respectively.

$$B_V = \frac{1}{9}[(c_{11} + c_{22} + c_{33}) + 2(c_{12} + c_{23} + c_{13})] \quad (2.64)$$

$$G_V = \frac{1}{15}[(c_{11} + c_{22} + c_{33}) - (c_{12} + c_{23} + c_{13}) + 3(c_{44} + c_{55} + c_{66})] \quad (2.65)$$

$$B_R = \frac{1}{9}[(\sigma_{11} + \sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}) + 2(\sigma_{12} + \sigma_{13} + \sigma_{23})] \quad (2.66)$$

$$G_V = \frac{1}{15}[(\sigma_{11} + \sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}) - (\sigma_{12} + \sigma_{13} + \sigma_{23}) + 3(\sigma_{44} + \sigma_{55} + \sigma_{66})] \quad (2.67)$$

Hill proposed that, Voigt and Reuss averaging approaches serve as upper and lower limits of the elastic moduli respectively. Therefore, the Hill averaged approach gives bulk and shear modulus as presented in Eq. 2.68 and 2.69. Then using the bulk and shear moduli we can obtain other elastic moduli such as the young's modulus \mathcal{E} and the poisson ratio ρ as presented in Eq. 2.70 and 2.71 respectively.

$$B_H = \frac{1}{2}(B_V + B_R) \quad (2.68)$$

$$G_H = \frac{1}{2}(G_V + G_R) \quad (2.69)$$

$$\mathcal{E} = \frac{9B_H G_H}{3B_H + G_H} \quad (2.70)$$

$$\rho = \frac{3B_H - 2G_H}{2(3B_H + G_H)} \quad (2.71)$$

Apart from the mechanical properties which can be extracted from the equations above, we can also comment about the mechanical stability of materials based on the Born-Huang criteria for the bulk and low dimensional materials which talk about the material stability in terms of the elastic tensors.⁴⁴ This is important because, a crystal system cannot exist in a stable or a meta-stable phase if their elastic tensors do not obey the Born-Huang stability criteria. For example, the stability criteria for a bulk cubic system are presented in Eq. 2.72 and for a low dimensional hexagonal system are presented in Eq. 2.73.^{45,46}

$$c_{11} + 2c_{12} > 0; c_{44} > 0; c_{11} - c_{12} > 0 \quad (2.72)$$

$$c_{11} > 0; c_{11} - c_{12} > 0; c_{66} > 0 \quad (2.73)$$

ab-initio Molecular Dynamics

Classical molecular dynamics simulations deviate from the quantum mechanical approach, making it reliable for prediction of dynamics on meso-scopic scales. However, ab-initio molecular dynamics originates from a different approach and is used to get insights into the effects of temperature and the structural stability of materials. It exploits the fact that, atomic motions in periodic potentials obey Newtons second law of motion. So, rather than computing forces from classical mechanics, in ab-initio method, the forces are computed from ground state electron density obtained by the density functional theory. This makes ab-initio method highly accurate as compared to the coarsed approach of classical molecular dynamics, although, the disadvantage is associated computational cost. Hence, ab-initio method is just confined to a few hundred atoms. However, for for relatively simple systems, this method is quite feasible with proper balance in accuracy and computational time. In this thesis we employ, ab-initio molecular dynamics to estimate the structural properties of material at a particular temperature. This is achieved by a proper choice of thermostat out of, Gaussian, simple velocity rescaling, Berendsen, Bussi-Donadio-Parrinello, Andersen etc.⁴⁷⁻⁵⁰

In the Gaussian thermostat, the instantaneous temperature is exactly equal to the target temperature which is achieved by modifying the force as, $F = F_{interaction} + F_{constraint}$, where $F_{interaction}$ is the typical interactions force computed during simulation and $F_{constraint}$ is a Lagrangian multiplier such that, the kinetic energy is constant. Such a thermostat does not sample the canonical distribution rather it samples the isokinetic. Hence, the position-dependent (structural) properties can be obtained using this thermostat but not the velocity-dependent (dynamical) properties.⁴⁷

The simple velocity rescaling thermostat is a non-physical thermostat although it is the easiest to implement. In this scheme, the particle momentum is rescaled in such a way that, the instanteneous temperature correlates to the target temperature similar to the Gaussian thermostat which leads to isokinetic ensemble. However, this scheme fails to properly sample the isokinetic ensemble so it is not recommended. Berendsen thermostat is a weak coupling thermostat the simple velocity rescaling thermostat. However, since it samples neither canonical nor the isokinetic distribution, it is not recommended.⁴⁷

Bussi-Donadio-Parrinello thermostat is also known as, Canonical Sampling through Velocity Rescaling. In such a thermostat, the rescaling is done to kinetic energy which is stochastically selected from the kinetic energy distribution under the canonical ensemble scheme. Hence, this thermostat properly samples canonical ensemble and similar to the Berendsen thermostat, a time coupling parameter can be introduced to vary the velocity rescaling. This thermostat is reliable since the choice of time coupling constant does not affect structural properties and dynamical properties.⁴⁹

Andersen thermostat selects particles randomly and facilitates a collision among them in a heat bath wherein the particle attains new velocity governed by the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution. Such a thermostat can easily reproduce a canonical ensemble. Hence, it can be used to account for the structural properties of the material. We implement this thermostat in our ab-initio molecular dynamics to ascertain the structural stability of low dimensional systems.⁵⁰

2.7 Boltzmann Transport Theory

Transport properties of materials are governed by the response of carriers (such as, electrons or phonons) to external fields such as electric, magnetic or temperature gradient. Such carrier motion gives rise to finite electric or thermal conductivity owing to the exchange of energy and momentum due to scattering from crystal impurities under the influence of external fields.

Boltzmann transport theory deals with various transport parameters such as, the Seebeck coefficient, electrical conductivity, and electronic thermal conductivity.⁵¹ These parameters are computed by solving the semi-classical Boltzmann transport equation which considers various external parameters effecting the transport properties of a material in the constant relaxation time approximation regime.⁵¹ These equation have to be solved iteratively to compute the electron, phonon contributions to the thermoelectric properties. We begin with a distribution function $f(r,k,t)$ which defines, the number of carriers in state ' k ' around a point ' r ' at time ' t '. Such a distribution function can change over time by the virtue of, (i) diffusion, (ii) influence of external fields and, (iii) scattering/collisions. The evolution of such a system can be determined by computing the time derivative which leads to the semi-classical Boltzmann transport equation presented in Eq. 2.74 which reduces to Eq. 2.75 in case of a steady state system where, the net rate of change of distribution function $f(r,k,t)$ is zero. These equations

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are solved by following different approximations, off which the relaxation time approximation is the most reliable technique.

$$\frac{f(r, k, t)}{\partial t} = -v_k \frac{\partial f_k}{\partial r} - k \frac{\partial f(r, k, t)}{\partial k} - \frac{f(r, k, t) - f^0(r, k, t)}{\tau_k} \quad (2.74)$$

$$-v_k \frac{\partial f_k}{\partial r} - k \frac{\partial f(r, k, t)}{\partial k} - \frac{f(r, k, t) - f^0(r, k, t)}{\tau_k} = 0 \quad (2.75)$$

The energy conversion (from thermal to electrical and vice-versa) efficiency of a material is quantified by the figure of merit presented in Eq. 2.76 where, ‘ S ’ is Seebeck coefficient, ‘ σ ’ is the electrical conductivity, ‘ T ’ is temperature, ‘ κ_e ’ and ‘ κ_l ’ are the electronic and lattice contributions of thermal conductivity respectively. The electronic contribution to thermoelectrics is computed using the Boltzmann transport equations whereas the lattice contributions are computed using the phonon Boltzmann transport equation wherein the third order phonon scattering effects are incorporated. This is implemented in the ShengBTE code.

$$zT = \left(\frac{S^2 \sigma}{\kappa_e + \kappa_l} \right) T \quad (2.76)$$

The electronic contributions to thermoelectric transport properties are computed by extrapolating the electronic band dispersion energies under Fourier expansion. This is done under the constant relaxation time approximation wherein the Seebeck coefficient of the system is independent of the scattering rates.⁵² However, one issue is that, the electrical conductivity (σ) and the electronic thermal conductivity (κ_e) are computed as a function of the relaxation time (τ). Similarly, the lattice contribution to thermal conductivity (κ_l) is computed in terms of the third order interatomic force constants since, the second order interatomic force constants under harmonic approximation neglect the crystal anharmonicity. Further, the deformation potential theory is implemented to compute transport parameters independent of the relaxation time as proposed by Bardeen and Shokley, wherein the carrier mobility (μ) can be used to estimate the relaxation time (τ) as presented in Eq. 2.77 and 2.78 respectively, where, C_{ii} are the elastic constants and E_1 is the deformation potential constant.⁵³ The later is computed by subjecting the system to strain of the form $\pm\delta(x)$ and the corresponding valence band maxima ($E^{(VBM)}$) and conduction band minima ($E^{(CBM)}$) energies are computed from the electronic dispersion relation to incorporate the hole and electron dependent properties respectively.⁵³ However, these band energies are corrected and realigned with respect to the core energy ($E^{(core)}$) at the corresponding strain. The plot of these aligned eigen values with

strain is linear in nature wherein, on linear fit; the slope represents the deformation potential constant.

$$\mu = \frac{(8\pi)^{1/2} \hbar^4 e C_{ii}}{(m^*)^{5/2} (k_B T)^{3/2} E_1^2} \quad (2.77)$$

$$\tau = \frac{\mu m^*}{e} \quad (2.78)$$

Thermally activated electrons and holes are vital in transport phenomena of inorganic materials since they exhibit highly coherent wavelengths longer than the lattice constant with the magnitudes close to the acoustic phonon mode at the center of Brillouin zone.⁵⁴ The dimensional quantum confinement is known to alter the transport properties and the associated dynamics such as, electron-phonon coupling and scattering mechanisms. Hence, it is necessary to incorporate these scenarios by extending the deformation potential theory to low dimensional materials which was proposed by Bardeen and Shockley.^{52,55,56} It was eventually shown that, the carrier mobilities explicitly demonstrate the effects of dimensional quantum confinement.⁵⁷⁻⁵⁹

2.8 Topological Properties

The topological properties in terms of, \mathbb{Z}_2 invariant, slab-band structures, angle resolved photoemission spectroscopy etc. lie at the core of investigations performed in this thesis. These properties can be obtained by transforming the plane wave basis set in the reciprocal space to maximally localised Wannier functions in real space. This helps generate the tight-binding model which is used to obtain the required properties. Here we discuss various methods which are developed to compute the said topological properties, beginning from the theory of maximally localised Wannier functions, *Berry* connection and the *Berry* curvature, spin Hall conductivity, the tight-binding Hamiltonian model, Wannier charge centers, methods to compute \mathbb{Z}_2 invariants etc.

Maximally Localised Wannier Functions

The maximally localised Wannier functions approach was developed by Marzari and Vanderbilt to transform the eigen functions from spanning the reciprocal space to be localised in real space.^{60,61} In a typical *first-principles* calculation, the electronic structure of periodic systems

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defined by the extended Bloch states for n^{th} band with crystal momentum ' k ' as ψ_{nk} . However, Marzari and Vanderbilt gave an alternate approach wherein, the spatially localised wannier functions centred at a crystal lattice site R , $\omega_n R(\vec{r})$ are represented in terms of the Bloch states as presented in Eq. 2.79 where, V is the unit cell volume, $U^{(k)}$ is a unitary matrix to mix the Bloch states at each crystal momentum ' k '. Since, the unitary matrix $U^{(k)}$ is not uniquely defined, different choice of such matrix would lead to different spacial localisation of the wannier functions.

$$\omega_n R(\vec{r}) = \frac{V}{(2\pi)^3} \int_{BZ} \left[\sum_m U_{mn}^{(k)} \psi_{mk}(\vec{r}) \right] e^{-k \cdot R} dk \quad (2.79)$$

The spread (Ω) of a wannier function is presented in Eq. 2.80 such that, it can be decoupled into a gauge invariant term (Ω_I) and a term ($\tilde{\Omega}$) which depends on the gauge choice of $U^{(k)}$. The latter can be further decomposed into diagonal (Ω_D) and off-diagonal (Ω_{OD}) terms constituting the wannier functions as presented in Eq. 2.81.

$$\Omega = \sum_n \left[\langle \omega_{n0}(\vec{r}) | \vec{r}^2 | \omega_{n0}(\vec{r}) \rangle - |\langle \omega_{n0}(\vec{r}) | \vec{r} | \omega_{n0}(\vec{r}) \rangle|^2 \right] \quad (2.80)$$

$$\Omega = \Omega_I + \tilde{\Omega} = \Omega_I + \Omega_D + \Omega_{OD} \quad (2.81)$$

Where,

$$\Omega_I = \sum_n \left[\langle \omega_{n0}(\vec{r}) | \vec{r}^2 | \omega_{n0}(\vec{r}) \rangle - \sum_{Rm} |\langle \omega_{nR}(\vec{r}) | \vec{r} | \omega_{n0}(\vec{r}) \rangle|^2 \right] \quad (2.82)$$

$$\Omega_D = \sum_n \sum_{R \neq 0} |\langle \omega_{nR}(\vec{r}) | \vec{r} | \omega_{n0}(\vec{r}) \rangle|^2 \quad (2.83)$$

$$\Omega_{OD} = \sum_{m \neq n} \sum_R |\langle \omega_{nR}(\vec{r}) | \vec{r} | \omega_{m0}(\vec{r}) \rangle|^2 \quad (2.84)$$

In order to obtain, the maximally localised wannier functions, Marzari and Vanderbilt proposed to minimize the gauge dependent spread function ($\tilde{\Omega}$) with respect to a set of unitary matrices $U^{(k)}$.⁶⁰ For this purpose, two key ingredients are obtained from the first-principles electronic structure calculations i.e., (i) the overlap between cell periodic part of Bloch states ($|u_{nk}\rangle$) are computed over vectors which connects a given k -point to its neighbours as presented in Eq. 2.85 and, (ii) initially by guess, the Bloch states ($|\psi_{nk}\rangle$) are projected onto a localised

orbital ($|g_n\rangle$) (as presented in Eq. 2.86) such that, the small $N \times N$ matrices $M^{(k,b)}$, $A^{(k)}$ and $U^{(k)}$ are independent of the basis set used to obtain the original Blöch states.⁶⁰

$$M_{mn}^{(k,b)} = \langle u_{mk} | u_{nk+b} \rangle \quad (2.85)$$

$$A_{mn}^{(k)} = \langle \psi_{mk} | g_n \rangle \quad (2.86)$$

Berry Connection and Curvature

In terms of periodic Blöch states ($|u_{nk}\rangle = e^{-ik \cdot r} |\psi_{nk}\rangle$), the Berry connection is defined as in Eq. 2.87. Then, the curl of Berry connections gives the Berry curvature as presented in Eq. 2.88.

$$A_n(k) = \langle u_{nk} | i \nabla_k | u_{nk} \rangle \quad (2.87)$$

$$\Omega_n(k) = \nabla_k \times A_n(k) = -\text{Im} \langle \nabla_k u_{nk} | \times | \nabla_k u_{nk} \rangle \quad (2.88)$$

The quantities presented in Eq. 2.87 and 2.88 are central to the description of electronic properties of crystals.⁶²

Spin Hall Conductivity

Under the independent particle approximation, the spin Hall conductivity of a material is given by the Kubo-Greenwood formula presented in Eq. 2.89.

$$\sigma_{\alpha\beta}^{\text{spin}\gamma}(\omega) = \frac{\hbar}{\Omega_c N_k} \sum_k \sum_n f_{nk} \sum_{m \neq n} \frac{2 \text{Im} [\langle nk | \hat{j}_\alpha^\gamma | mk \rangle \langle mk | -e \hat{v}_\beta | nk \rangle]}{(\epsilon_{nk} - \epsilon_{mk})^2 - (\hbar\omega + i\eta)^2} \quad (2.89)$$

Here, $\hat{j}_\alpha^\gamma = \frac{1}{2} \{ \hat{s}_\gamma, \hat{v}_\alpha \}$ is the spin current operator with the spin operator $\hat{s}_\gamma = \frac{\hbar}{2} \hat{\sigma}_\gamma$ where, α and β represent the cartesian directions and γ represents the spin direction which are typically x, y and z respectively. Ω_c is the cell volume, N_k are the number of k-points used to sample the brillouin zone, f_{nk} is the Fermi-Dirac distribution function, $\hbar\omega$ is the optical frequency and η is a smearing paramter in energy units.

The velocity matrix in the numerator of Eq. 2.89 is a known quantity, however, the spin current matrix $\langle nk | \hat{j}_\alpha^\gamma | mk \rangle$ which is unknown term can be computed using wannier

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interpolation method. Eq. 2.89 can be further resolved into a band projected Berry curvature like term presented in Eq. 2.90 such that, the momentum resolved term summing over the occupied bands is presented in Eq. 2.91. Then the final form of the spin Hall conductivity is presented in Eq. 2.92.⁶⁴

$$\Omega_{n,\alpha\beta}^{\text{spin}\gamma}(k) = \hbar^2 \sum_{m \neq n} \frac{-2 \text{Im} [\langle nk | \frac{1}{2} \{ \hat{s}_\gamma, \hat{v}_\alpha \} | mk \rangle \langle mk | -e\hat{v}_\beta | nk \rangle]}{(\epsilon_{nk} - \epsilon_{mk})^2 - (\hbar\omega + i\eta)^2} \quad (2.90)$$

$$\Omega_{\alpha\beta}^{\text{spin}\gamma}(k) = \sum_n f_{nk} \Omega_{n,\alpha\beta}^{\text{spin}\gamma}(k) \quad (2.91)$$

$$\sigma_{\alpha\beta}^{\text{spin}\gamma}(\omega) = -\frac{e^2}{\hbar} \frac{1}{\Omega_c N_k} \sum_k \Omega_{\alpha\beta}^{\text{spin}\gamma}(k) \quad (2.92)$$

Where the unit of $\Omega_{\alpha\beta}^{\text{spin}\gamma}(k)$ is \AA^2 and the unit of $\sigma_{\alpha\beta}^{\text{spin}\gamma}(\omega)$ is $(\hbar/e)Scm^{-1}$ wherein, for $\omega = 0$ we have the DC spin Hall conductivity and for $\omega \neq 0$ we have the frequency dependent or AC spin Hall conductivity. Eq. 2.91 is used to compute momentum resolved, band projected spin Berry curvature.

Tight-Binding Model

A semi-empirical approach to study electronic structures of periodic systems by projecting the Hamiltonian onto a series of localised orbitals is known as the tight-binding method. There are three methods to generate and construct such as model which are, (i) Slater-Koster method, (ii) discrete k-p model on a lattice and (iii) maximally localised wannier functions.⁶⁵⁻⁶⁷ Over the years, the maximally localised wannier functions have gained a lot of popularity to generate tight-binding model for predicting materials properties. The basis functions in a tight-binding method can be mutually orthogonal or non-orthogonal. Wannier functions generate orthogonal basis functions for the tight-binding model which is implemented in WannierTools code to predict material properties.⁶⁷

To generate the tight binding model, consider, ‘ i ’ atoms with ‘ μ ’ orbitals such that, the combination is labelled as, $\{i,\mu\}$ with, ‘ \vec{R} ’ representing the lattice vectors of the three dimensional periodic arrangement and $\vec{\tau}_i$ indicating the position of atoms in the unit cell. Then, the local orbital of i^{th} atom centered at $(\vec{R} + \vec{\tau}_i)$ can be presented as in Eq. 2.93.

$$\phi_{Rm}(\vec{r}) \equiv \phi_m(\vec{r} - \vec{R}) \equiv \varphi_{i\mu}(\vec{r} - \vec{R} - \vec{\tau}_i) \quad (2.93)$$

Since the basis functions have to be orthogonal, the need to satisfy the relation, $\langle \phi_{Rm} | \phi_{R'm} \rangle = \delta_{RR'} \delta_{mn}$. Then, the tight-binding parameters of the Hamiltonian with translational symmetry under the Bloch periodic condition is given as presented in Eq. 2.94.

$$H_{mn}(\vec{R}) = \langle \phi_{0m} | \hat{H} | \phi_{Rn} \rangle \quad (2.94)$$

Using the tight-binding Hamiltonian presented in Eq. 2.94, we can present the tight-binding Hamiltonian in momentum space by performing a Fourier transformation under two conventions presented in Eq. 2.95 and 2.96.⁶⁷

$$H_{mn}(k) = \sum_R e^{ik \cdot R} H_{mn}(\vec{R}) \quad (2.95)$$

$$H_{mn}(k) = \sum_R e^{ik \cdot (R + \tau_m - \tau_n)} H_{mn}(\vec{R}) \quad (2.96)$$

The eigen values obtained under the two conventions presented in Eq. 2.95 and 2.96 are identical but the eigen functions are different i.e., eigen functions in Eq. 2.95 are similar to the Bloch eigen functions $\psi_{nk}(\vec{r})$ and, the eigen functions in Eq. 2.96 are similar to the periodic Bloch eigen functions $u_{nk}(\vec{r}) = \psi_{nk}(\vec{r})e^{-ikr}$. We use the tight-binding Hamiltonian presented in Eq. 2.96 to compute material properties.

Topological Invariants

The topological insulators are classified into trivial and non-trivial characters by computing the \mathbb{Z}_2 invariants and the Chern numbers.^{68,69} The former is used in case of systems where the time-reversal is invariant and the later is used in case of systems where the time-reversal symmetry is broken. We will proceed with discussions of the \mathbb{Z}_2 invariants.

Fu and Kane proposed that, for systems governed by the inversion symmetry in bulk and low dimensional phase, the \mathbb{Z}_2 invariants can be computed by taking the product of parities of the Kramer degenerate occupied eigen states at time reversal invariant momenta and parity invariant points in the Brillouin zone.⁷⁰

Equation 2.97 and 2.98 are used to compute the \mathbb{Z}_2 invariants for bulk materials since, the bulk has eight time-reversal invariant points which leads to four independent \mathbb{Z}_2 invariants. One of them is ν_0 , which is computed as the product over all the eight points (as presented in

Eq. 2.97) and the other three (ν_1, ν_2, ν_3) are computed as products over four δ_i for which the time reversal invariant momenta lie in the same plane.⁷⁰

$$(-1)^{\nu_0} = \prod_{i=1}^8 \delta_i \quad (2.97)$$

$$(-1)^{\nu_k} = \prod_{\substack{n_k=1; \\ n_{j \neq k}=0,1}} \delta_{i=(n_1 n_2 n_3)} \quad (2.98)$$

Equation 2.99 presents the \mathbb{Z}_2 for low dimensional materials wherein, the product of parities are computed only along four time-reversal invariant momenta.⁷⁰

$$(-1)^\nu = \prod_{i=1}^4 \delta_i \quad (2.99)$$

However, for systems violating the time-reversal symmetry, the method of computing \mathbb{Z}_2 invariant is based on the wilson loop and wannier charge center methods.^{71,72} It was found that, both of these methods accurately predict the \mathbb{Z}_2 invariants in systems violating the time-reversal symmetry. For systems obeying time-reversal symmetry, the \mathbb{Z}_2 could be computed in terms of the time-reversal polarization (\mathcal{P}_θ) which is gauge invariant (as presented in Eq. 2.100).⁷⁰

$$\Delta = [\mathcal{P}_\theta(\mathcal{T}/2) - \mathcal{P}_\theta(0)] \text{mod} 2 \quad (2.100)$$

This equation is modified into Eq. 2.101 and 2.102 wherein, the time-reversal polarization relation is modified in terms of the wannier charge centers along two momentum planes in the brillouin zone (as in Eq. 2.101 and 2.102).⁷²

$$\nu_0 = [(\mathbb{Z}_2)_{k_i=0} + (\mathbb{Z}_2)_{k_i=0.5}] \text{mod} 2 \quad (2.101)$$

$$\nu_i = (\mathbb{Z}_2)_{k_i=0.5}, i = 1, 2, 3 \quad (2.102)$$

Surface States

It is a computationally expensive task to compute the slab band structures to observe the surface/edge states in topological systems. For this purpose, we employ, the tight-binding Hamiltonian model generated using wannier functions to compute the surface/edge states

using the surface Green's function for a semi-infinite system. The Green's function approach based on the effective field theory and transfer matrix converge slowly near singularities.^{73–75} As an alternative, the iterative Green's function method developed in 1980's is used for faster convergence.^{76,77} The faster convergence and resulting lower computational time is due to the principle layers (which are large enough to ensure that, the hoppings to next nearest layers are negligible). This is achieved by replacing the principle layers with an effective two principle layers such that, the interaction of effective layers is governed by the energy dependent residual interactions which are weaker. This process of replacing the layers is repeated iteratively until the interactions between the layers is quite small as per requirements.⁷⁸

$$\mathcal{G}_s(k_{\parallel}, \omega) \approx (\omega - \epsilon_n^s)^{-1} \quad (2.103)$$

$$\tilde{\mathcal{G}}_s(k_{\parallel}, \omega) \approx (\omega - \tilde{\epsilon}_n^s)^{-1} \quad (2.104)$$

$$\mathcal{G}_b(k_{\parallel}, \omega) \approx (\omega - \epsilon_n)^{-1} \quad (2.105)$$

The surface ($\mathcal{G}_s(k_{\parallel}, \omega)$) and bulk ($\mathcal{G}_b(k_{\parallel}, \omega)$) Green's function obtained from such iterative process are presented in Eq. 2.103 and 2.105 respectively where, $\tilde{\mathcal{G}}_s$ is the surface Green's function of a dual surface. Then, the surface/edge spectrum can be obtained from the imaginary part of the surface Green's function as presented in Eq. 2.106.

$$\mathcal{A}(k_{\parallel}, \omega) = -\frac{1}{\pi} \lim_{\eta \rightarrow 0^+} \text{Im Tr } \mathcal{G}_s(k_{\parallel}, \omega + i\eta) \quad (2.106)$$

2.9 Computational Packages

We use Quantum ESPRESSO open-source package which an integrated suite to perform; electronic-structure calculations and materials modeling at on bulk as well as nano-scale.⁷⁹ It is based on density functional theory, plane waves approximation and pseudopotential methods. Using this package, we performed *first-principles* computations under self-consistent field formalism to obtain the ground state eigen energies of the bulk and low dimensional periodic systems. For electronic structure calculations (wherein we compute the electronic eigen states as a function of crystal momentum) we perform computations in terms of non-self consistent field formalisms. This code is so versatile that, we can perform structural relaxations and

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optimizations, compute the electronic charge densities, perform computations using van der Waals dispersion corrections, compute electronic-structure under the influence of spin-orbit interactions, compute the density of states and orbital projected density of states, compute vibrational properties under density functional perturbation theory etc. Another advantage of Quantum ESPRESSO code is that, due to its open-source availability, it can be interfaced with several computational codes to compute other material properties. Several members of active computational physics group develop codes which can be easily interfaced with Quantum ESPRESSO increasing its capabilities.

Figure 2.2: Computational codes used in this thesis.

For example, using the ground state energies and the corresponding crystal structure, we can interface the Quantum ESPRESSO code with the ElaStic code (a part of the Exciting code) to compute the elastic stress tensors.⁸⁰ This is achieved in ElaStic code by, perturbing the ground state system with small strain of the order of $\pm 5\%$ or 10% (as per our requirement). The corresponding crystal structures are fed into Quantum ESPRESSO code and the respective ground state energies are computed. Then, the ElaStic code plots a curve of energy versus strain and performs linear or polynomial fitting eventually giving the elastic stress tensors.

For computing the thermoelectric transport properties, we employ the open-source BoltzTrap code which implements the semi-classical Boltzmann transport equations to compute the semi-classical transport coefficients.⁸¹ This code is interfaced with Quantum ESPRESSO and uses a mesh of electronic-structures for computing the thermoelectric properties. Hence, we can get the insights into the electronic aspect of thermoelectric properties using this code. As far as the lattice or vibrational aspect is concerned, we use ShengBTE code which computes the semi-classical Boltzmann transport equations for phonons.⁸² The 2nd and 3rd order inter-atomic force constants required in ShengBTE are obtained using Quantum ESPRESSO.

The topological properties are computed by employing open-source packages such as, Wannier90 and WannierTools code.^{83,84} The Wannier90 code is used to generate the maximally localised wannier functions. These functions are obtained by performing fourier transforms of the plane wave basis set generated in Quantum ESPRESSO. The general workflow is that, we perform self-consistent field calculations on a system, then the non-consistent field calculations (which gives information about the distribution of eigen states in the momentum space), this is followed by the interfacing script *pw2wannier* (which performs the transformation of basis sets and generates the input parameters required for wannierisation) bridging Quantum ESPRESSO and Wannier90, then finally, wannierisation is performed to compute the maximally localised wannier functions. Using the maximally localised wannier functions obtained from Wannier90, we generate the exact tight-binding Hamiltonian model which would be interfaced with the WannierTools code.

We employed the maximally localised wannier functions to compute and investigate topological properties using WannierTools code. This code extracts the information from the exact tight-binding Hamiltonian generated using Wannier90 and computes topological properties such as, angle resolved photo-emission spectroscopy-like spectra, spin-textures, topological invariants (using Wilson loop method), slab band structures etc.

During the entire process of investigations and prediction of material properties, open-source packages such as, xcrysden and VESTA were extensively used.^{85,86} These are crystalline and molecular structure visualisation programs used to, display and visualize the crystal structures and morphologies, trace the brillouin zone momentum path (for computing band structures and phonon dispersion curves), generate 2D and 3D plots of charge density profiles / contours using volumetric data of electronic and nuclear densities etc.

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CHAPTER 3

Topological Insulating Phase in Some Bulk Materials

We discuss the origin and background of the topological phases and phase transitions in bulk materials in this chapter. Specifically, we will discuss about Half-Heusler compounds and present the results of our investigation on topological insulating nature of LiMgX ($X = \text{Bi, Sb, As}$) in the backdrop of existing relevant literature. We will discuss the effects of strain fields in realising non-trivial topological nature in such compounds. Also, we discuss different mechanisms by which topological insulating nature can be realised in binary compound such as AuI . The topological phase transitions are qualitatively discussed in terms of the band structures and orbital character inversions which are characteristic to quantum transitions. This is followed by the quantitative analysis in terms of the \mathbb{Z}_2 invariants and angle resolved photo emission spectroscopy-like surface state spectra. These are accompanied with discussions about the stability of the proposed materials in terms of phonon dispersion curves etc.

3.1 The Case of Half-Heusler' LiMgX ($X = \text{Bi, Sb, As}$)

Topological Insulators are a quantum phase of matter known for hosting exotic quantum phenomena such as, spin-momentum locked transport of electrons across the topologically protected surfaces states which are robust against scattering from crystal impurities.¹ Materials

hosting such quantum feature have applications in, spintronics, quantum computation, sensors etc. which has generated enormous interest in the scientific community. Ever since the discovery of topological phenomena in bulk materials (as discussed in chapter 1), numerous materials have been explored theoretically as well as experimentally as potential candidates hosting topological insulating nature.²⁻⁷ Various mechanisms have been employed in this regard, for example, by applying strain, electric field, doping etc.⁸⁻¹⁷

Application of strain has been a famous choice to realise topological quantum phase transitions in bulk materials for example, β -As₂Te₃, AMgBi (A = Li, Na, K) and elemental tellurium with possibility of hosting multi-functional applications.^{14, 18-23} In case elemental tellurium which is made up of helical chains governed by three fold screw symmetry and weak van der Waals interaction which can be manipulated by application of pressure to realise non-trivial topological phases.¹⁹ Similarly, AMgBi (A = Li, Na, K) has been investigated to exhibit non-trivial topological properties in Pnma and P6₃mmc phase under the influence of strain. Of these, LiMgBi exhibits type-I anti-ferroelectric properties with polar topological states.²³ In such scenarios where strain induced topological phase transitions are observed in materials, the governing dynamics is that of altered atomic orbitals in the periodic lattice arrangement leading to new hybridizations. Also, apart from the application of strain, in some quintuple layered compounds (such as, Bi₂Te₃, Bi₂Se₃ etc.) the non-trivial topological character originates intrinsically owing to the strong spin-orbit interactions of the heavy elements due to high atomic nuclear charge.²⁴ So the question is, in which other materials can we come across such exotic features? Can we discover/establish a finitely large repository of materials which can exhibit such exotic quantum phenomena for multifunctional applications? These questions directed our focus of first-principles investigations towards Half-Heusler compounds.

It is a well established fact that, the electronic properties of a material originate from the arrangement of atoms in a particular crystal structure governed by space groups. This provides us with innumerable avenues which can be explored wherein, novel materials can be designed and investigated for any desired application. Half-Heusler compounds (of type XYZ) can be aptly described as such materials because, these compounds are made up of X⁺ ion stuffed in (YZ)⁻ zincblende sublattice where the elements at X, Y and Z site can be from the *s*, *p* and *d* block of the periodic table.²⁵ Thus providing enormous permutations and combinations of these elements and hence material properties. Also, the zincblende

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sub-lattice of such materials may exhibit band orders across the Fermi level similar to that of bulk HgTe originating through the adiabatic connection of the band topologies.²⁶ Hence, Half-Heusler compounds are ideal candidates to realise non-trivial topological phases such as topological insulators, apart from properties which can have multi-functional applications such as, semi-conductors, thermoelectrics, piezoelectrics, opto-electronics, superconductivity, magnetism etc.^{21,22,27-34} One technique is to employ screening potentials to classify the Half-Heusler compounds into trivial and non-trivial insulators.³⁵ However, we proceed with application of strain which alters the crystal structure governing electronic properties.

Figure 3.1: Face centered cubic structure of LiMgBi where; Li, Mg and Bi occupy, $4b$, $4c$ and $4a$ Wyckoff positions respectively (left). Irreducible Brillouin zone of the face centered cubic structure indicating the momentum path used for computing electronic band structures and phonon dispersion curves (right).

We began our investigations with Half-Heusler family of LiMgX where the element ‘X’ is replaced by Pnictogen family of elements such as, Bi, Sb and As. These systems were previously predicted to be semiconductors due to 8-electron valency of the zincblende sublattice compositions made of MgX (X = Bi, Sb, As).²⁵ Belonging to the $\bar{F}43m$ space group these systems are presented in the Hermann-Mauguin representation as [216] (presented in Fig. 3.1). We introduce volume expansion pressure which is similar to hydrostatic pressure but originates from insertion of a cavity nuclei as discussed in the following sections.³⁷ We observed that, these compounds undergo topological phase transitions under volume expansion pressure which is qualitatively discussed in terms of band dispersion inversions. But, does a band dispersion inversion always guarantee a non-trivial topological character? We found that, this is not the case and rigorous investigations in terms of \mathbb{Z}_2 invariants is

required to compliment the qualitative picture. Also, we observe that, the pressures required for topological phase transitions in such bulk materials is quite high, which motivated us to explore the dimensional engineering of two dimensional phase cleaved from [111] crystal direction of these bulk compounds wherein, the quantum confinement effects may exhibit contrasting scenarios, hosting interesting non-trivial character. We employ, state-of-the-art density functional theory calculations to qualitatively investigate topological phase transitions in half-heusler compounds LiMgX (X = Bi, Sb, As) in terms of electronic structure and orbital projected density of states. These are complimented by computing the topological properties such as \mathbb{Z}_2 , angle resolved photoemission spectroscopy-like surface state plots using the exact tight-binding hamiltonian generated using maximally localised wannier functions.

LiMgBi: Structure and Lattice Dynamics

The structure of LiMgBi was optimized under generalised gradient approximation with lattice constant (a) of 6.81 Å which was found to be in agreement with the experimental (6.74 Å) and theoretical (6.71 Å) values.²¹ This face centered cubic structure is defined by space group the $\overline{F}43m[216]$ space group which is presented alongside the brillouin zone in Fig. 3.1. The system was found to be dynamically stable (as evident from the phonon dispersion curves presented in Fig. 3.2) with the primitive cell vectors in terms of lattice constant (a) defined as, $v_1 = (a/2)(-1,0,1)$, $v_2 = (a/2)(0,1,1)$, $v_3 = (a/2)(-1,1,0)$ wherein, atoms Li, Mg and Bi occupy, 4b, 4c and 4a Wyckoff positions respectively.³⁰

We performed phonon dispersion calculations to verify the lattice dynamic stability of LiMgBi. This is essential because, phonon dynamics are fundamental in underpinning the vibrational lattice dynamics during phase transition and to ascertain experimental feasibility of the material. The phonon dispersions of LiMgBi are presented in Fig 3.3 in the absence of volume expansion pressure, indicating dynamic stability and absence of imaginary modes. The three atoms in the unit cell give rise to nine phonon branches in

Figure 3.2: Phonon dispersion curves in absence of volume expansion pressure.

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the dispersion relation. In lower frequency regime, the three vibrational modes correspond to acoustic branches i.e., one longitudinal acoustic and two transverse acoustic modes which are degenerate along, $W \rightarrow X$ and $L \rightarrow \Gamma$ path in the brillouin zone.³⁸ Similarly, in higher frequency regime, the six vibrational modes correspond to optical branches i.e., two longitudinal optical and four transverse optical modes. Here, the former is degenerate at Γ and the latter is degenerate along, $\Gamma \rightarrow K$, $K \rightarrow X$ and $X \rightarrow \Gamma$ path in the brillouin zone.³⁸

LiMgBi: Electronic Properties

Figure 3.3: Electronic band structure of LiMgBi at in absence of volume expansion pressure.

We increased the lattice constant in steps of 0.5% from 0.0% to 8.0% to observe topological quantum phase transitions in LiMgBi. Due to cubic symmetry such increment in lattice gives rise to an isotropic effect which we refer to as the volume expansion pressure. Experimentally, such phenomena can be expected due to the presence of an intrinsic *void* in the crystal, extreme internal *thermal* and *cavitation* pressure arising from impurities known as *cavity nuclei*.

As expected, due to 8-electron valency, this structure exhibits semi-conducting character as evident from the electronic band structure presented in Fig. 3.3 which was compared to previous reports as presented in Tab. 3.1.²¹ Since it is known that, the error in band-gap prediction under generalised gradient approximation is higher as compared to hybrid methods such as HSE06, we performed HSE06 calculations and present them in Tab. 3.1 which indicates that, the results are in strong agreement with previous studies at 0.0% strain and accurate as compared to the generalised gradient approach.

Table 3.1: Theoretical and experimental values of lattice constant (a) and energy band gap.

Parameter	Work	LiMgBi
Lattice (\AA)	GGA ^(present)	6.81
	Theory ²¹	6.71
	Experiment ^{21,39}	6.74
Band Gap (eV)	GGA ^(present)	0.35
	HSE06 ^(present)	0.70
	Theory ²¹	0.62

Figure 3.4: (A) Increment in the unit cell volume (a.u.³) due to volume expansion pressure. (B) Volume strain with respect to % volume expansion pressure. (C) Change in total energy (eV) of the system indicating a shift from the equilibrium state leading to a quantum phase transition.

We studied the increment in unit cell volume (a.u.³) under volume expansion pressure (as presented in Fig 3.4(A)) it in terms of, volume strain (presented in Fig 3.4(B)) and, total energy ($\Delta E = E_i - E_0$ in eV) with respect to % volume expansion pressure (presented in Fig 3.4(C)) and found that, due to increment in volume expansion pressure, the system deviates from its equilibrium state which probably would lead to a topological quantum phase transition, analysed quantitatively below.

The analysis of electronic band dispersion gives qualitative insights into the topological quantum phase transitions in materials. We hence, analysed the electronic band structures of LiMgBi and look for inversion in dispersion (under band engineering due to pressure) which characterises the topological insulating nature of the material. We observed that, such a phenomena occurs in LiMgBi at a critical pressure of 4.0% wherein, the system undergoes a phase transition from a semi-conductor to a Dirac semi-metal such that, further application pressure breaks the Dirac degeneracy as presented in Fig. 3.5.

Figure 3.5: The closing and reopening of the band gap with respect to % VEP indicating the Topological Phase Transition in FCC LiMgBi.

In the absence of volume expansion pressure, by generalised gradient approximation and hybrid functional approach, we observed an electronic band gap of 0.35 eV and 0.70 eV respectively at the center of brillouin zone (i.e., at Γ point) as presented in Fig. 3.6(A) and

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Tab. 3.1. For qualitative analysis, we performed calculation of the electronic properties such as band gap under generalised gradient approximation and hybrid approach at different volume expansion pressures of 0%, 4% and 6.5%. We observed that, the energy gap varies as, 0.35 eV \rightarrow 0.00 eV \rightarrow 0.001 eV (under generalised gradient approximation) and 0.70 eV \rightarrow 0.00 eV \rightarrow 0.04 eV (under hybrid approach); confirming the phenomena of band closing and reopening as observed in Fig. 3.5.

It was observed that, the valence band maxima is doubly degenerate whereas, the conduction band minima is non-degenerate state at the brillouin zone center (Γ). This band feature is protected by two-fold symmetry of the face centered cubic structure. As we gradually increased the volume expansion pressure, at 4.0% critical point, LiMgBi undergoes a topological quantum phase transition from a trivial insulator to a Dirac semimetal (as presented in Fig 3.6(middle)) with degenerate conduction and valence band frontiers. Here, we chose to represent the eigen states at the brillouin zone center (Γ) as Γ_i where ‘ i ’ is the band index without spin degeneracy. Figure 3.6 presents the electronic band evolution at the brillouin zone center during the topological quantum phase transition with increase in volume expansion pressure. At 0% pressure the band order is $\Gamma_{10} > \Gamma_8 > \Gamma_6$ where, $\Gamma_{6,8}$ are populated by the p -orbitals and Γ_{10} is populated by the s -orbital with, $\Gamma_{6,8}$ being degenerate as evident from in Fig 3.6(top). With increase in volume expansion pressure, a Dirac degeneracy appears at 4.0% as presented in Fig 3.6(middle) creating degenerate $\Gamma_{8,10}$ bands.

Figure 3.6: Electronic band structure of LiMgBi at, 0.0% (top), 4.5% (middle) and 6.5% (bottom) volume expansion pressure

As this degeneracy forms, the degeneracy of $\Gamma_{6,8}$ lifts off. On further increasing the pressure, the Dirac dispersion is retained till 6% volume expansion pressure beyond which, the band-gap reopens to 1.10 meV (under generalised gradient approximation) as presented in Fig. 3.6(bottom). This reopening indicates towards band inversion in terms of the inverted band order i.e., $\Gamma_8 > \Gamma_6 > \Gamma_{10}$. In order to ascertain the non-trivial topological character, we computed the orbital projected density of states.

Figure 3.7(A) presents the orbital projected density of states for LiMgBi at 0% volume expansion pressure. It is clearly evident that, the valence band is populated by the p -orbital of Bi while, the conduction band is dominated by the s -orbitals of Li, Mg and Bi wherein, a strong hybridization was observed between the s -orbitals of Mg and Bi. With increment in pressure, the s -orbital contributions of Li, Mg and Bi from conduction band enter the valence band, while the p -orbital contribution of Bi from the valence band enters the conduction band at the critical pressure of 4% (as presented in Fig. 3.7(B)). Further increase in pressure makes the hybridization of s -orbitals of Mg and Bi weaker while, the hybridization between the s -orbitals of Li and Bi become stronger evident from Fig 3.7(C). Thus, at 6.5% of pressure, although the gap opens but, the inverted orbital contributions don't change. Therefore, Fig. 3.7(A-C) visually summarises the exchange of orbital character due to volume expansion pressure driving the system LiMgBi; through a topological quantum

Figure 3.7: Orbital projected density of states at, (A) 0%, (B) 4% and (C) 6.5% volume expansion pressure (inset panels represent states near Fermi level with energy range -0.5 eV to 0.5 eV).

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phase transition. We confirm the generalised gradient approximation results in terms of the hybrid approach. Figure 3.8 presents the density of states under hybrid functional approach. It is interesting to note that, similar to the calculations under generalised gradient approximations, the hybrid approach give similar results i.e., at 4% pressure the density of states is semi-metallic and at 6.5% the gap reopens to 40 meV.

Figure 3.8: Density of states under hybrid approach at 4% and 6.5% volume expansion pressure.

the relativistic effects which arise from the core electronic contribution of Bi atoms. Since, the gap opening is quite small it indicates that, for spintronic applications, the system has to me maintained at low temperatures.

We expected that, the presence of Bi at $4a$ Wyckoff position in the face centered cubic structure would lead to pronounced spin-orbit interactions. Figure 3.8(A) and (B) represent the electronic band structures without and with spin-orbit interactions at critical volume expansion pressure of 4%. The Dirac degeneracy at the brillouin zone center lifts off due to strong spin-orbit interactions giving rise to a band gap of 1.20 meV. This further confirms the characteristic behaviour of a typical topological insulator governed by

Figure 3.9: Electronic Band Structure at center of the Brillouin zone, (A) without and (B) with spin-orbit interactions, at critical volume expansion pressure of 4%.

LiMgBi: Topological Properties

Following the investigations of the electronic properties, we computed the non-trivial surface states to quantitatively ascertain the topological insulating nature. Figure 3.10 was the angle resolved photo emission spectroscopy-like spectra which clearly indicates the Dirac dispersion of surface states at 4.5% volume expansion pressure i.e., beyond the critical value of pressure. These surface states host dissipationless Fermions which are spin locked with momentum in the Brillouin zone.

Hence, we can experimentally verify the non-trivial topological nature of LiMgBi by performing angle resolved photo emission spectroscopy to probe the surface states along the surface.

Figure 3.10: Surface states at 4.5% volume expansion pressure.

Figure 3.11: Evolution of the \mathbb{Z}_2 invariant (v_0) as a function of pressure.

Apart from the surface states, mathematically, \mathbb{Z}_2 invariants are essential to characterize and classify a bulk material as a non-trivial topological insulator. Since, LiMgBi is a half-heusler compound, it does not possess inversion symmetry. Hence, we cannot proceed with Fu and Kane method of computing the \mathbb{Z}_2 invariants. We rather use the Wannier charge center method discussed in the methodology chapter 2 to compute the \mathbb{Z}_2 invariants along six time reversal invariant planes. The computed \mathbb{Z}_2 invariants are, $(v_0, v_1 v_2 v_3) = (1, 000)$ indicating that, LiMgBi is a strong topological insulator with robust surface states which won't decompose into two dimensional quantum spin Hall material.⁴⁰ In Fig. 3.11 we present the evolution of \mathbb{Z}_2 invariant (v_0) as a function of volume expansion pressure which clearly demarcates the topological quantum phase transitions.

On similar line of investigation (i.e., qualitative and quantitative approach), we explored LiMgSb and LiMgAs. It was expected that, these materials won't be as strong as topological

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insulator LiMgBi; owing to the weaker spin-orbit interaction. Motivating us to explore the low dimensional phases of materials. Also, one issue with LiMgBi is that, the Fermi level does not lie in the global gap due to spin-orbit interaction. This motivated us to approach other method such as breaking the crystal symmetry etc.

LiMgSb and LiMgAs: Structure and Lattice Dynamics

The bulk structures of LiMgSb and LiMgAs exist in face-centered cubic phase with lattice constant (a) under generalised gradient approximation as 6.63 \AA and 6.19 \AA respectively.^{21,22} Here, Wyckoff positions $4b$, $4c$ and $4a$ are occupied by Li, Mg and Sb / As respectively. The lattice constants presented here are in agreement with previous reports. The interatomic distances in LiMgAs are, As-Mg = 2.69 \AA , Mg-Li = 5.38 \AA and in LiMgSb are, Sb-Mg = 2.87 \AA and Mg-Li = 2.86 \AA . We provide greater focus and emphasis on LiMgAs rather than LiMgSb since the former has been well explored and investigated experimentally for various applications.

Figure 3.12: Phonon dispersion curves alongside phonon density of states of LiMgAs indicating dynamic stability of the system.

To reiterate the significance of dynamic stability of LiMgAs, we compute the phonon dispersion curves and phonon density of states (presented in Fig. 3.12) which clearly indicates the absence of imaginary modes in the entire Brillouin zone. The absence of imaginary modes in the phonon dispersions indicates that, the increase in potential energy against any combination of atomic displacements is same as the condition that all phonons have real frequencies in harmonic approximation.^{41–45} On the other hand, the presence of imaginary modes indicates that the system is dynamically unstable due to decrease in potential energy

around the equilibrium atomic positions originating from different combinations of atomic displacements. The phonon dispersion curves and density of states are presented in Fig. 3.12 are under pristine conditions i.e., without any external pressure. Similar to LiMgBi, the three atoms occupying the unit cell give rise to nine phonon branches evident from the dispersion relation which can be decomposed into three in plane acoustic branches dominating lower frequencies and six optical branches dominating higher frequencies.

LiMgSb and LiMgAs: Electronic Properties

This face centered cubic structure of LiMgSb hosts indirect band gap of ~ 0.9 eV indicating the semi-conducting nature due to 8-electron valency in the absence of volume expansion pressure. Similar to LiMgBi, we apply volume expansion pressure expecting topological quantum phase transitions. As the pressure is applied the indirect gap transforms into a direct gap under 5% volume expansion pressure at the brillouin zone center. At very high pressure of 17% a Dirac degeneracy is observed at the brillouin zone center (as presented in Fig. 3.13(top)) beyond which the gap reopens to 3.1 meV (under 20% pressure as presented in Fig. (bottom)). Such dispersion behaviour is also accompanied with inversion of the $-s$ and $-p$ orbital characters in valence band and conduction

Figure 3.13: Electronic band structure at, 17% (top) and 20% (bottom) pressure indicating inversion of band dispersion.

band across Fermi level (based on the analysis of orbital projected density of states). However, the non-trivial band dispersions and density of states, the phase transition observed in LiMgSb are further confirmed by computing the topological properties.

Similar to LiMgBi and LiMgSb, LiMgAs exhibits semi-conducting character due to the 8-electron valency with indirect band gap as presented in Fig. 3.14. Since the zincblende sub-lattice formed by Mg-As in LiMgAs is adiabatically connected to the band topology

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of HgTe, we discuss the topological properties in terms of band orders around Fermi level similar to that of HgTe i.e., the Γ_8 band denoting the p-type orbitals and Γ_6 band denoting the s-type orbitals. The band energies at these indices give insights into the band inversion strength which is given by $\Delta = E_{\Gamma_8} - E_{\Gamma_6}$.^{26,46}

Figure 3.14: Electronic band structure of LiMgAs.

Although the global gap is of indirect nature along momentum path $X \rightarrow U \rightarrow L \rightarrow \Gamma$ in the Brillouin zone, the system exhibits a direct gap of 1.67 eV at the Brillouin zone center which is close to 1.55 eV observed in previous studies.²¹ By applying volume expansion/compression pressure can drive the systems through a phase transition. We observed that, under volume compression the global gap increases indicating potential applications for strain induced photovoltaic's

which is open for further research. However, our interest lies in a phase transition which would host Dirac degeneracy. This is observed under volume expansion pressure wherein contrary to compression; the applied pressure drives the system through a phase transition.

Figure 3.15: Electronic band structure around Fermi level indicating the Dirac degeneracy at critical pressure and band reopening at 17% pressure with dispersion inversion (right).

As the pressure is increased, the global gap becomes direct along the Brillouin zone center and decreases as presented in Fig. 3.15(left). At 15% pressure, we observe the critical point of phase transition hosting the Dirac degeneracy as presented in Fig. 3.15(right). On increasing the pressure beyond this critical point, at 17% (inset Fig. 3.15(right)) the Dirac degeneracy lifts off indicating exchange of band dispersions. Apart from exchange of dispersions, we also

observe the exchange of orbitals as evident from the orbital projected density of states (with and without spin-orbit interactions) presented in Fig. 3.16. Under pristine conditions, the conduction band is populated by the s -orbitals arising from Li, Mg and As and the valence band populated purely by the p -orbitals arising from As.

Figure 3.16: Orbital projected density of states without spin-orbit interactions (top) and with spin-orbit interactions (bottom) before (left) and at critical volume expansion pressure (right) respectively, hosting exchanged orbital features around Fermi.

The s -orbitals from Li, Mg and As exhibit strong hybridization with the p -orbitals of As in conduction band as compared to that in valence band. At the critical pressure the Dirac degeneracy leads to a non-negligible increase in the p and s -orbital contributions across the Fermi level is observed (as presented in Fig. 3.16(top)). As evident from Fig. 3.16(top), the s -orbital contributions increase in the valence band but, the dominant contribution is from the p -orbital of As. This implies that, the inversion is weak owing to the presence of Fermions arising from the p -orbital of As. This leads to a linear Dirac dispersion in the conduction band and non-linear/parabolic dispersion in the valence band respectively. The corresponding velocity of Fermions was computed using, $v_f = \partial E / \hbar \partial k$.⁴⁷ We observed that, the velocity of Fermions in conduction band was, $\sim 0.06 \text{ ms}^{-1}$ and $\sim 0.64 \text{ ms}^{-1}$ along $L \rightarrow \Gamma$ and $\Gamma \rightarrow K$ directions in brillouin zone respectively. Similarly, in the valence band the velocity was, \sim

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0.04 ms^{-1} and $\sim 0.33 \text{ ms}^{-1}$ along $L \rightarrow \Gamma$ and $\Gamma \rightarrow K$ directions in brillouin zone respectively.

We also computed the band inversion strength (Δ) which was quite weak i.e., $\Delta \sim 7.0 \text{ meV}$. However, under spin-orbit interaction due to the high nuclear charge of As the Dirac degeneracy lifts off to $\sim 1.5 \text{ meV}$ at the critical point in phase transition characterised by pronounced orbital exchanges as presented in Fig. 3.16(bottom). These qualitative computations were verified by quantitative computations of the topological properties which gave a contradicting result.

LiMgSb and LiMgAs: Topological Properties

Figure 3.17: Angle resolved photoemission spectroscopy-like spectra of LiMgSb (top) and LiMgAs (bottom) beyond the critical pressure.

We observe that, both, LiMgSb and LiMgAs exhibit band dispersion inversions and exchange of orbital characters under the influence of volume expansion pressure as evident from our discussions above. Beyond the critical phase transition point, we computed the angle resolved photoemission spectroscopy-like spectra for LiMgSb and LiMgAs which are presented in Fig. 3.17 top and bottom panel respectively. These spectra do indicate that, the global bulk gap host conducting surface states. However, on computing the \mathbb{Z}_2 invariant (along the time reversal invariant points using the wannier charge center method) to classify the systems into non-trivial phases; we observed that, both LiMgSb and LiMgAs are trivial with \mathbb{Z}_2 invariants as $((\nu_0, \nu_1 \nu_2 \nu_3) = (0, 000))$ which contradicts our qualitative analysis. This implies that, the qualitative analysis of the electronic properties alone cannot be used to investigate the topological character of materials.

Hence, computing the surface states along with the \mathbb{Z}_2 invariants are mandatory. This establishes a necessary and sufficient condition to

realise a topological insulator.

Such contradictory result originates from the fact that, the spin-orbit interactions due to Sb and As are far weaker as compared to Bi. Also, as evident from the electronic properties, the phase transitions in LiMgSb and LiMgAs occur at very high pressures, this implies that, we need to explore low dimensional phases which can be dimensionally engineered from these materials to realised non-trivial topological insulators at relative lower pressures due to high surface-to-volume ratio and quantum confinement effects. Potentially, the low dimensional phases engineered from these bulk materials can host topologically non-trivial behaviour as observed in HgTe which is trivial in bulk but non-trivial upon dimensional confinement. Also, as in LiMgBi, the Fermi level does not lie in the global gap hence we investigated alternate techniques such as the cubic symmetry is broken while realising the topological quantum phase transition. With this motivation, we explored binary compound AuI.

3.2 The Case of Binary Compound AuI

The beauty of non-trivial topological states lies in the exotic quantum phenomena observed in, topological conductors (where, the band bending leads to charge accumulation on surfaces) and topological insulators (wherein the bulk is insulating with conducting surfaces states robust against any sorts of perturbations).^{1,3,48,70} The former has received scarce attention according to our literature survey while, the latter has gathered lots of attention in recent decades. Topological insulators are of a great interest because, these materials are also capable of hosting interesting properties with applications in, thermoelectrics, superconductivity etc.^{5,20,49,50} Typically, in well explored topological insulators such as, $\text{Bi}_{(1-x)}\text{Sb}_x$, Bi_2Te_3 , Bi_2Se_3 , Sb_2Te_3 , HgTe-CdTe etc.^{24,51,52} the non-trivial topological states arise due to the band inversions across the Fermi level which exist due to strong spin-orbit interactions within the material due to heavy elements. Some of the most common orbital inversions protected by in ternal crystal symmetries and observed in topological quantum phase transitions are, *s-p* (in $\text{Bi}_{(1-x)}\text{Sb}_x$, HgTe-CdTe); *p-p* (in Bi_2Te_3 , Bi_2Se_3 , Sb_2Te_3) and *d-p* (in IrBi_3 , LaAs).^{24,51-54,70} In some cases, when a material exhibits weak spin-orbit interactions, it can be enhanced by applying strain/pressure which alters the orbital characters of the elements in the material.¹⁹ In such scenarios, the band inversion mechanism is generally described as the closing and opening of conduction and valence band frontiers.^{19,53} During such phase transitions the system traverses

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through a critical point which exhibits Dirac degeneracy of the conduction and valence band frontiers along a high-symmetry point in the Brillouin zone which is characterised as semi-metallic nature (analogous to the dispersions observed in two dimensional X-ene's).⁵⁵ Binary compounds such as, mercury chalcogenides (i.e., HgTe, HgSe, β -HgS) and wurtzite gold iodide (AuI) compounds are some classical examples of bulk semi-metallic materials.^{12,56,57} Previously, binary compounds, HgTe, HgSe, AuI and Silver Iodide (AgI) were investigated for non-trivial topological states apart from their native semi-metallic character. It should be noted that, this semi-metallic nature is different from the one observed in topological Dirac semi-metals (or Weyl semi-metals). The latter exhibits degenerate nodes/points in the Brillouin zone in the presence of spin-orbit interactions while the former does not possess degeneracies when the spin-orbit interactions are considered.⁵⁸

Of these binary compounds, AuI is an interesting candidate since it exists in different polymorphs. With its wurtzite phase explored for topological phenomena, the aurophilic tetragonal phase has been experimentally investigated under high-pressure.^{56,59} With respect to topological properties, the wurtzite phase exhibits HgTe like inverted band structure with semi-metallic character. It is a fact that, wurtzite and zincblende crystal structures exhibit similar properties. This motivated us to explore topological quantum phenomena in zincblende phase of AuI since it had not been explored till date, due to debatable stability in the zincblende phase. Also, we were motivated to investigate AuI because of its similarity with HgTe (which exhibits topological insulator nature when confined into quantum wells or under very high pressures in bulk phase).^{60,61} With this motivation and background, we began our investigations on zincblende AuI by applying pressure. We found that, contrary to bulk HgTe and wurtzite AuI, the zincblende structure of AuI is highly sensitive to external perturbations and does not retain its the native semi-metallic character. Zincblende AuI undergoes topological quantum phase transitions when subjected to, (i) small isotropic compressive pressure and (ii) uniaxial pressure along [001] crystal direction breaking the cubic symmetry. Due to such high sensitivity, topological quantum phase transitions in AuI can be expected to occur at low pressures making it experimentally more feasible.

AuI: Structure, Lattice Dynamics and Stability

The cubic zincblende structure of AuI belongs to the $F\bar{4}3m[216]$ space group and $m\bar{3}m$ Laue class. It is basically a stuffing of Au^{+1} and I^{-1} ions as presented in Fig. 3.18. Such crystal

structure is governed by the bulk inversion asymmetry. Since, zincblende materials are non-centrosymmetric crystal structures without polar and chiral inversion centers, we can expect that, zincblende AuI would facilitate removal of band spin degeneracies due to spin-orbit interactions (which causes the coupling of electronic spin and orbital degrees of freedom) rather than external magnetic field. The governing dynamics of spin-orbit interactions in such systems originates from the asymmetry in the potential which favours unique spin orientations splitting the electronic bands into sub-bands which are spin aligned and anti-aligned. Under generalised gradient approximations, the optimized lattice constant (a) was found to be 6.54 Å. Since, zincblende AuI was predicted for the first time, we thoroughly investigate the structural stability and experimental viability in terms of energetic, mechanical and dynamic parameters. This was necessary because, there's a lot of debate in the condensed matter community regarding the stability of zincblende phase of AuI as compared to its wurtzite polymorph.

Figure 3.18: (a) Zincblende structure of AuI with, Au (golden) and I (purple) occupying two sublattice positions. (b) Phonon dispersion curves alongside the phonon density of states (inset brillouin zone).

Energetic stability gives insights into, whether the proposed system would be experimentally feasible based on thermodynamics. We compute the formation energy ΔE_f (defined as; $\Delta E_f = E_{AuI} - n_{Au}E_{Au} - n_I E_I$; where E_x are the total energies) which can be used to predict the energetic stability of AuI. From a thermodynamic perspective, this gives insights into the type of reaction (endothermic or exothermic) which would lead to zincblende AuI. The criteria for a stable compound is that, the formation energy should be negative which indicates that, the end product is stable as compared to reactants. In case of zincblende AuI; the formation energy was found to be $\Delta E_f = -3.551$ eV/atom (since, $E_{AuI} = -1211.628$ eV/atom, $E_{Au} = -896.425$ eV/atom, $E_I = -311.652$ eV/atom, $n_{Au} = 1$ and $n_I = 1$). The negative formation energy implies that, zincblende AuI would form spontaneously when Au

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and I are brought together.

To assess the practical applications of zincblende AuI we compute the mechanical properties which can be extracted by understanding the mechanical stability of the system. For this purpose, we compute second-order elastic tensors using first-principles total-energy and/or stress calculations. The elastic tensor matrix (with units in GPa) is presented below. Born and Huang established a criteria to predict the mechanical stability of materials in bulk and low dimensional phase in terms of elastic tensors. For a cubic system, these criteria are, $c_{11} - c_{12} > 0$, $c_{11} > 0$, $c_{44} > 0$ and $c_{11} + 2c_{12} > 0$ with $c_{11} > 0$ being an extra condition.⁶² If the elastic tensors of a cubic material follow these criteria explicitly then, the material is said to be mechanically stable. These conditions are necessary and sufficient to indicate the stable or meta-stable configurations of materials.⁶³ As evident from the matrix above, the elastic tensors of AuI satisfy the Born-Huang criteria for cubic systems which indicates that zincblende AuI is mechanically stable. Apart stability, we also compute certain material properties using the elastic tensors. According to Pugh's criteria, Zincblende AuI exhibits ductile nature according to Pugh's criteria i.e., the ratio of shear modulus ($\mathcal{G} = 7.29$ GPa) to bulk modulus ($\mathcal{B} = 36.09$ GPa) is 0.20 which is < 0.57 .⁶⁴ Also, zincblende AuI exhibits a young's modulus of 20.49 GPa.⁶⁵ We use Lamé's relation to compute the Poisson's ratio which was found to be 0.41.⁶⁶ This value is comparable to isotropic engineering materials and polymers and in agreement with the ductile nature according to Pugh's criteria.⁶⁷

$$\begin{bmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} & C_{13} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C_{21} & C_{22} & C_{23} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C_{31} & C_{32} & C_{33} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{44} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{44} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 41.2 & 33.5 & 33.5 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 33.5 & 41.2 & 33.5 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 33.5 & 33.5 & 41.2 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 11.2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 11.2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 11.2 \end{bmatrix}$$

To support the energetic and mechanical picture of stability, we compute the phonon dispersion curves which are essential to probe the lattice and vibrational dynamics of zincblende AuI eventually giving insights into the stability. From Fig. 3.18 it is clear that, the phonon dispersion curves and the phonon density of states do not possess negative vibrational frequencies throughout the brillouin zone; indicating dynamic stability of zincblende AuI. As compared to the half-heuslers discussed in previous section, due to two atoms in the unit cell of zincblende AuI we have six phonon branches which are distributed into three acoustic and

three optical modes. The acoustic modes account for the coherent motion of atoms whereas, the optical modes account for the incoherent motion of atoms. Since the zincblende AuI is ionic in nature we can expect that the optical modes would be IR active (since, the incoherent displacements would give rise to time-varying electric dipole moment). Experimentally, this feature can be exploited to characterize the proposed system.

AuI: Electronic Properties

Figure 3.19: Flow chart indicating different approaches to realise non-trivial topological character in zincblende AuI. (left) Retaining cubic symmetry, under isotropic compression AuI undergoes topological phase transition from semi-metal to a topological conductor. (right) On breaking the cubic symmetry, under uni-axial compressive pressure (along [001] crystal direction) AuI undergoes topological phase transition from semi-metal to topological insulator.

Figure 3.19 presents different routes used to explore the topological quantum phase transitions in zincblende AuI. We found that, zincblende AuI exhibits anomalous behaviour as compared to its wurtzite polymorph, HgTe and other materials.^{12,56,57} Under pristine conditions, zincblende AuI exhibits a semi-metallic nature, from here we follow two routes to realise non-trivial topological character. The first one (as presented in Fig. 3.19(left)) is, to impose isotropic compressive and expansive pressure on the system. On isotropic expansion we found that, the semi-metallic nature is lost which creates a global band gap making the system a trivial insulator which can be band engineered for ultra-wide opto-electronic applications. However, under isotropic compression, the system undergoes

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non-trivial topological quantum phase transitions driving the semi-metallic system into a topological conducting state. Topological conductors exhibit Dresselhaus-like band-spin splitting governed by orbital band inversion.⁶⁸ Here, the Fermi level lies within the conduction band, hence to realise (a more desired) non-trivial topological insulating nature with the Fermi level lying in between the global gap we need to perform Fermi level engineering by varying the carrier concentrations.⁴⁸ However, if such approach is not feasible experimentally then, we can proceed with the second route (as presented in Fig. 3.19(right)). Here, we break the cubic symmetry by imposing a uni-axial compressive pressure along [001] crystal direction to realize a non-trivial topological quantum phase transition from semi-metal to topological insulator with Fermi level lying in between the global gap.⁵³ Both the routes are unique and governed by non-trivial topological band inversions involving d -orbitals originating from Au.⁵³

Figure 3.20: Orbital projected density of states (overlayed with density of states) at (a) 0%, (b) 0.5% and (c) 2% compressive pressures. (d) Electronic band structure alongside density of states showing semi-metallic nature at the center of Brillouin zone (inset, momentum path). (e) Electronic band structure hosting Dresselhaus-like band spin splitting and topological conducting state under 2% compressive pressure.

The electronic band structure of zincblende AuI exhibits Dirac degeneracies with degenerate conduction and valence band frontiers as presented in Fig. 3.20(d). As compared to wurtzite phase, the Dirac degeneracy is located at the brillouin zone center (Γ) with, p -orbitals of I and d -orbitals of Au populating the valence band and s -orbital of Au populating the conduction band (as presented in the orbital projected density of states at 0% pressure in Fig. 3.20(a)).⁵⁶ On imposing mild isotropic compressive pressure of 0.4%, AuI undergoes a topological quantum phase transitions from semi-metal to a non-trivial topological conductor with exchange of orbitals (as presented in the orbital projected density of states at 0.5% pressure in Fig. 3.20(b)).

Although, the Dirac degeneracy at the center of brillouin zone lifts off at around 0.2% only; but, the associated splitting is quite weak to realise a topological phase transition. Since appreciable splitting can be achieved under higher pressures we increased the pressure till 3% in steps of 0.2%. At 2% pressure, band splitting becomes quite prominent as presented in Fig. 3.20(e) which drives AuI into a non-trivial topological quantum phase transition. This non-trivial transition is accompanied by the exchange of orbital contributions across the Fermi level. Here, we observed a unique orbital inversion of s and p - d orbitals across the Fermi level as compared to other conventional inversions which involve on the s and/or p -orbitals. The band inversion is presented in Fig.3.20(c), in terms of the orbital projected density of states under 2% presented. Figure 3.20(e) presents the unique band-spin splitting Dresselhaus type. Such splitting originates due to the, non-centrosymmetric zincblende structure of AuI which is governed by bulk inversion asymmetry. The bulk inversion asymmetry gives rise to a perturbative Hamiltonian made up of odd powers of linear momentum (p_i , where $i = x, y, z$) and pauli spin matrices (σ_j , where $j = x, y, z$) as presented in Eq. 3.1 below.

$$H_D \propto p_x(p_y^2 - p_z^2)\sigma_x + p_y(p_z^2 - p_x^2)\sigma_y + p_z(p_x^2 - p_y^2)\sigma_z \quad (3.1)$$

The Fermi level enclosed in conduction band minima is a typical signature of a topological conductor (as evident from Fig. 3.20(e)) which is absent in the wurtzite phase of AuI.⁵⁶ The topological conducting nature originates from the band bending phenomena, hosting charge carrier accumulations on the surface. The anomalous downward band bending is quite common in several topological insulators owing to significant charge defects which alter the Fermi level in a material.⁴⁸ Hence, we can realise a non-trivial topological insulator from the topological conducting phase subjecting AuI to metal-insulator transition.⁴⁸ This can be

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done by reducing the carrier concentrations governed by the Mott transition and Ioffe-Regel criterion (which requires increase in crystal disorder).⁴⁸ However, we can circum-navigate the requirement of engineering the Fermi level by breaking the cubic symmetry.

Figure 3.21: Density of states (a) and the electronic band structure (b) (with $\pm k = \pm 2\pi/a$) at 1.1% uni-axial compressive pressure along [001] crystal direction (inset, indicates the non-trivial global band gap). (c) Orbital projected density of states indicating orbital exchange across the Fermi level. (d) Exact tight-binding model generated electronic band structure of AuI under 2% isotropic (left) and 1.1% uni-axial compression (right) respectively.

In case of semi-metallic cubic systems, it is well established in literature that, breaking the cubic symmetry would retain the orbital character of conduction and valence bands but lifts off the Dirac degeneracies at Fermi.⁵³ Hence, we subject the cubic zincblende AuI to uni-axial compressive pressure along [001] crystal direction which breaks the crystal cubic symmetry. As a result, this lifts off the Dirac degeneracies of the conduction and valence band frontiers at the center of the brillouin zone. In order a sizable gap we further increase the pressure from 0% to 2%. We come across a critical pressure at 1.1% which marks the non-trivial topological quantum phase transition.^{14,53,69} This pressure is *critical* in the sense that, the valence band and conduction band are completely resolved across Fermi level (whereas, at $1.1 \pm 0.1\%$ the valence band crosses Fermi level) giving rise to a narrow global gap in the entire brillouin zone. This band opening at the critical pressure exhibits exchange of band

dispersions across Fermi level indicating band inversion as presented in Fig. 3.21(b). A global band gap of ~ 79.84 meV was observed under the critical pressure as evident from the density of states and the electronic band structure presented in Fig. 3.21(a,b). This global band gap is narrow but superior as compared to other bulk topological insulators such as, Sb_2Se_3 and $\beta\text{-As}_2\text{Te}_3$.^{14,69} On analysing the orbital projected density of states presented in Fig. 3.21(c) we find that, the orbital inversions are same as that in semi-metal to topological conductor transition. We compared the electronic band structure with the band structure obtained from the exact tight-binding hamiltonian and found that both the systems, under isotropic compressive pressure and uni-axial compressive pressure; host spin polarization as presented in Fig. 3.21(d). The unconventional and non-trivial topological properties observed in zincblende AuI can be attributed to the compressive pressure wherein the elements come closer, eventually enhancing the spin-orbit interactions originating from strong interactions between the atomic orbitals. Such a phenomena is known as proximity induced Kane-Mele interaction, which has been previously observed in two dimensional materials.⁷⁰

AuI: Topological Properties

Following the quantitative analysis of non-trivial topological quantum phase transitions from; semi-metal to topological conductor and topological insulator, we now proceed with the quantitative analysis in terms of the surface state spectra and the \mathbb{Z}_2 invariants. Since the system is cubic which lacks inversion symmetry, we employ the wannier charge center method to compute the \mathbb{Z}_2 invariants along the time reversal invariant planes. When the cubic symmetry is retained, the principle \mathbb{Z}_2 invariant ν_0 changes from $\nu_0 = 0$ to $\nu_0 = 1$ (at 0.4% isotropic compression and beyond, till 3%). Similarly, when the cubic symmetry is broken under uni-axial pressure along [001] crystal direction, the \mathbb{Z}_2 invariants are $(\nu_0, \nu_1 \nu_2 \nu_3) = (1, 001)$ indicating that AuI is a strong topological insulator. Both the phases i.e., topological conductor and topological insulator are non-trivial and characterised by \mathbb{Z}_2 invariants. This is followed by computing the angle resolved photoemission spectroscopy-like spectra of the topological conductor and topological insulator which are presented in Fig. 3.22(a) and (b) respectively. Since the topological conductor obeys cubic symmetry the surface states are computed along the hexagonal surface which is evident from the brillouin zone path used in surface states (presented in Fig. 3.22(a)). However, when the cubic symmetry is broken the hexagonal surface loses its hexagonal symmetry hence, the brillouin zone path is presented in terms of

crystal momentum $\pm k$ (presented in Fig. 3.22(b)).

3.3 Conclusion

We presented our investigations of topological quantum phase transitions in bulk materials. We began with Half-Heusler compounds LiMgX (X = Bi, Sb, As); governed by $F\bar{4}3m$ space group with face centered cubic structures. LiMgBi was found to be dynamically stable with a direct global gap in the electronic band structure. On applying volume expansion pressure, we observed that at a critical pressure of 4.5% LiMgBi undergoes a topological quantum phase transition governed by s - p orbital band inversions with,

spin-orbit coupling interactions induced gap of 1.10 meV. The closing and opening of the band gap was verified by using hybrid functional approach apart from the generalised gradient approach. The non-trivial character

was verified by computing the surface state spectra which exhibit conducting nature. Also, we computed the \mathbb{Z}_2 invariants which were $(\nu_0, \nu_1 \nu_2 \nu_3) = (1, 0 0 0)$ which indicated that, LiMgBi is a strong topological insulator. We then presented similar phase transitions in LiMgSb, however, we observed that although LiMgSb presented band gap closing and reopening along with exchange of orbitals across Fermi level and conducting surface state spectra but, on computing the \mathbb{Z}_2 invariants we found it to be a trivial insulator. Similarly, LiMgAs which was another direct band gap semi-conductor was subjected to pressure. Similar to LiMgSb, this system also presented band gap closing and reopening with exchange of orbital characters across Fermi level and conducting surface state spectra, but on computing the \mathbb{Z}_2 invariants we found it to be a trivial insulator like LiMgSb. Although the site 'X' in LiMgX were replaced with members of pnictogen family but, we observed contradicting topological properties. With this

Figure 3.22: Angle resolved photoemission spectroscopy-like spectra of AuI indicating surface states in (a) topological conducting phase and (b) topological insulating phase.

we established the necessary and sufficient condition for realising a non-trivial topological insulator i.e., apart from band gap closing and reopening, orbital inversion across Fermi level and conducting surface state spectra, the system should *necessarily* exhibit non-trivial \mathbb{Z}_2 invariants. Further, since these systems (LiMgSb, and LiMgAs) presented topological phase transitions at very high pressures we proposed that, dimensionally engineered monolayers can be realised using these bulk materials to realise non-trivial topological quantum phase transitions at relatively lower pressures.

Another problem in the topological insulator LiMgBi was that, the conduction bands crossed the Fermi level during the topological phase transitions. We addressed this issue by breaking the cubic symmetry and converting the material from a topological conductor to a topological insulator. We presented this phenomena in binary zincblende compound AuI. Although the stability of such a compound has been debated but, on computing phonon dispersion curves, formation energy and elastic tensors we found that, AuI is dynamically, energetically and mechanically stable. We followed two approaches to realise non-trivial topological properties in this binary compound, (i) application of isotropic ompression and (ii) application of uni-axial compressive pressure along [001] crystal direction. We observed semi-metal to topological conductor and topological insulator transitions respectively under the said approaches. We observed that, due to the bulk inversion asymmetry, AuI exhibits Dresselhaus-like band-spin splittings characterized by unconventional s , p - d orbital band inversions. The non-trivial nature was confirmed by computing the conducting surface state spectra and the principle \mathbb{Z}_2 invariant which was $\nu_0 = 1$ (when cubic symmetry was retained and broken).

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CHAPTER 4

Topological Insulating Phase in Some Low Dimensional Materials

In this chapter we discuss three methods such as, dimensional engineering, application of stress/strain and, partial functionalization, by which non-trivial topological insulating nature can be realised in two dimensional materials LiMgAs, AuI, Tellurene and Selenene. We discuss these non-trivial character in terms of qualitative and quantitative analysis (similar to that in chapter 3) wherein we present, non-trivial band and orbital inversions, unconventional Berry and spin-Berry curvature, quantum conductivity, \mathbb{Z}_2 invariant (ν), angle resolved photoemission spectroscopy-like edge state spectra and slab band structures. Apart from this, we also discuss methods to practically realise such materials. These studies are presented with investigation of material stability in terms of phonon dispersion curves, AIMD etc.

4.1 Dimensionally Engineered Topological Insulator: LiMgAs

Over the past two decades, low dimensional topological materials such as, two dimensional topological insulators have sparked immense excitement in the field of condensed matter physics. This is because of the non-trivial characteristics such as, insulating bulk and helical edge conducting states.¹⁻⁵ These states are robust against material impurities and back-scattering which ensures dissipationless transport of electrons in perpetual helical paths along

the edges. Eversince the prediction of topological insulators in low dimensional systems such as, graphene and HgTe/CdTe quantum wells, several materials have been predicted and experimentally realised to host the topological insulating nature.⁶⁻¹² Similar to the bulk materials where the spin-orbit interactions were enhanced by various mechanisms, in the low dimensional materials several techniques have been explored to realise similar effects. For example, in order to enhance the spin-orbit interactions in low dimensional materials and to induce non-trivial topological properties in them via topological quantum phase transitions, techniques such as, (i) application of strain/pressure, (ii) doping, (iii) variation of layer thickness, (iv) van der Waals layered systems or stacking effect and, (v) application of electric field etc. have been proposed. Also, elemental monolayers such as, silicene, germanene and stanene are known to exhibit non-trivial topological insulating nature by the virtue of enhanced spin-orbit interactions which originate from the buckling in these monolayers.⁸⁻¹² However, buckling solely does not guarantee that the system would be topologically non-trivial. For example, arsenene and antimonene exhibit buckled structure but, these monolayers are non-trivial only under the influence of tensile strain.^{11,12} Although, these low dimensional materials exhibit non-trivial topologies, they are inefficient and tough to be realised at room temperatures since, the spin-orbit interactions induced global gap in the brillouin zone are smaller than the thermal perturbations at room temperature. This indicates that, there is a lot of scope to explore other potential materials which can have room temperature applications. This motivated us to explore low dimensional materials for non-trivial topological properties.

There are several methods by which we can design low dimensional materials such as, free standing structures, structures supported by substrates etc. Here, we began our investigations by dimensionally engineering low dimensional structures from bulk crystal surfaces. This was achieved by isolating and confining the material along a particular crystal direction. For example, we performed one dimensional confinement of [111] crystal plane cleaved from the bulk half-Heusler compound LiMgAs. This dimensionally engineered system was investigated for non-trivial topological properties originating from the quantum confinement effects. We observed that, the low dimensional material designed by such method is superior as compared to their bulk parents. Therefore, we successfully address the issues which we came across in material design as discussed in previous chapters. For example, as proposed in previous chapter, we do observe non-trivial topologies in low dimensional phase as compared to the trivial topologies in the bulk parent. Also, since the surface-to-volume ratio is high, the

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pressure required to realise non-trivial topologies is quite low as compared to the bulk. Such method of material design is reliable since, it has been previously explored in NbN wherein, the [100] and [111] crystal planes were isolated by dimensional engineering from the rocksalt parent structure for photocatalytic and piezoelectric applications.¹³ This method can also be thought of as an analogue to the variation of thickness of the material wherein, by reducing the layers of a material, eventually a monolayer is achieved (as in the case of graphene which is a monolayer of graphite).

Structure and Lattice Dynamics

Figure 4.1: (a) Bulk structure of half-Heusler LiMgAs and its [111] crystal plane (b). (c) One-dimensional quantum confinement by introducing 15 Å vacuum in z-direction. (d, e) Side and top view of the low-dimensional supercell. (f) Irreducible first Brillouin zones of the bulk and low-dimensional of LiMgAs.

We designed a low-dimensional phase of LiMgAs by cleaving [111] crystal plane from the bulk face-centered cubic structure and isolating it along the z-direction by introducing a vacuum (as presented in Fig. 4.1(a-c)). Under generalised gradient approximations, this structure exhibits a trigonal structure governed by the $P\bar{3}m1[164]$ space group (similar to 1T-MoS₂) with optimized lattice constant (a) of 4.28 Å (as evident from Fig. 4.1(c)). We can think of this structure as an atomic sandwich wherein, As atoms are stuffed between the top layer of Li and bottom layer of Mg as presented in Fig. 4.1(d,e). The thickness (layer height) of such atomic sandwich is 1.60 Å. Here, the interatomic distances of As-Mg and As-Li are 2.58 Å and 2.62 Å respectively. The quantum confinement along one dimension is

Figure 4.2: Phonon dispersion curves and density of states indicating dynamic stability of low dimensional LiMgAs.

achieved due to the vacuum of 15 (Å) along the z -direction which is also introduced to avoid interlayer interactions or interactions between the periodic images as show in Fig. 4.1(c).

Since this structure is being predicted for the first time, we investigated its dynamic stability (in terms of the phonon dispersion curves and phonon density of states) to comment on the experimental feasibility of such structure. From our computations of the phonon dispersion curves and the phonon density of states presented in Fig. 4.2, it is clear that, the absence of negative phonon frequencies throughout the brillouin zone indicate towards the dynamic stability of the proposed structure. The unit cell of the proposed structure hosts three atoms giving rise to nine phonon branches similar to the bulk parent. Contrary to the bulk phase wherein, the nine phonon branches were composed of three in plane acoustic branches (dominant at lower frequencies) and six optical branches (dominant at higher frequencies), the nine phonon branches in the low dimensional phase exhibits are composed of, three in plane acoustic branches, three out-of-plane acoustic (ZA) and optical (ZO) branches (due to the one dimensional quantum confinement owing to the 15 Å vacuum along z -direction) and, three optical branches.

Electronic Properties

The low dimensional phase of LiMgAs exhibits a semi-conducting nature with a direct band gap of 1.56 eV at the center of the brillouin zone (as evident from Fig. 4.3) as compared to the bulk which had a slightly smaller indirect band gap. This is due to the quantum

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confinement effects wherein, the electronic degrees of freedom are different as compared to the bulk. Throughout the Brillouin zone the conduction band and valence band frontiers are non-degenerate. However, in the vicinity of Fermi, the valence band maxima along the high symmetry paths, $L \rightarrow \Gamma$ and $W \rightarrow X$ is degenerate while, along the paths $X \rightarrow U \rightarrow L$ and $\Gamma \rightarrow K \rightarrow W$ they are non-degenerate (as evident from Fig. 2.27). This feature is exactly similar to the bulk parent.

Figure 4.3: Electronic band structure of low dimensional LiMgAs.

Fermion velocities of the order of $v_f \sim 0.56 \text{ ms}^{-1}$ and $\sim 1.31 \text{ ms}^{-1}$ along the high symmetry path $K \rightarrow \Gamma$ and $\Gamma \rightarrow M$ respectively in the Brillouin zone. Similarly, the valence band maxima hosts Fermion velocities of the order of, $v_f \sim 11.13 \text{ ms}^{-1}$ and $\sim 7.64 \text{ ms}^{-1}$ along high symmetry path $K \rightarrow \Gamma$ and $\Gamma \rightarrow M$ respectively in the Brillouin zone. These Fermion velocities are comparable to that of graphene (in a particular momentum direction) and superior to other two dimensional materials. Owing to the extra electronic degrees of freedom due to quantum confinement, the low dimensional exhibits higher Fermion velocities as compared to the bulk parent. Beyond the critical point (which hosts Dirac degeneracies at the center of Brillouin zone) in the topological quantum phase transition, the bulk electronic band structure hosts a global gap in the Brillouin zone. Also, as evident from Fig. 4.4(right), the band degeneracy in the valence band maxima lifts off giving rise to Fermionic contributions in the vacant conduction band.

With further increase in the compressive pressure we observed topological quantum phase transition i.e., the Dirac degeneracy at Γ lifts off creating a gap which indicates the topological insulating nature. This critical pressure is quite small (2.96 GPa) as compared to

On imposing isotropic compressive pressure on the low dimensional structure of LiMgAs we observed that, the band gap reduces; eventually forming a Dirac degeneracy (at 10% compressive pressures presented in Fig. 4.4) at the center of the Brillouin zone (Γ) marking the critical point in the topological quantum phase transition. The Dirac degeneracy of the conduction and valence band frontiers; exhibit remarkable Fermion velocities.¹⁴ The conduction band minima hosts

Figure 4.4: Electronic band structure of low dimensional LiMgAs at (left) 8% and (right) 10% pressure.

Figure 4.5: Orbital projected density of states without spin-orbit interactions (top) and with spin-orbit interactions (bottom) before (left) and at critical pressure (right) respectively, hosting exchanged orbital features around Fermi.

the bulk parent wherein the pressure was of the order of 8.18 GPa. The non-trivial topological quantum phase transition can be analysed in terms of the orbital projected density of states which indicates the exchange of orbital contributions across the Fermi level. From the orbital projected density of states presented in Fig. 4.5, we observe that, the orbital exchange is quite strong as compared to that in the bulk phase.

The proposed low dimensional LiMgAs exhibits orbital orders similar to that of the bulk parent i.e., the valence band is populated by the p -orbital and the conduction band is

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populated by the s -orbital. Under critical compressive pressure, the s -orbitals in conduction band penetrate the valence band and the p -orbital from valence band penetrates the conduction band. Such band orbital order is somewhat similar to that of HgTe.¹⁵ This implies that, the p -orbital Fermions of As atom are the major contributors to the observed non-trivial topological insulating nature. In the proposed low dimensional LiMgAs, the band inversion strength is positive and strong i.e., $\Delta \sim 113.7$ meV as compared to the bulk parent favouring non-trivial phase of LiMgAs in the proposed low dimensional structure.^{15,16} When, the spin-orbit interactions (which is quite pronounced in this phase due to buckling as compared to the bulk phase) are considered a global gap of ~ 55.0 meV is observed while the non-global gap is as high as 0.16 eV.¹⁰ This is superior to graphene, silicene, arsenene etc.^{6,11,17} Figure 4.6(left) and (right) represent; the band inverted dispersions with and without the spin-orbit interactions (under critical pressure), alongside the schematic inversion mechanism in terms of orbital contributions under 0% and 10% pressure respectively. The band dispersions due to spin-orbit interactions indicates that, the proposed low dimensional phase can have applications in spintronics at room temperature.^{18,19}

Figure 4.6: (left) Electronic band dispersions of low dimensional LiMgAs with and without spin-orbit interactions (under critical pressure). (right) Schematic representation of the orbital inversion mechanism due to pressure and spin-orbit interactions at 0% and 10% pressure.

Topological Properties

Following the qualitative description of non-trivial topological quantum phase transitions in the low dimensional phase of LiMgAs, we now discuss the quantitative descriptions in terms of the angle resolved photoemission spectroscopy-like spectra and \mathbb{Z}_2 . Figure 4.7 represents the conducting edge states in the presence of the spin-orbit interaction induced bulk gap (under critical pressure). These non-trivial edge states are confirmed for their non-trivial character

Figure 4.7: Angle resolved photoemission spectroscopy-like spectra indicating conducting edge states.

by computing the \mathbb{Z}_2 invariant (ν). We can compute the \mathbb{Z}_2 by using Fu and Kane method discussed in chapter 2 and/or by computing the wannier charge centers across the Fermi at time reversal invariant planes. We find that, the \mathbb{Z}_2 is $\nu = 1$ confirming the non-trivial nature topological insulating nature of low dimensional LiMgAs as compared to the trivial bulk. This affirmatively confirms that, dimensional engineering method can be used to realise non-trivial topological materials from trivial bulk parents.

4.2 Functionalization; a Tool for Large-gap Topological Insulator

For room temperature applications in, spintronics, valleytronics, electronic and quantum computation, the persistence of conducting edge states (robust against weak deformations and external perturbations) are necessary. This is possible if the low dimensional material possesses large-gap due to spin-orbit interactions. If the gap is smaller than the thermal energy at room temperature then, irrespective of symmetry protection, the conducting edge states would annihilate. This indicates that, a large-gap low dimensional topological insulator is desired and needed for practical applications which would host, gapless spin-polarized helical edge states with non-magnetic insulating global gap in bulk, spin currents protected against backscattering and, quantized Hall conductance without magnetic field.

Although, graphene and other group IV and V elements have been previously explored for non-trivial topological insulating nature from theoretical perspective but, phenomena could be observed experimentally at ultra-low temperatures and ultra-high pressures in quantum wells of HgTe/CdTe and InAs/GaSb.^{20–32} This has motivated numerous investigations based

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on *first-principles* and theoretical modelling methods guiding the experimental efforts. In spite of several methods proposed theoretically, one of the persistent problems is realising large-gap low dimensional topological insulators. As an alternative, this had been addressed by using functionalization techniques in monolayers of group IV, V; Xene's and MXene's etc. The governing phenomena is that of orbital filtering effect wherein, p_z -orbitals in the monolayer are saturated by the functional molecule which enhances the spin-orbit interactions.^{24,33-43} This technique has been found to be viable experimentally. For example, halogenation of Bi monolayers was observed to induce non-trivial topological insulating states. However, these states were sensitive to hybridizations with the substrates which made it less reliable. Apart from this, other problems such as, effects of environmental oxidation and eventual degradation of the edge state makes low dimensional topological insulators vulnerable; hindering their practical applications.⁴⁴

Inspired by the investigation of group IV and V elemental monolayers for non-trivial topologies, efforts were made to explore similar features in group VI Xene's with honeycomb lattice structure for example, in tellurium and selenium based monolayers. It was speculated that, honeycomb lattice structure cannot be achieved with tellurium and selenium owing to their electronic configurations. Rather, these elemental monolayers have been observed to exhibit ring, chain, square and rectangular lattice structures.^{31,42,47} Contrary to such studies, in an experimental effort, recently it was observed that, thickness-dependent transition from Au-Te surface alloy to honeycomb lattice of tellurium (i.e., 3×3 superstructures) can be achieved due to the fact that, Tellurium atoms self-organise themselves on Au[111] surface (under high temperatures and ultra-high vacuum) with 0.5 monolayer coverage.⁴⁸ This motivated us to ask the question, are there any other alternatives by which we can realise dynamically stable honeycomb lattice structure of tellurium and selenium? Also, if such alternative exists, leading to the monolayers tellurene and selenene then, can they host non-trivial topologies?

We addressed these questions by employing *first-principles* computation to investigate, (i) the stability of tellurene and selenene, (ii) the role of *functionalization* in the stability of such monolayers and (iii) the corresponding effects on the on-trivial topological properties. We found that, pristine elemental monolayers of tellurene and selenene are not dynamically stable, which is in agreement with previous studies.⁴⁹ However, on performing functionalization with oxygen and sulphur, the dynamic stability was achieved. We found that, upon functionalization, by the virtue of orbital filtering effects the proposed monolayers host

large-gap topological insulating behaviour due to strong spin-orbit interactions. This implies that, the proposed monolayers can be experimentally viable for potential applications. We restrict our discussions to non-trivial topological properties observed in oxygen functionalised tellurene and sulphur functionalised selenene, since these materials host large-gap governed by spin-orbit interactions which are superior to several other materials.

Structure and Lattice Dynamics

Figure 4.8: Phonon dispersion curves alongside the phonon density of states of tellurene monolayer (top) and oxygen functionalised tellurene monolayer (bottom).

We began our investigations with honeycomb lattice structures of tellurene and selenene; similar to graphene and other group IV and V elemental monolayers. Under the generalised gradient approximations, the optimized lattice constant (a) of tellurene and selenene were, 4.94 \AA and 4.36 \AA respectively. These structures are buckled and not planar like graphene with, buckling height (h) of 0.72 \AA and 0.63 \AA respectively. The angle between the tellurium atoms and selenium atoms are 114.14° and 114.29° respectively. However, we found that, the elemental monolayers i.e., tellurene and selenene are dynamically unstable since, the phonon dispersion curves indicate the presence of negative phonon frequencies (as presented in Fig. 4.8(top) and Fig. 4.10(top-left) respectively). Such dynamical instability of tellurene and selenene is in agreement with previous studies.⁴⁹ This confirms that, electronic configurations

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of tellurium and selenium do not facilitate the formation of, *sp*-hybridizations and reactive surfaces due to dangling bonds.⁵⁰

Figure 4.9: Phonon dispersion curves (inset, crystal structures) of, selenene monolayer (top-left), sulphur functionalised selenene monolayer (top-right), oxygen functionalised selenene monolayer (bottom-left) and, sulphur functionalised tellurene monolayer (bottom-right).

We proceed with functionalization of tellurene and selenene with oxygen and sulphur at alternate sub-lattice positions of the honeycomb lattice. The choice of oxygen and sulphur was made since, they can form bonds with tellurium and selenium due to their electronic configurations. The resulting structures of TeO, SeS and, SeO; did not exhibit imaginary modes or negative phonon frequencies in the entire brillouin zone (except TeS which is unstable) as evident from the phonon dispersion curves presented in Fig. 4.8(bottom) and Fig. 4.9. It is worth mentioning that, the phonon dispersion curves presented in Fig. 4.9 exhibit soft phonon modes along brillouin zone path, $M \rightarrow K \rightarrow \Gamma$ which points towards structural instability at higher temperatures. Hence, we arrive at the most sought-after honeycomb lattice structures in tellurene and selenene. These structures (presented as insets in Fig. 4.8 and 4.9) are governed by the D_{3d} point group symmetry which is lower than D_{6h} point group symmetry of graphene. This leads to a broken spatial inversion symmetry in the proposed systems. Under generalised gradient approximations, the optimized lattice constant (*a*) of TeO and TeS was found to be, 5.26 Å and 5.36 Å, with reduced buckling height (*h*) of 0.57 Å and 0.81 Å and a layer thickness (*t*) of 4.18 Å and 5.28 Å respectively. Similarly, the lattice constant (*a*);

buckling height (h) and; layer thickness (t) in SeO and SeS were found to be, 4.79 Å, 4.80 Å; 0.68 Å, 0.91 Å and 4 Å, 5.04 Å respectively. The angle between the constituent atoms in TeO; TeS; SeO and SeS were found to be, $\angle\text{O-Te-Te} = 100.74^\circ$, $\angle\text{Te-Te-Te} = 116.61^\circ$; $\angle\text{S-Te-Te} = 104.68^\circ$, $\angle\text{Te-Te-Te} = 113.80^\circ$; $\angle\text{O-Se-Se} = 103.87^\circ$, $\angle\text{Se-Se-Se} = 114.44^\circ$ and; $\angle\text{S-Se-Se} = 108.12^\circ$, $\angle\text{Se-Se-Se} = 110.79^\circ$ respectively. We observed that, apart from stability, the functionalization of tellurene and selenene leads to the saturation of out of plane p_z -orbitals (also known as dangling bonds) of Te and Se; ultimately giving rise to sp^3 -hybridization and enhanced spin-orbit interactions.^{24,41} We discuss the qualitative and quantitative analysis of TeO and SeS in this chapter since, these systems exhibit promising and exciting properties.

Electronic Properties

Figure 4.10: Electronic band structure and density of states indicating semi-metallic nature of TeO (inset, density of states close to Fermi level and, bulk Brillouin zone with highlighted edge Brillouin zone).

From Fig. 4.10 it is evident that, in the absence of spin-orbit interactions, TeO exhibits graphene-like semi-metallic with almost linear dispersions hosting Dirac degeneracies of the conduction and valence band frontiers along the high symmetry point K in the Brillouin zone. Whereas, SeO and SeS exhibit a semi-conducting character with global gaps of the order of 10^{-3} eV (i.e., in SeO the gap is 1.8 meV and in SeS it is 2.3 meV as evident from Fig. 4.11) along the high symmetry point K in the Brillouin zone. Since these energy gaps are far lower than the thermal energy at room temperature (which is typically 25 meV at 300 K) we can assume that, SeO and SeS would be semi-metallic in nature at room temperature.

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Figure 4.11: Electronic band structures of SeO (top) and SeS (bottom) in the absence of spin-orbit interactions.

the orbital projected density of states (presented in Fig. 4.13(left)) that the orbital inversion mechanism occurs due to the p -orbitals of Te and O.

The electronic band structures of TeO and SeS, with and without spin-orbit interactions are presented in Fig. 4.12. When spin-orbit interactions are considered, we observe that, the Dirac degeneracies are annihilated along the high symmetry point K in TeO and SeS, rendering a global large-gap of 0.365 eV and 0.167 eV respectively. Such unusual behaviour originates due to the orbital filtering effects. Since, the spin-orbit interaction induced gap is highest in TeO; we discuss it in detail in the following paragraphs (since all the effects in SeS would be similar to those as observed in TeO). The strong spin-orbit interaction can be interpreted in terms of dominant σ orbitals around the Fermi energy, rather than the π orbitals as evident Fig. 4.13(right).³⁵ Also, we can observe from the

Figure 4.12: Electronic band structure of TeO (left) and SeS (right) with and without spin-orbit interactions.

Such non-trivial orbital inversions and spin-orbit interactions induced large-gap indicates towards potential non-trivial topological insulating nature of TeO. The orbital inversion mechanism is understood as; the splitting of p -orbital near Fermi level into; p_z and (p_x, p_y)

due to the D_{3d} point group symmetry and the D_3 groups of wave vector at Dirac degeneracies along K and K' point in the Brillouin zone governing the system. Hence, the flat bands (in valence band) made up of px , py -orbitals and the massive Dirac cones make TeO unique as compared to graphene. This implies that TeO can be thought of as an orbital analog of quantum anomalous Hall effect and Wigner crystallization.³⁰

Figure 4.13: (left) Orbital projected density of states TeO (top) without and (bottom) with spin-orbit interactions indicating exchange of p -orbitals across the Fermi level highlighted by downward arrows. (right) π and σ orbitals projected electronic band structures (top) without and (bottom) with spin-orbit interactions.

Substrate Effects

Apart from the free standing monolayer of TeO discussed in previous sections, it was necessary to explore the quantum well heterostructures for practical applications. We designed van der Waals quantum well heterostructure using a 2×2 hexagonal-Boron Nitride (h BN) monolayer (as presented in Fig. 4.15). We sandwich the TeO monolayer between two layers of h BN creating a

Figure 4.14: Electronic band structure of quantum well h BN/TeO/ h BN.

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quantum well of the form $h\text{BN}/\text{TeO}/h\text{BN}$. With the lattice mismatch of $\sim 4.79\%$, the interlayer separations were varied from 3 \AA to 6 \AA to observe the effects of van der Waals interactions at different separations. On optimizing the system by including the van der Waals correlation corrections, we observed that, TeO and $h\text{BN}$ monolayers retained their original structures. On subjecting this heterostructure to a tensile strain of $\sim 14\%$ the system retained its non-trivial global gap of $\sim 0.11 \text{ eV}$ (evident from Fig. 4.14). This is considerably higher as compared to the thermal energy at room temperature with majority contribution arising from TeO around the Fermi energy.

Figure 4.15: Schematic representation of van der Waals; $h\text{BN}/\text{TeO}/h\text{BN}$ quantum well device under isotropic tensile strain.

This is due to weak interlayer coupling or absence of interlayer hybridization (as evident from the charge density plot in Fig. 4.15) of TeO and $h\text{BN}$ at interlayer separation of 6 \AA . Hence, the proposed structure would electrically insulate the layers of TeO protecting the spin-polarised helical edge states. This increases the number of edge transport channels to host dissipationless charge-spin transport.³⁷ We discuss the stability of such a heterostructure in terms of the formation / binding energy (E_b) which is defined as; $E_b = E_{hetero} - E_{TeO} - 2 \cdot E_{hBN}$, where, E_{hetero} is total energy of the heterostructure, E_{TeO} and E_{hBN} are the total energies of TeO and $h\text{BN}$ monolayers. The binding energy was found to be -0.904 eV indicating that, the proposed structure under 14% tensile strain would be thermodynamically stable and

experimentally viable.

Topological Properties

Figure 4.16: (left-top) *Berry* curvature mapping the entire brillouin zone; indicates opposite signs. (left-bottom) *k*-resolved spin *Berry* curvature mapped along the brillouin zone valley points K' (area under curve = 41.57 arb. units) and K (area under curve = 41.46 arb. units). (right-top) Spin projected electronic band structure along the brillouin zone valley points K' and K (inset temperature scale indicates, positive and negative spin). (right-bottom) Electronic band structure (with and without spin-orbit interactions) along the brillouin zone valley points K' and K .

We quantified the non-trivial topological properties of TeO in terms of the \mathbb{Z}_2 invariant ν by using the wilson loops method around wannier charge centers. We found that, the invariant $\nu = 1$ indicates that the system is a two dimensional topological insulator. We also analysed the *Berry* curvature distribution in the entire brillouin zone (as presented in Fig. 4.16) for the n^{th} occupied band. By integrating the *Berry* curvature throughout the brillouin zone, we found the Chern number to be $C = 1$ which further confirms the non-trivial topological insulating character of the system.

The bulk-boundary correspondance is a characteristic phenomena observed in non-trivial topological insulators. This implies that, the bulk global gap due to spin-orbit interactions would host conducting states along the edges of TeO monolayer. The edge conducting edge

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states are confirmed by computing the angle resolved photoemission spectroscopy-like spectra along the high symmetry paths corresponding to the orthorhombic edge Brillouin zone. It is evident from Fig. 4.17 that, TeO monolayer is a two dimensional topological insulator hosting robust conducting edge states along the high symmetry point S of the edge Brillouin zone.

We further analysed the origin and nature of spin Hall conductivity in TeO monolayer. As the strong spin-orbit interactions annihilate the Dirac degeneracy along the high symmetry point K in the Brillouin zone (with the Fermi energy within the global gap), we can expect significantly large spin Hall conductivity.⁵¹ This is due to the spin *Berry* curvature contributions arising from the positive and negative spins around Fermi energy which do not cancel-out excluding one sign of spin *Berry* curvature to persist. Such spin *Berry* curvature governed topology in TeO gives rise to unconventionally large transverse spin Hall conductivity (σ_{xy}^z) of the order of ≈ 63.25 (\hbar/e) $\Omega^{-1}cm^{-1}$ (as evident from Fig. 4.18).

Figure 4.17: Conducting edge states in TeO.

Figure 4.18: Fermi energy scan of the spin Hall conductivity ($\sigma_{xy}^{spinz}(\omega)$) in units of (\hbar/e) $\Omega^{-1}cm^{-1}$ (red line is the Fermi level and green lines indicate non-trivial global gap).

electrons from different valleys (K' and K) would experience opposite Lorentz forces which

This value is quite high as compared to other systems indicating a higher charge-spin-current conversion efficiency.^{52,53} The absence of quantization in the spin Hall conductivity (as the function of Fermi energy) can be attributed to the presence of buckling in the system.⁵² From the *Berry* curvature plot (presented in Fig. 4.16) we observe sharp peaks in the valley region of the Brillouin zone with opposite signs at K' and K which implies that TeO can host valley Hall effects.⁵⁴ This indicates that, when the TeO monolayer is subjected to a voltage bias, the

would give rise to electronic motion in opposite directions perpendicular to the drift current, eventually creating a charge-spin segregation and making the system a quantum valley Hall insulator.⁵⁵ The behaviour is clearly evident from the spin projected electronic band structure and the electronic band structures (with and without spin-orbit interactions) along the brillouin zone valley points K' and K presented in Fig. 4.16.⁵⁴

Figure 4.19: (top-left) Slab band structures indicating the conducting edge states (arrows indicate Dirac dispersions). (top-right) Angle resolved photoemission spectroscopy-like spectra indicating the conducting edge state spectra (arrows indicate Dirac dispersions). (bottom) Conducting edge spin density of states indicating spin polarizations in [100] and [010] crystal directions respectively.

Similarly, we confirmed the non-trivial topological insulating nature of SeS by plotting the slab band structures of SeS in nanoribbon configurations which are governed by the orthorhombic brillouin zone. It is evident from these slab band structures (presented in Fig. 4.19) that, SeS hosts conducting states along the edges while the bulk exhibits a global gap due to spin-orbit interactions. We also computed the angle resolved photoemission spectroscopy-like spectra which indicates conducting Dirac dispersions between the high symmetry points

Γ and X (which is equivalent to high symmetry point K in a hexagonal Brillouin zone). The helical edge states of a two dimensional topological insulator are spin-polarised. This is evident from the spin-density of states along the edge crystal directions [100] and [010] which clearly indicate spin polarization as presented in Fig. 4.19. Apart from these plots, we also computed the \mathbb{Z}_2 invariant ν which turns out to be $\nu = 1$, confirming the non-trivial topological insulating nature of SeS monolayer.

4.3 Strain Induced Topological Insulator: AuI

By our investigations on, LiMgAs (which addressed the issue of realising a non-trivial topological behaviour in a dimensionally engineered material) and design of large-gap topological insulators TeO and SeS (wherein the partial functionalizations with oxygen and sulphur gave rise to non-trivial topological behaviour due to the orbital filtering effects) we demonstrated different methods by which non-trivial topologies can be realised in low dimensional materials. Thus contributing to the material repository which hosts previously explored two dimensional topological insulators such as in, Xenes, functionalised MXenes, transition-metal dichalcogenides and metal halides.^{12,22–28,30,31,37,56–61} With our work on LiMgAs we reiterate that, if a low dimensional material does not exhibit topological insulating nature intrinsically (as observed in TeO and SeS) then, they can be explored by driving the system through a topological quantum phase transition by imposing strain on the system. In such process of materials design, we come across dilemma when, a low dimensional material hosts non-trivial topological properties but is impractical due to its toxicity. For example, Lead (Pb) based two dimensional materials are known to exhibit topological insulating properties, however, these materials are practically not viable due to the toxicity associated with Pb (with synthesis, use and recycle of such materials being next to impossible).²⁴ Hence, it is clear that, the process of design and prediction of a novel two dimensional topological insulator is quite challenging from materials science point-of-view. One thing that motivates the research in materials science and condensed matter physics is the versatility of a material i.e., a single material with multi-functional applications. For example, a material which is topologically insulating may be a good catalyst, may host high thermoelectric conversion efficiencies etc. With this background, we were motivated us to ask a question, can we design/realise a two dimensional topological insulator using a transition-metal element?

We therefore, explored Gold Iodide (AuI) monolayer which was dimensionally engineered from its bulk zincblende parent discussed in chapter 3. Such a system can be synthesized through conventional routes such as, chemical vapour deposition, molecular beam epitaxy and cleaving/exfoliating it from its bulk parent. Also, since AuI contains Au (which is one of the precious metals) we can explore it for multifunctional properties such as electro-catalysis, thermoelectric etc.

Structure, Lattice Dynamics and AIMD

Figure 4.20: (a) Primitive cell side view of zincblende AuI with highlighted [111] crystal plane; having layer thickness of 0.94 Å. (b) Top view of [111] crystal plane isolated from the primitive cell of the zincblende AuI.

We began our investigation by isolating AuI monolayers from [111] crystal plane of the zincblende AuI structure (which exhibits topological conducting and insulating nature as discussed in chapter 3) as presented in Fig. 4.20. This structure exhibits buckling and is governed by $P3m1[156]$ space group. However, the buckling (~ 0.94 Å) vanishes on relaxing the structure which implies that, the system undergoes a structural phase transition (as presented in Fig. 4.22). The structural phase transition occurs from the buckled phase of $P3m1[156]$ to planar phase of $P6_3mmc[194]$ space group. The planar structure marks the global minima under generalised gradient approximation with optimized lattice constant (a) of 4.72 Å (with two sub-lattice positions occupied by Au and I). To simulate an ideal two dimensional monolayer, the system was confined along [001] crystal direction by introducing a vacuum of 25 Å. The bond length between Au and I is 2.73 Å, the angle $\angle Au-I-Au$ is 119.88° and $\angle I-Au-I$ is 120.24°.

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Figure 4.21: Phonon dispersion curve alongside phonon density of states indicating dynamic stability of the, (a) P3m1 phase (before relaxing the structure) and (b) P6₃mmc phase (after relaxing the structure) of AuI monolayer. (c) Structural stability at 300 K and 3 picoseconds time step of ab-initio molecular dynamics simulation. (d) Variation of temperature and total energy of AuI monolayer at different time steps of simulation.

Both the phases of AuI are dynamically stable as evident from the phonon dispersion curves and the phonon density of states presented in Fig. 4.21. Since there are two atoms in the unit cell, the phonon dispersion curves comprise of six phonon branches which can be decomposed into three acoustic and three optical branches. It is evident from the phonon dispersion curves that, the longitudinal and transverse optical (LO-TO) modes are non-degenerate at the center of the Brillouin zone indicating towards the ionic character of AuI which is governed by long-range Coulomb interactions. Also, the out-of-plane ZA and ZO modes in the acoustic and optical branches confirm the two-dimensional nature of the system. We also compute the formation energy (given by, $E_f = E_{AuI} - E_{Au} - E_I$ where, E_X ($X = AuI, Au, I$) are the total energies) to get insights into the thermodynamic stability and viability of the proposed system. We found that, the ground state of AuI monolayer turns out to be highly thermodynamically stable with formation energy of the order of -3.814 eV/atom which is lower than the formation energy of the zincblende parent i.e., -3.551 eV/atom. This implies that, AuI monolayers can be synthesized via conventional methods such as, chemical vapour deposition or molecular beam epitaxy ensuring layer-by-layer growth of a material along the crystal direction of choice. Also, from the ab-initio molecular dynamics simulations at 300 K we found that, the

structural integrity is retained throughout the 3 picoseconds (3000 femtoseconds) simulation time indicating that, AuI monolayer would be stable at room temperature.

Electronic Properties

Figure 4.22: (a) Total energy (in Ry units) variation with % strain. The cyan background indicate trivial insulator nature of AuI and white region indicates topological insulating nature. The black dashed line marks the structural phase transition from $P3m1$ to $P6_3mmc$ phase. (i) Critical DP at 2% strain, ii) narrow gap at 0% strain and, iii) enhanced gap at 3% strain. (b) Electronic band structure at 0% strain alongside density of states with inset of hexagonal brillouin zone.

Under pristine conditions (i.e., in the ground state at 0% strain) the planar phase of AuI exhibits a narrow gap of ~ 14.4 meV (as evident from Fig. 4.22(a(ii))) at the brillouin zone center (as presented in Fig. 4.22(b)). This phase marks the global minima of as evident from the energy versus strain plot in Fig. 4.22(a). Now, to realise a non-trivial topological quantum phase transition and to investigate the topological character of the gap at 0% strain, we search for a critical Dirac point in the vicinity of global minima by imposing bi-axial compressive and tensile strain of $\pm 10\%$. We found that, the critical point hosting Dirac degeneracy exists at a compressive strain of -2% (as resented in Fig. 4.22(a(i))). Hence, -2% marks the lower boundary of the non-trivial topological quantum phase transitions. Below this strain, the system exhibits trivial semi-conducting nature hosting a global band gap of 0.5 eV at -5% strain and 0.8 eV at -10% strain along the brillouin zone center. We performed qualitative analysis of the non-trivial topological quantum phase transition in terms of the orbital projected density of states presented in Fig. 4.23. It is evident from the orbital projected density of states that, at -2% strain (i.e., critical point) and the strain regime below it; the valence band is populated with p - d hybrid orbitals of I and Au respectively (as evident from Fig. 4.23(a)) and the conduction band is populated by the s -orbitals of Au and I and s - p hybrid orbitals of Au

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and I (as evident from Fig. 4.23(a)). Such orbital distributions are common in transition metal based topological insulators or topological materials due to partially filled d -orbitals.^{36,62,63}

Figure 4.23: Orbital projected density of states at: (a) 2% strain, (b) 0% strain, and (c) 3% strain. (d) Topological quantum phase transitions in terms of the inversion of the electron localization functions.

On increasing the strain from the critical point (at -2%) towards the positive regime (i.e., towards the upper boundary) we observed that the band gap increases from ~ 14.4 meV (at 0% strain) to 0.113 eV (at 3% strain) with orbital and band dispersion inversions becoming prominent (as evident from Fig. 4.23(b-c) and Fig. 4.22(a(ii-iii))). It is clear from the orbital projected density of states that, the s -orbitals of Au and I cross the Fermi level (at 0% strain, Fig. 4.23(b)) and completely populate the valence band at 3% strain by explicit exchange of the p - d hybrid orbitals and s -orbitals of Au and I across the Fermi level (as evident in Fig. 4.23(c)) leading to a large non-trivial gap at 3% strain. The non-trivial nature is further confirmed by computing the electron localization functions at -2% (critical strain) and 0% strain (as presented in Fig. 4.23(d)). It is evident that, the features of the electron localization functions are exchanged indicating a topological quantum phase transition. The non-trivial nature can be attributed to the strong spin-orbit interactions between the core and valence d -orbital electrons of Au.⁶² It was observed that, the narrow gap at 0% strain gets enhanced by the virtue of strain as evident from the band dispersions presented in Fig.

4.22(a(ii-iii)). This global spin-orbit interaction induced gap is superior as compared to other well known two dimensional topological insulators such as, graphene, selenene, germanene etc.^{12,22–24,27,31} The non-trivial topological quantum phase transitions are accompanied by anomalous structural phase transitions. Usually, the buckling height should increase under compressive strain and decreases under tensile strain however, in AuI monolayer, we observe an inversion in the atomic positions along z-direction (i.e., under compressive strain sub-lattice Au is at top and sub-lattice I is at bottom whereas, under tensile strain this gets inverted; causing an inverted buckling with the monolayer eventually becoming planar). Such anomalous nature leads to orbital alterations giving rise to extra degrees of freedom for electrons and imposes a lorentz force on electrons causing to spin-charge accumulation along the edges.

Topological Properties

Figure 4.24: (a,b) Slab band structure and edge state spectra at 0% strain indicating the bulk states, edge states and, the Dirac point. (c,d) Slab band structure and edge state spectra at 3% strain indicating the bulk states, edge states and, the Dirac point.

To confirm the non-trivial nature, we computed the \mathbb{Z}_2 invariant ν , slab band structures and angle resolved photoemission spectroscopy-like spectra. Using the wilson loop method

around wannier charge centers we found that, AuI monolayer is indeed a non-trivial two dimensional topological insulator with \mathbb{Z}_2 invariant $\nu = 1$ in the range of strain from -1% to 3% . Since the non-trivial spin-orbit interactions induced gap at 0% strain was enhance by strain engineering to a large-gap at 3% strain, we had to verify the persistence of conducting edge states. For this purpose we computed angle resolved photoemission spectroscopy-like spectra at 0% strain and 3% strain (as presented in Fig. 4.24). It is evident from the slab band structures (for nanoribbon configuration of AuI) in Fig. 4.24(a,c) that, AuI monolayer at 0% and 3% strain hosts conducting edge states with Dirac points at the center of the brillouin zone. These states would be robust against deformations and non-magnetic impurities. Similarly, from Fig. 4.24(b,d) it is clear that, the Dirac dispersion along the edges of AuI monolayer would persist at 0% as well as 3% strain.

4.4 Conclusion

We presented our investigations on the dimensional engineering of non-trivial two dimensional topological insulator LiMgAs from trivial bulk parent. As expected, this system presented non-trivial topological quantum phase transitions at low pressure due to quantum confinement effects and large surface-volume ratio. The proposed monolayer of LiMgAs was found to be dynamically stable with absence of negative phonon frequencies in the entire brillouin zone. Also, the non-trivial phase of LiMgAs monolayer exhibits unconventional Fermion velocities along different directions of the brillouin zone. The non-trivial topological phase transition in this system is characterised by s - p orbital inversions across the Fermi level accompanying the inversion in band dispersions. This system is proposed to exhibit room temperature applications owing to large-gap induced by spin-orbit interactions. Also, we compared the band inversion strength which is stronger as compared to the bulk parent, indicating towards the underlying quantum confinement effects. We finally confirmed the non-trivial nature by computing the \mathbb{Z}_2 invariant which was $\nu = 1$ and edge state spectra indicating a conducting Dirac dispersion along the edge brillouin zone path.

To further increase the non-trivial gap solely due to spin-orbit interactions i.e., without applying strain, we explored functionalization technique. We presented, elemental monolayers of Tellurium and Selenium for the first time. According to previous reports in literature, we too observed that, the free-standing elemental monolayers are dynamically unstable. However,

on partially functionalizing these monolayers with oxygen and sulphur (since, they would form bonds due to mutually favourable electronic configurations) we observed that TeO, SeS and SeS were dynamically stable except TeS. These stable monolayers were then explored for their electronic properties and we found that both, TeO and SeS present are large-gap systems under the influence of spin-orbit interactions. On inclusion of spin-orbit interactions we observed s - p orbital inversions across the Fermi indicating towards potential non-trivial character of TeO and SeS. The effect was attributed to orbital filtering effects which saturate the dangle bonds (originating from the p_z -orbitals) in z -direction giving rise to extra degrees of freedom to the electrons. This was confirmed by plotting the π and σ orbital projected band structures. We performed in depth analysis of TeO since it exhibited highest non-trivial gap under spin-orbit interactions of 0.365 eV. We presented the Berry curvature and spin-Berry curvature analysis of TeO in the non-trivial regime under the influence of spin-orbit interactions. From the analysis we observed that, TeO can be used for spintronic and valleytronic applications, due to the opposite Lorentz forces acting on the electrons which leads to the spin-charge accumulation along the edges. This was presented in terms of the spin-projected electronic band structure along the two valleys points in the Brillouin zone. The large-gap induced due to spin-orbit interactions also leads to unconventionally high spin Hall conductivity in the global gap (which was observed to be superior to several other materials). From experimental perspective, we also presented the investigations of quantum well $h\text{BN}/\text{TeO}/h\text{BN}$ which was found to retain the large-gap due to spin-orbit interactions under a tensile strain of 14%. These computations were followed by computing the edge state spectra of TeO and SeS. Clearly, TeO and SeS presented Dirac dispersions along the edge Brillouin zone path. Also, we presented that the spin channels along the edges of SeS traverse in opposite directions by plotting the edge spectra along the [100] and [010] crystal directions. Ultimately, we presented the \mathbb{Z}_2 invariant which was found to be $\nu = 1$ indicating that, the non-trivial characters are indeed topological in nature and that, TeO and SeS are two dimensional topological insulators.

Similar to the dimensional engineering of LiMgAs from bulk parent, we presented the dimensionally engineered AuI monolayer. We saw that, due to quantum confinement effects, the low dimensional phase exhibits a narrow gap as compared to the bulk parent which exhibits semi-metallic character. The ground state of this system was found to exhibit buckled structure governed by the $P3m1$ space group rather than $P6_3mmc$ space group. However, in the $P3m1$ phase, AuI monolayer presented a gap of 14.4 meV, from here we subjected the

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system to compressive and tensile pressures to mark the topological quantum phase transition boundaries. We found that, the lower boundary was at -2% and the upper boundary was at 4% , within this region, AuI presented non-trivial topological insulating phase in two different structural phases of $P3m1$ and $P6_3mmc$ with the non-trivial gap as high as 0.113 eV under spin-orbit interactions. The underlying mechanism was found to be unconventional $s, p-d$ orbital inversion mechanism alongwith the inverted band disperions. Also, we presented the inversion mechanism in terms of the exchange of charge densities or electron localisation functions across the Fermi level. To ascertain that, the non-trivial nature persists at the pressure of 3% (where the spin-orbit interactions induced gap is 0.113 eV) we computed the slab band structures and the edge state spectra both of which clearly host the non-trivial Dirac like edge dispersion in the edge brillouin zone. Finally we present the \mathbb{Z}_2 invariant and find that it is $\nu = 1$ in the region of -2% to 4% strain.

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CHAPTER 5

Energy Applications of Bulk and Low Dimensional Topological Materials

This chapter focuses on multifunctional applications of bulk and low dimensional materials proposed in chapters 3 and 4. We begin with brief discussions on the background of the thermoelectric applications of bulk topological insulators and the implications of non-trivial topologies of binary zincblende AuI on the thermoelectric transport properties. We then discuss in brief the basal plane catalytic activity of low dimensional AuI towards hydrogen evolution reactions in terms of different mechanisms such as, volmer, volmer-tafel and volmer-heyrovsky. We then shift our focus on the edge sites rather than the basal plane of two dimensional topological insulators for catalytic applications. We establish a relation between the non-trivial topologies and catalysis. This is done by discussing topological quantum catalysis in two dimensional topological insulator LiMgAs.

5.1 Thermoelectric Applications of Bulk Topological Insulator: AuI

Zincblende phase of AuI binary compound was explored for non-trivial topological quantum phase transitions from semi-metallic to topological conducting/insulating phase. As expected, AuI binary compound did exhibit non-trivial topological properties which was discussed in

chapter 3. Apart from the non-trivial nature we were also motivated to explore the binary system AuI for thermoelectric applications. This is because, it was previously observed that, several strong topological insulators such as, Bi_2Te_3 , Bi_2Se_3 , Sb_2Te_3 host remarkable thermoelectric transport properties.¹ This implies that, materials hosting topological insulating nature can also exhibit decent thermoelectric properties due to linear band dispersions, dissipationless transport of Fermions, dense states across Fermi etc. Hence, till date, several bulk materials which exhibit non-trivial topological insulating nature also host thermoelectric phenomena.²⁻¹¹

As compared to other energy application materials, the field of thermoelectrics has been struggling due to the feeble power conversion efficiencies of conventional thermoelectric materials. Such drawback has restricted thermoelectric materials to niche applications such as, space probes, picnic refrigerators and domestic water heaters. Hence, the development of novel materials (which exhibit enhanced thermoelectric power conversion efficiencies) would promote the application of thermoelectric materials to harvest waste heat from major sources like thermal

stations/automobiles or replace conventional cooling techniques, eventually reducing the carbon footprints. The thermoelectric power conversion efficiency of a material can be quantified in terms of the figure of merit (defined as zT) which depends on, the seebeck co-efficient (S), electrical conductivity (σ), temperature, electronic thermal conductivity and, lattice thermal conductivity (κ). These parameters in turn depend on the carrier concentrations in a complex manner as evident from Fig. 5.1 which necessitates the optimization of carrier concentrations with respect to these parameters. From this Fig. 5.1 is evident that, alongwith carrier concentration, it is the overall optimization of zT which is important since other parameters exhibit significantly biased behaviour with respect to carrier concentrations. Hence, an ideal thermoelectric material can be realised in a sweet spot where, the zT is optimized which ensures efficient conversion of heat into electricity. Achieving such condition hence a non-trivial

Figure 5.1: A typical schematic indicating the thermoelectric material design strategy with respect to carrier concentrations.

task requiring fine tuning of, the electronic band dispersion curves and the phonon dispersion curves. Hence, over the past few years, it has become a norm to, either tune the electronic transport of heavy materials (by band engineering, nano structuring, chemical doping, etc. which leads to lower thermal conductivity) or to suppress the thermal transport through lighter materials (by alloying, defects, dimensional confinement, etc.).¹²⁻¹⁸

However, the major hurdle which obstructs the thermoelectric efficiency arises due to an entanglement between, seebeck coefficient, electrical conductivity and thermal conductivity. This is due to the fact that these parameters are governed by the inter-dependent electrons and holes in a material. This leads to a compromised overall transport efficiency since, modification in one of the electronic parameters changes the other. Hence, the most effective method would be to minimize the lattice thermal conductivity by modifying the phonon transport properties of a material. Semi-metallic systems were known to host promising thermoelectric properties due to unconventional band topologies and coupled optical-acoustic phonon modes. However, such materials have received scare attention for thermoelectric applications.¹⁹⁻²² Recently, semi-metallic systems such as HgTe, BiTe etc. were investigated for thermoelectric applications.^{11, 23-27} This motivates us to perform in-depth computations of the thermoelectric and transport properties of zincblende AuI apart from non-trivial topological quantum phase transitions.

Structure and Lattice Dynamics

As discussed in previous chapter 3, the zincblende phase of AuI is energetically, mechanically and dynamically stable. Apart from dynamic stability, observing phonon dispersion curves in the entire brillouin zone gives insights into, electron-phonon coupling (in metals), LO-TO splitting (in polar materials), flexural phonon modes (in two dimensional materials) etc. In case of zincblende AuI which is governed by the cubic symmetry we observe a narrow gap between acoustic and optic phonon branches. Such narrow gaps are known to reduce the thermal conductivity owing to the strong coupling between acoustic and optical branches.²⁸ Also, the highest observed phonon frequency was $\sim 110 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ along the brillouin zone path of $\Gamma \rightarrow X$ which was lower than some of the famous thermoelectric materials such as, Bi_2Te_3 , PbTe, SnSe and semi-metals such as, BiTe and HgTe.^{24, 29-32} Contrary to these materials (wherein the highest optic mode is located at the centre of the brillouin zone) we observe a significant softening of the optical phonon modes and hardening of the acoustic phonon

5.1. Thermoelectric Applications of Bulk Topological Insulator: AuI

Figure 5.2: (a) Face centred cubic zincblende structure of AuI. (b) Phonon dispersion curves alongside phonon density of states. (c) Phonon group velocities versus frequency (rad ps^{-1}) and, (d) Specific heat (C_v) of AuI versus temperature.

Figure 5.3: (a) Mode Grüneisen parameter as a function of phonon frequency. (b) Total Grüneisen parameters as a function of temperature. (c) Phonon scattering rates. (d) Lattice thermal conductivity and cumulative thermal conductivity as a function of, (e) Phonon frequency and (f) Phonon mean free path.

modes at the centre of the Brillouin zone. Such phonon dispersions are also observed in other compounds such as Perovskites and magnesium boride (MgB_2).^{33,34} Apart from this, the longitudinal acoustic mode has a frequency of $\sim 52 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which is significantly lower than

the materials exhibiting low thermal conductivity. Phonon dispersion curves are of great significance when we intend to analyse the phonon group velocities (presented in Fig. 5.2(c)) which govern the transport properties. Generally, 90% of lattice thermal transport originates from the acoustic branches; however, recent reports suggest that, mild contributions may originate from the optical branches as well.^{35–39} Using phonon group velocities, we can project phonon number density on the phonon frequencies to understand the contributions arising from the acoustic and optical branches. Figure. 5.2(c) indicates that, apart from the acoustic branches, optical branches also contribute significantly. Also, the ultra-low optical phonon frequencies at the brillouin zone center reaffirm strong optic-acoustic coupling. Finally, in order to validate that AuI obeys the Dulong-Petit law, we compute temperature dependent specific heat (presented in Fig. 5.2(d)).

Thermoelectric Transport Properties: Lattice Contribution

Figure 5.4: Electronic contribution to thermoelectric properties as a function of chemical potential (μ) for three different carrier concentrations.

We compute the electronic and lattice contributions to thermoelectric transport properties using the semi-classical Boltzmann transport equations for electrons and phonons. Firstly, we explore the role of lattice vibrations in terms of phonons on thermoelectric transport

properties. In Fig. 5.3(a) we present the mode Grüneisen parameters (γ) as a function of phonon frequencies. With this parameter, we get insights into the anharmonic effects originating from phonon-phonon interactions. This is done by computing the variations in the frequency of a phonon mode for a particular unit cell volume. From Fig. 5.3 it is clear that, Grüneisen parameters are widely spread indicating towards large anharmonic effects due to strong phonon-phonon scattering. Also, we observe suppression in phonon lifetimes and thermal conductivity which is due to enhanced anharmonicity. This is also clear from the Slack model which states that, the lattice thermal conductivity has inverse relation with the Grüneisen parameter.⁴⁰ This explains the large magnitudes of Grüneisen parameters and corresponding reduction in lattice thermal conductivity. In Fig. 5.3(b) we present the average magnitudes of Grüneisen parameters as a function of temperature. It is evident that, the magnitude of Grüneisen parameter saturates becoming almost constant (~ 1.55) at higher temperatures. This indicates that the crystal structure hosts strong bonding character. However, the computed magnitude of Grüneisen parameter is lower than other thermoelectric materials which implies lower anharmonicity as compared to, PbS (2.46), PbSe (2.66) and SnSe (2.83).³¹ The strong crystal bonding is also evident from the analysis of electro-negativity and charge distributions which indicate towards the polar-covalent bonding in the crystal. Also, the moderate magnitudes of youngs and shear modulus indicate towards softening of bond strength which gives rise to reduced phonon transport.⁴¹

In Fig. 5.3(c) we present the phonon scattering rates for AuI which is explicitly used to interpret phonon lifetimes. These scattering rates are computed as a function of phonon frequencies in two scenarios wherein we, include and exclude the isotopic contributions arising from the mass anharmonicity. It was observed that, the overall phonon scattering rates follow the trend observed in the anharmonic scattering rates with slightly higher magnitude. This implies that, zincblende AuI exhibits mass anisotropy with isotropic effects contributing to the prediction of thermal transport properties. It is also evident from the literature that, the mass anisotropy is detrimental in predicting lattice thermal conductivity.⁴² Hence, to understand the effect of temperature we compute the scattering rates at higher temperatures. We found that, at higher temperatures, anharmonic effects dominate over the mass anisotropy. The temperature dependent thermal conductivity, cumulative magnitude of thermal conductivity as a function of phonon frequency and phonon mean free path are presented in Fig. 5.3(d), (e) and (f) respectively. It is evident that, the phonon mean free path decreases rapidly from 101

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nm to 60 nm in the temperature range of 300-500 K. The magnitude of thermal conductivity at 300 K is 0.46 W/mK which is isotropic owing to the cubic symmetry of AuI. This value at room temperature is significantly lower than other materials such as, PbTe (2.2 W/mK), BiCuSeO (0.89 W/mK), HgTe (2.14 W/mK) and SnSe (0.6 W/mK).^{30–32,43}

One of the important factors in quantifying thermal transport properties is phonon lifetime which can be understood in terms of phonon scattering rates which in turn give rise to lower thermal conductivity. It is evident from the cumulative magnitudes of thermal conductivity (in terms of phonon frequency and mean free path) that, at a particular temperature, the thermal transportation by phonons leads to thermal conductivity. It is evident from Fig. 5.3(f) that, the characteristic mean free path at room temperature is 101 nm which reduces drastically to 76 nm and 60 nm at temperature of 400 K and 500 K respectively. This implies that, the average distance traversed by phonons (between two successive scattering events) decreases as the temperature increases. Hence, the overall thermal conductivity is suppressed.

Thermoelectric Transport Properties: Electronic Contribution

Figure 5.5: Computed electronic contributions to thermoelectric parameters as a function of chemical potential (μ) at three different temperatures.

Before we proceed with discussions regarding temperature dependent variations of electronic thermoelectric parameters, we address their variations as a function of the chemical potential for different carrier concentrations (as presented in Fig. 5.4). All the thermoelectric parameters exhibit converged behaviour at three different carrier concentrations (as evident

from Fig. 5.4). We observe that, the power factor is optimal at $1 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ carrier concentration. Hence, we proceed with computation of temperature dependent electronic thermoelectric parameters at this concentration. It is evident from Fig. 5.5 that, the electronic thermoelectric parameters for a fixed carrier concentration exhibit enhanced behaviour. This system exhibits promising power conversion efficiencies near room temperature due to the rise in power factor and the figure of merit (zT_e independent of the lattice thermal conductivity) which is evident from Fig. 5.5(d,e) in the temperature range of 300-500 K.

We compute temperature dependent relaxation time to compensate for the relaxation time dependent quantities (electrical and electronic conductivities) obtained using the semi-classical Boltzmann transport approach which would result in accurate magnitudes of electrical and electronic conductivities. Although, AuI exhibits unique electronic band topologies but the constituent charge carriers exhibit significantly distinct magnitudes of carrier mobilities. Here, enhanced electron mobility originates due to the inverse relationship between carrier effective mass and mobility. We observed that, the magnitude of electron mobility at room temperature was $58,930 \text{ cm}^2/\text{Vs}$ which is higher than the hole mobility $4,741 \text{ cm}^2/\text{Vs}$. Hence, we expect a reduced relaxation time for holes as compared to electrons. Here, the carrier relaxation time at room temperature were observed to be 1.8 ps and 0.67 ps for electrons and holes respectively.

Thermoelectric Transport Properties: Figure of Merit

We present the temperature dependent carrier mobilities, relaxation time, electrical and electronic conductivities independent of relaxation time in Fig. 5.6. In regime independent of relaxation time, the magnitude of power factor are affected drastically (as presented in Fig. 5.6(d) and (i)). The hole power factor was observed to be as low as $0.08 \text{ (V}^2/\text{K}^2\Omega\text{m)}$ (which even lower than the electron power factor of $0.22 \text{ (V}^2/\text{K}^2\Omega\text{m)}$) due to low hole mobility and relaxation time. The Seebeck co-efficient for hole and electron were observed to be comparable with magnitudes ranging as $150\text{-}200 \text{ } \mu\text{V/K}$ at $300\text{-}600 \text{ K}$ temperature (as evident from Fig. 5.6(a) and (f)). Also, we observed a significant difference in the room temperature electronic and electrical conductivities (as evident from Fig. 5.6 (b)-(c) and (g)-(h)). With such mutually compensating characteristics (i.e., similar thermal conductivities and Seebeck coefficient with negligible difference as evident from Fig. 5.6(a) and (f)), the overall figure of merit (zT) turns out have similar character in case of holes and electrons. The nature of overall zT exhibits an inverted parabolic trend (as evident from Fig. 5.6(e) and (j)), with a

5. Energy Applications of Bulk and Low Dimensional Topological Materials

Figure 5.6: Variation of thermoelectric parameters and total Figure of Merit for three different carrier concentrations.

maximum magnitude of 0.58 and 0.57 observed at 400 K for electrons and holes respectively. Such room temperature figure of merit is quite remarkable as compared to several materials which exhibit high figure of merit at higher temperatures. This figure of merit can be further enhanced to realise efficient thermoelectric power conversion by optimizing the power factor. This can be achieved through chemical doping or dimensional engineering which modulates the electronic band structure.

Hence, topological insulators can be realised to be efficient thermoelectric materials. However, it would be interesting to explore topological insulators for other energy applications such as electro-catalysis. With this motivation we explored two dimensional AuI which was dimensionally engineered from the bulk parent and observed to exhibit non-trivial topology in chapter 4. Eventually, we observed that, the basal activity of two dimensional topological insulators (such as AuI) is decent but not excellent. This lead us to explore the most recently developed field of topological quantum catalysis in low dimensional systems. This phenomena was explored in two dimensional LiMgAs which exhibits non-trivial topological properties.

5.2 Catalytic Activity of Two Dimensional Topological Insulator: AuI

Two dimensional phase of AuI was explored in chapter 4 for non-trivial topological insulating nature. Further to these investigations, we also explored AuI monolayers for catalytic activity. This was out of curiosity (i.e., how would AuI monolayer respond towards hydrogen evolution reaction?) since, Au is one of the precious transition metals known for catalytic applications. With this we hope to propose a two dimensional material which can be used as a catalyst to facilitate energy conversions sufficing the rising energy demands. The motivation lies in several low dimensional materials which were previously explored for catalytic applications and discussed in following paragraphs.

Metal halides have recently received attention for potential applications such as, photocatalysts, ultraviolet optical devices and quantum cutting solar materials.⁴⁴ For example, Huang et.al., recently investigated binary compounds comprising of group-11 transition-metals and halides.⁴⁴ It was proposed by Huang et.al., that such binary compounds can be mechanically exfoliated from their bulk counterparts. Also, alloy monolayers of Cu, Ag, Au and Pt were explored for nano- and opto-electronic applications.⁴⁵ This was possible

due to various Au based nanostructures (such as, nano-particles, nano-wires, nano-ribbons, nano-plates, nano-sheets and nano-tubes) which can be synthesized experimentally.^{46–51}

From perspective of a catalytic material, to efficiently achieve hydrogen evolution reaction Au based materials have turned out to be potential alternatives as compared to rare metals such as platinum (Pt), palladium (Pd) etc.^{52–54} The standard catalytic materials of choice explored thus far are typically made up of, Pt, Pd and their alloys. These materials host spontaneous hydrogen evolution reactions with Gibbs free energy close to zero.^{55,56} This criteria has inspired exploration of numerous two dimensional transition metal based catalysts for hydrogen evolution reaction.^{57–61} Apart from the transition metal based compounds, the material search has proliferated into single atom catalysis which employs single atoms of precious metals such as Pt, Pd, Au etc. Tran et.al., have shown that, the reaction Gibbs free energy can be further reduced by designing catalysts made up of MoS₂ and Mo₃S₁₃ with Au substrate.^{62–65} Similarly, Au nano-particles were also explored as catalyst for hydrogen evolution reaction. It was observed that, nano-particles provide best alternative for Pt free catalysis owing to their large surface area as compared to the volume occupying the space. Apart from this, Au based catalysts exhibit good activity for water-gas shift reactions at low temperatures as compared to Pt catalyst.⁵² Also, NiAu/Au core shell's and materials with Au at corner sites; were found to exhibit promising catalytic activity as compared to Pt based catalyst with the latter being more active for hydrogen evolution reaction as compared to CO₂ reduction.^{66,67}

Catalysis Mechanism

We explored the catalytic activity of AuI monolayer at 0% strain since this structure was found to be thermodynamic stability with a narrow electronic band gap. We might expect that, under pristine conditions, AuI monolayer (which exhibits non-trivial topological properties) would facilitate catalytic activity along the edges due to the non-trivial edge charge accumulation.⁶⁸ But, since the non-trivial gap (~ 14.4 meV) was found to be smaller than thermal energy at room temperature (~ 25 meV) the resulting charge accumulation along the edges won't be high enough to facilitate catalytic activity as compared to the basal plane. Hence, we investigated the catalytic activity along the basal plane of pristine AuI monolayer.

A typical hydrogen evolution reaction is a multi-step process as presented in Fig. 5.7(a). Typically, the hydrogen evolution reaction begins with the interaction and adsorption of a

Figure 5.7: (a) Steps involved in the catalysis mechanism of AuI monolayer in hydrogen evolution reaction. Charge density plot of (b) Volmer and (c) Volmer-Heyrovsky reactions.

primary hydrogen over the catalyst surface (as presented in Fig.5.7(a)). This is known as the Volmer reaction (as evident from step 1. in Fig. 5.7(a)). Every catalyst should obey Sabatier's principle which states that, the intermediate state in a chemical reaction is characterised by optimal binding of the adsorbate and the adsorbant. Hence, in a hydrogen evolution reactions the primary hydrogen should form optimal bond with the catalyst surface (neither too weak nor too strong) facilitating the Volmer reaction. This would ensure the formation of a hydrogen molecule due to the interaction of primary hydrogen with the secondary hydrogen.

Such reaction mechanism is quantified in terms of, optimal adsorption energy ($\Delta E_H = 0.24$ eV) and Gibbs free energy ($\Delta G_H = 0.00$ eV) during the Volmer reaction under $pH = 0$ and for a reduction potential of $U = 0$. These parameters have attained the reputation of reliable descriptors for hydrogen evolution reaction. These parameters i.e., the adsorption energy and the Gibbs free energy are computed as, $\Delta G_H = \Delta E_H + \Delta_{ZPE} - T\Delta S$ and $\Delta E_H = (E_{AuI+H} - E_{AuI} - \frac{1}{2}E_{H_2})$ respectively. Here, ΔE_H presents the hydrogen adsorption energy, Δ_{ZPE} presents the zero-point energy between the adsorbed and gaseous phases of

hydrogen atom and ΔS is the change in entropy between the adsorbed and gaseous phases of hydrogen atom. Generally, the term $\Delta_{ZPE} - T\Delta S$ is approximated to be 0.24 eV. In case of an ideal catalyst for hydrogen evolution reaction, ΔG_H should be zero. Hence, we typically expect optimal adsorption energy value of $\Delta E_H = -0.24$ eV during the Volmer reactions. The terms E_{AuI+H} and E_{AuI} are the total energies of hydrogen adsorption on, top sites (i.e., on top of Au/I, bridge and hollow) and total energy of pristine AuI respectively. E_{H_2} is the total energy of H_2 molecule in vacuum. We employ these equations to compute the adsorption energies along the four sites (i.e., top of Au/I, bridge and hollow) of a $3 \times 3 \times 1$ AuI monolayer.

From our computations we found that, top of Au was the most favourable site for primary reaction with adsorption energy (-0.64 eV) and the Gibbs free energy (-0.40 eV) close to optimum values. Similarly, the Gibbs free energy at I, bridge and hollow sites are 0.90 eV, -1.25 eV and -0.49 eV respectively. From the analysis of the Lowdin charge we found that, a charge transfer of $\sim 0.26e$ occurs from Au site to the primary hydrogen (as evident from step 2. in Fig. 5.7(a) and (b)). The charge redistribution is such that, the charge over Au gets depleted while charge over I gets accumulated.

Following the primary reaction, the hydrogen evolution can occur through two different mechanisms such as, Volmer-Tafel and Volmer-Heyrovsky. In a Volmer-Tafel reaction the primary hydrogen reacts with a secondary hydrogen adsorbed on a neighbouring site leading to the evolution reaction. But in case of AuI, on adsorption of a secondary hydrogen over I site (which is the nearest neighbour to Au site where the primary hydrogen is adsorbed) we observe a high charge transfer as compared to that at Au site i.e., $\sim 0.43e$. The corresponding Gibbs free energy also indicates towards a strong interaction of the secondary hydrogen at I site. Hence, AuI monolayer won't facilitate Volmer-Tafel reaction owing to the strong interactions at I site. Even the Volmer-Tafel reaction at a neighbouring Au atom won't be possible since, the distance between the two such Au atoms would be quite large (~ 4.7 Å). However, in practical conditions, the primary hydrogen might interact with a secondary hydrogen originating from the surroundings (as evident from step 3-5 presented in Fig. 5.7(a)). Such reaction mechanism is known as Volmer-Heyrovsky reaction.

The adsorption energy of a secondary hydrogen during a Volmer-Heyrovsky reaction is given as, $\Delta E_{H^*} = \frac{1}{n}(E_{AuI+nH^*} - E_{AuI} - \frac{n}{2}E_{H_2})$ and the corresponding Gibbs free energy is given as, $\Delta G_{H^*}(n) = \Delta E_{H^*}(n) + \Delta_{ZPE} - T\Delta S$. We proceed with the adsorption energy and Gibbs free energy formalisms proposed by Lee et.al., for Volmer-Tafel reactions. We found

that, the Gibbs free energy for Volmer-Tafel reaction was -0.62 eV which was higher than that for Volmer-Heyrovsky -0.23 eV. This indicates that, the most favourable mechanism for hydrogen evolution reaction is Volmer-Heyrovsky (at Au site as presented in Fig. 5.7(a)) rather than Volmer-Tafel. Hence, AuI monolayer would facilitate the evolution of hydrogen molecule through Volmer-Heyrovsky mechanism (as evident from Fig. 5.7(a-c)).^{69,70}

Therefore, we can ask a question; in low dimensional topological materials such as, two dimensional topological insulators can we expect superior catalytic activity as compared to the one observed in the basal planes of AuI? Will the large non-trivial spin-orbit interactions induced gap would facilitate such behaviour? For this purpose, we explore a completely new phenomena which is currently at the frontiers of materials science research and known as topological quantum catalysis. For this purpose, we choose two dimensional topological insulator LiMgAs (explored in chapter 4) which exhibits large non-trivial gap, leading to large edge charge accumulations.

5.3 Topological Quantum Catalysis in LiMgAs

Why exactly do we need a topological quantum catalyst? The need arises due to the rise in global energy demands which has attained great importance over the past few decades.⁷¹⁻⁷³ To address the rise in global demand, the primary focus was on generation of energy using Hydrogen-rich resources. This technique was observed to be effective which lead to the use of Platinum group metals such as, Pt, Ru, Rh, Ir and Pd as a catalysts in hydrogen evolution reactions.⁷⁴ But, just as any promising material, these rare metals came with a disadvantage of; associated cost, rarity and short lifetime of electrodes. This has motivated extensive research in materials science to find a cost-effective and abundant alternative. Thus far, combination of metals (such as, Pt, Pd, Ir, Ru, Au, Ni), binary metal alloys, 3d transition metal hydroxides, phosphides, carbides and transition metal chalcogenides, nitrides, borides, oxides and sulphides were proposed as promising; cost-effective alternatives.^{74,75} But, the efficiency and performance of such materials depended on the pH of surrounding media leading; different results in acidic and alkaline media.⁷⁵

In a catalytic reaction, the major factor governing the activity, efficiency and performance originates from the surface states. These surface states in turn originate from; [111] surfaces of noble metals and the surface dangling bonds of a semi-conductor which significantly affect

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the physio-chemical processes occurring at the interfaces and surfaces.⁷⁶ These surface states arise due to the spatial proximity and orbital features across the Fermi level. Although these surface states are promising but, they are typically quite sensitive and not robust against, impurities in crystal lattice, defects and surface degradation (due to redox reactions) which are known to alter the atomic terminations and crystal orientations.⁷⁶ Also, as suggested by Gerischer and Parson, another major challenge faced by materials is that, they have to obey Sabatier's principle which talks about thermoneutral condition (yielding maximum exchange current densities).⁷⁷⁻⁸⁰ Hence, realising materials which simultaneously would host robust surface states to facilitate physio-chemical reactions and obey Sabatier's principle is quite a challenging task.

With the discovery and experimental realisation of topological quantum materials (such as, topological insulators and topological semi-metals (Dirac, Weyl, Nodal-line)) we can now address the problems with existing catalysts mentioned in previous paragraph.⁸¹ The characteristic features which makes these materials stand out from existing catalysts is that, the conducting surface/edge states and Fermi arcs are robust to crystal impurities (magnetic/non-magnetic) and surface oxidations/degradations. This implies that, the catalyst material would have longer life-times facilitating hydrogen evolution reaction due to the sea of electrons which exhibit high mobilities.⁸¹ This approach to solve the problem in catalysis was initially proposed in 2011 wherein, gold-covered surface of Bi_2Se_3 topological insulators were investigated for CO and O_2 adsorptions. It was observed in this initial work that the surface states persisted as long as the bulk gap was retained under time-reversal symmetry.⁷⁶ The results were quite promising with the potential of being implemented as alternatives to conventional *d*-band heterogeneous catalysis. However, ever since then, the phenomena of topological quantum catalysis received scarce attention until recently; when a new perspective was proposed for heterogenous catalysis using materials such as, topological semi-metals, chiral crystals, Full/Half-Heusler alloys and Perovskite manganites.⁸²

However, the lower carrier densities across the Fermi level originating from the weak electrostatic screening strength is a major drawback of the topological semi-metals (such as, Dirac and Weyl semi-metals) making them less reliable.⁸³ We therefore revisit and investigate the potential role of conducting edge states of a two dimensional topological insulator in heterogenous catalysis. This is because, topological insulators exhibit, high carrier mobilities, high carrier densities across Fermi level and robust charge accumulations along the

edges. We investigate the catalytic response of the edge states of two dimensional topological insulator LiMgAs along [100] and [010] crystal directions. We explicitly established the fact that, the catalytic response and performance gets significantly enhanced due to the edge states originating from the spin-orbit interactions. With this, we hope that, we can bypass conventional d -band theory and single atom catalysis with topological quantum catalysis for varied applications.

Structure and Lattice Dynamics

Figure 5.8: (a,b) Unit cell of LiMgAs at 0% strain and 10% biaxial compressive strain (corresponding monolayer thickness (h) is 1.60 \AA and 1.95 \AA respectively). (c) The hexagonal and orthorhombic Brillouin zone obtained using matrix (R) (d). (e-h) ab-initio molecular dynamics simulations under 0% strain and 10% compressive strain for 3 picoseconds at 300 K.

We build upon the two dimensional topological insulator LiMgAs which has been discussed in chapter 4. At 0% strain, LiMgAs monolayer (governed by $\overline{P3m1}$ space group) exhibits structure similar to 1T-MoS₂ with, the hexagonal lattice of As atoms occupies octahedral coordinations between two layers of hexagonal-closed-packed structures made up of Li and Mg (as presented in Fig. 5.8(a)) with the octahedral belonging to D_{3d} tetragonal symmetry.⁸⁴ This structure is retained even at 10% biaxial compressive stress (i.e., after topological quantum phase transition) as evident from Fig. 5.8(b). The dynamic stability of LiMgAs was established in chapter 4, hence we investigated the stability and viability of LiMgAs at room temperature (300 K) by performing ab-initio molecular dynamics simulations. From Fig. 5.8(e-h) we observe that, the structure of LiMgAs at 0% and 10% biaxial compressive stress are stable due to small variations in the energy and thermostat temperature. However, under 10% biaxial

compressive stress we observe that, the system initially exhibits large fluctuations in energy (Fig. 5.8(g)) but eventually thermalise after 1.5 picoseconds (highlighted blue line in Fig. 5.8(g)) attaining structural stability.

With the stability established, we used a rotation matrix (\mathcal{R}) to transform the hexagonal unit cell into an orthorhombic unit cell at 10% biaxial compressive stress (presented in Fig. 5.8(b,d)). This phase was used to obtain, zig-zag and planar like nanoribbon configurations by exploiting periodicity along [100] and [010] crystal directions respectively. We investigated the energetic stability of these nanoribbon configurations (presented in Fig. 5.9(c,d)) in terms of the formation energy E_f ($= E_{LiMgAs} - E_{Li} - E_{Mg} - E_{As}$, where E_{LiMgAs} is the energy of LiMgAs and E_X ; $X = Li, Mg, As$; are the total energies of constituent elements) and found them to be -2.03 eV/atom and -2.90 eV/atom for zig-zag and planar like configurations respectively. This indicates that the nano-ribbon configurations are energetically lower as compared to their two dimensional monolayer which has formation energy -1.70 eV/atom. Hence, LiMgAs nanoribbons are energetically stable and viable experimentally.

A Revisit to Topological Properties

Figure 5.9: (a) Electronic band structure with spin-orbit interactions at 0% and 10% biaxial compressive strain alongside the charge densities of bands I, II and III. (b) Edge slab band structure. (c,d) Zig-zag and planar terminations of nanoribbons with lattice parameters.

Since, two dimensional LiMgAs is a non-trivial topological insulator which is realised

through topological quantum phase transitions, it exhibits edge charge accumulations which are robust against external perturbations. Apart from the *s-p* orbital inversion mechanism discussed in chapter 4, in Fig. 5.9(a) we present the electronic band structures of LiMgAs at 0% and 10% biaxial compressive stress under the influence of spin-orbit interactions. It is evident from Fig. 5.9(a) that, the charge densities get exchanged across the Fermi level (i.e., the charge densities of bands I, II and III at 0% and 10% biaxial compressive stress get exchanged); confirming the non-trivial nature of topological quantum phase transition. Upon quantum phase transition, in the non-trivial regime (at 10% stress) the system was observed to exhibit a large-gap of 0.16 eV which is superior to several materials.⁸⁵ This indicates that, the edge charge accumulations would persist at room temperature since the gap is quite high as compared to the thermal energy at room temperature. In chapter 4 we observed that, the non-trivial phase of LiMgAs hosts high velocity Fermions along the conducting edge states.

Hence, we can expect unconventional catalytic response of the edge sites of LiMgAs towards hydrogen evolution reaction. The conducting edge sites are evident from Fig. 5.9(b) which shows the slab band structure computed using the exact tight-binding Hamiltonian model. With this we confirmed that, the edge sites are semi-metallic while the bulk bands host a spin-orbit interactions induced gap at 10% biaxial compressive stress. These semi-metallic conducting edge sites can be visualised in terms of the edge charge accumulations. The charge density plots presented in Fig. 5.9(c,d) indicate towards Fermionic accumulations along the edge sites owing to the non-trivial topology. Therefore, we can exploit these non-trivial charge accumulations to host topological quantum catalysis along the edges as compared to basal sites.

Basal Catalytic Activity

We began our investigations with the basal sites and eventually established that, the edge sites are superior as compared to the basal sites. We began our computations with $3 \times 3 \times 1$ supercell of the two dimensional topological insulator LiMgAs which exposes the basal sites for hydrogen evolution reaction. The primary Volmer reaction was carried out at different sites such as, top (of Li, Mg, As) and bridge sites (such as, Li-Mg, Mg-As, Li-As). The primary reaction should obey Sabatier's principle which implies that, the interaction of primary hydrogen should be optimal. This is quantified in terms of, adsorption energy ($\Delta E_H^{ads} = E_{LiMgAs+H} - E_{LiMgAs} - \frac{1}{2}E_{H_2}$) where, $E_{LiMgAs+H}$ is the total energy of H adsorbed

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LiMgAs, E_{LiMgAs} is the total energy of LiMgAs and E_{H_2} is the total energy of H_2 molecule) and Gibbs free energy ($\Delta G_H = \Delta E_H^{ads} + \Delta_{ZPE} - T\Delta S$ where, Δ_{ZPE} is the change in the zero-point energy of adsorbed and gaseous state of H and ΔS is the corresponding change in the entropy and T is room temperature) which should be -0.24 eV and 0.00 eV respectively, under neutral pH and reduction potential of $U = 0$.⁸⁶

Spin-orbit interaction	Site	E_H^{ads} (eV)	ΔG_H (eV)
OFF	Li	-3.430	-3.190
	Mg	-2.522	-2.282
	As	-2.380	-2.140
	Li-As	-3.838	-3.598
	Mg-As	-3.632	-3.392
	Li-Mg	-3.871	-3.631
ON	Li	-3.859	-3.619
	Mg	-2.601	-2.361
	As	-2.462	-2.222
	Li-As	-3.909	-3.669
	Mg-As	-4.084	-3.844
	Li-Mg	-4.325	-4.085

Table 5.1: Adsorption and Gibbs free energy at different basal sites of LiMgAs with and without spin-orbit interactions (SOI).

It was observed that, As top site was the most active sites during the primary reaction (amongst rest of the basal sites) with adsorption and Gibbs free energy without spin-orbit interactions (with spin-orbit interactions) as -2.38 eV (-2.46 eV) and -2.14 eV (-2.22 eV) respectively (the values for other sites are presented in Tab. 5.1). Due to the strong interactions on almost all the basal sites, we conclude that, the basal sites won't be ideal for catalytic application such as for hydrogen evolution reaction.

Topological Catalysis

As compared to the interactions on basal sites, the edge sites exhibit excellent activity during the primary reaction due to robust charge accumulations (presented in Fig. 5.9(c,d)). Different reaction mechanisms were investigated (in both zig-zag and planar termination configurations of nanoribbons 5.10(a,b)) to get insights into the hydrogen evolution reaction assisted by the robust edge states of the two dimensional topological insulator LiMgAs. The sites investigated for hydrogen evolution reaction were, top (Li, Mg, As) and bridge sites (Li-As, Mg-As). During the primary reaction, most active sites of zig-zag and planar configurations without

Figure 5.10: Hydrogen evolution reaction mechanism involving primary and secondary reactions at the edge sites of, (a) zig-zag and (b) planar nanoribbon configurations.

spin-orbit interactions (with spin-orbit interactions) were, As (As and Li-As) and As (As, Li) respectively. We observed close to ideal adsorption and Gibbs free energy (in zig-zag configuration with spin-orbit interaction) of, -0.264 eV and -0.024 eV at As top site and, -0.26 eV and -0.02 eV at Li-As bridge site respectively (values for other sites are tabulated in Tab. 5.2). We found that, similar to the zig-zag configurations, planar configurations also exhibit close to ideal adsorption and Gibbs free energy (under spin-orbit interactions) of, -0.213 eV and 0.026 eV at Li top site and, -0.212 eV and 0.027 eV at As top site respectively (values for other sites are tabulated in Tab. 5.3). We further confirmed and associated the origin of such excellent catalytic activity to the topological edge states by computing the primary reaction at the mid sites of nanoribbon, especially on top of those sites where the Gibbs free energy was minimum under spin-orbit interactions (along the edges). We found that, in both nanoribbon configurations, zig-zag and planar, the interactions at the mid site were of repelling nature with adsorption energy and Gibbs free energy of, 0.118 eV and 0.679 eV and, 0.358 eV and 0.919 eV respectively. Hence, we firmly establish the fact that, the

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superior catalytic behaviour indeed originates from the topologically robust edge sites.

Spin-orbit interaction	Site	E_H^{ads} (eV)	ΔG_H (eV)
OFF	Li	-1.016	-0.776
	Mg	-0.301	-0.060
	As	-0.202	0.037
	Li-As	-0.948	-0.708
	Mg-As	-0.959	-0.719
ON	Li	-0.021	0.218
	Mg	-0.057	0.182
	As	-0.264	-0.024
	Li-As	-0.260	-0.020
	Mg-As	-0.278	-0.038
	Mid-As	0.118	0.358

Table 5.2: Adsorption and Gibbs free energy at different sites of zig-zag nanoribbon configuration.

Spin-orbit interaction	Site	E_H^{ads} (eV)	ΔG_H (eV)
OFF	Li	-0.281	-0.041
	Mg	0.078	0.318
	As	-0.282	-0.042
	Li-As	0.045	0.285
	Mg-As	-0.269	-0.029
ON	Li	-0.213	0.026
	Mg	0.189	0.429
	As	-0.212	0.027
	Li-As	0.111	0.351
	Mg-As	-0.202	0.037
	Mid-Li	0.679	0.919

Table 5.3: Adsorption and Gibbs free energy at different sites of planar nanoribbon configuration.

With excellent catalytic activity during the primary reaction, we computed secondary reaction mechanisms i.e., Volmer-Heyrovsky (the H adsorbed in primary reaction interacts with a H^+ ion and evolves into H_2) and Volmer-Tafel (the H adsorbed in primary reaction interacts with a neighbouring H and evolves into H_2) along the optimal sites observed in the zig-zag and planar nanoribbon configurations (as presented in Fig. 5.10a(i,ii) and b(i,ii) respectively). The modified versions of adsorption and Gibbs free energy for Volmer-Heyrovsky intermediate reaction is given as, $\Delta E_{H^*}^{ads}(n) (= (\frac{1}{n} E_{LiMgAs+nH^*} - E_{LiMgAs} - \frac{n}{2} E_{H_2}))$ and $\Delta G_{H^*}(n) (= \Delta E_{H^*}^{ads}(n) + \Delta_{ZPE} - T\Delta S)$ respectively where $n = 2$ and terms having their

usual meaning.⁸⁶ Similar to the computations in case of AuI, for Volmer-Tafel intermediate reactions, we followed the modified formalism proposed by Lee et.al.

We found that, the zig-zag nanoribbon configuration facilitates both the secondary reactions Volmer-Heyrovsky and, Volmer-Tafel (as evident from Fig. 5.10a(i,ii)) with adsorption and Gibbs free energy of, -0.201 eV and 0.03 eV and, -0.296 eV and -0.05 eV respectively. Looking at the Gibbs free energy, it is clear that, the Volmer-Heyrovsky and Volmer-Tafel reaction mechanisms are exothermic and endothermic in nature respectively. Contrary to the zig-zag nanoribbon configurations, the planar nanoribbon configuration only facilitates Volmer-Heyrovsky reaction along the optimal sites As and Li (as evident from Fig. 5.10b(i,ii)) with adsorption and Gibbs free energy of, -0.53 eV and -0.29 eV respectively. This clearly established that, the zig-zag nanoribbon configuration is highly sensitive towards hydrogen evolution reaction as compared to the planar nanoribbon configuration. However, the overall conclusion is that, the non-trivial conducting edge sites of two dimensional topological insulator LiMgAs favour hydrogen evolution reaction rather than insulating basal sites.

Figure 5.11: Volcano plot using, exchange current densities (for rate constant $k_0 = 1$ s⁻¹ site⁻¹, according to Nørskov's assumptions) and Gibbs free energy data from literature for various materials. It is evident that, LiMgAs outperforms other topological materials placing it in Sabatiers optimum (highlighted in yellow).

We recomputed the exchange current densities (using, $i_0 = -ek_0 \frac{1}{1+\exp(-\frac{\Delta G_{H^*}}{k_B T})}$ for $\Delta G_{H^*} < 0$ and $i_0 = -ek_0 \frac{1}{1+\exp(\frac{\Delta G_{H^*}}{k_B T})}$ for $\Delta G_{H^*} > 0$) for various materials (using the Gibbs free energy from literature) under Nørskov's approximations with rate constant $k_0 = 1$ s⁻¹ site⁻¹ (presented in Tab. 5.4).^{55,87-98} As compared to these materials, due to the non-trivial quantum phenomena, two dimensional topological insulator LiMgAs is placed at the top of volcano plot in a Sabatier's optimum owing to superior catalytic activity towards hydrogen evolution reaction

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Material	ΔG_H (eV)	$\text{Log}_{10}(i_0)$ (Acm^{-2})	Material	ΔG_H (eV)	$\text{Log}_{10}(i_0)$ (Acm^{-2})
Pt	-0.090	-1.522	Rh	-0.080	-1.360
Pd/SnTe	-0.140	-2.349	Ni	-0.250	-4.192
<i>h</i> -B ₂ O	-0.070	-1.201	W	-0.510	-8.551
NiSi	0.070	-1.201	Co	-0.260	-4.359
MoS ₂	0.080	-1.360	Cu	0.200	-3.353
TiSi	-0.0375	-0.720	Mo	-0.450	-7.545
BiPd	0.095	-1.603	Re	-0.265	-4.443
Ni-doped-VAl ₃	0.115	-1.933	Nb	-0.560	-9.390
W/PdGa	0.200	-3.353	Au(111)	0.540	-9.054
Mo(110)	-0.290	-4.862	Ag(111)	0.545	-9.138
Mo(100)	-0.190	-3.186	PtGa	0.131	-2.199
Al(111)	0.535	-8.970	PtAl	0.132	-2.216
Al(100)	0.610	-10.228	Cu ₂ C ₂ N ₄	0.100	-1.685
LiMgAs^{present}	-0.020	-0.500	Cu(111)	0.585	-9.809
Pd	-0.115	-1.933	Ag(100)	0.760	-12.743
Ir	-0.055	-0.971			

Table 5.4: Gibbs free energy and exchange current density for various materials.

(as evident from Fig. 5.11). Such high exchange current densities (i.e., $\text{Log}_{10}(i_0) = -0.5$ Acm^{-2}) arise due to the Gibbs free energy of -0.02 eV. Apart from this, the positive Gibbs free energy at some edge sites indicates that, these sites would thermodynamically favour and readily facilitates hydrogen evolution reaction. Hence establishing the fact that two dimensional topological insulator LiMgAs is indeed a *novel* topological quantum catalyst.

5.4 Conclusion

We presented our computational results wherein, topological insulators were explored for potential energy applications such as, thermoelectrics and catalysis. We presented our computations of thermoelectric transport properties for bulk AuI due to the dense states across the Fermi level and the semi-metallic band dispersion. Due to semi-metallic nature, the electronic mobility was found to be high resulting in a high power factor. Also, we observed strong phonon-phonon scattering which lead to smaller lattice thermal conductivity. We employed the semi-classical Boltzmann transport equations to compute the thermoelectric transport coefficients. We explored the thermoelectric parameters at various temperatures and carrier concentrations. We found that, contrary to several thermoelectric materials which exhibit high figure of merit at higher temperatures, AuI exhibits excellent figure of merit of 0.55 at room temperature which is more useful from practical purposes.

We also presented our investigations on the catalytic activity of AuI monolayer towards

hydrogen evolution reaction. The dimensionally engineered AuI monolayer exposes the basal plane containing Au which is a transition metal known for superior catalytic activities. We therefore presented the hydrogen evolution reactions along the basal plane of the two dimensional topological insulator AuI. The basal plane was preferred over the edge sites because, under pristine conditions (i.e., without any strain) the non-trivial gap was found to be 14.4 meV which is far less than the thermal energy at room temperature. Hence, the edge conducting states won't be prominent which implied that, there won't be significant difference in the catalytic response of the basal plane as compared to the edge plane. We presented various mechanisms by which a hydrogen evolution reaction could occur on the basal plane of two dimensional topological insulator AuI. Based on the adsorption energy and Gibb's free energy values, we conclude that, the basal plane of AuI favours Volmer-Heyrovsky over Volmer-Tafel reaction. Also, the preferred site of interaction would be over Au rather than I since at I the hydrogen atom interacts too strongly. We confirm the evolution of hydrogen molecule by plotting the charge density profiles in 3D.

Similarly, inspired by the latest developments in the field of topological quantum catalysis, we explored two dimensional LiMgAs for topological catalysis favouring hydrogen evolution reaction. We presented the transformation of the hexagonal unit cell into an orthorhombic unit cell by using a rotation transformation matrix. The stability of the proposed system was confirmed by computing ab-initio molecular dynamics simulations. We reiterated the, non-trivial topological quantum phase transitions by presenting the exchange of charge density profiles of bands near the Fermi level. Also, we presented the electronic slab band structure which indicated the edge Dirac semi-metallic nature. This was confirmed by plotting the edge charge densities in for the zig-zag and planar-like nanoribbon configurations wherein, we observed distinct edge charge accumulations. We begin with the computation of catalytic activity on the basal plane of LiMgAs monolayer and found that the system would be inefficient due to large adsorption energies and Gibb's free energy. However, we observed that, the catalytic activity along the edges was excellent with Gibb's free energy as low as -0.02 eV. This places two dimensional topological insulator LiMgAs into the Sabartiers optimum i.e., near the top of the volcano plot with high exchange current densities. Also, we explored various mechanisms of hydrogen evolution reactions such as, Volmer, Volmer-Tafel and Volmer-Heyrovsky. Off the planar and zig-zag nanoribbon terminations, we found that, the zig-zag nanoribbon configuration facilitated both the mechanisms of hydrogen evolution reaction

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(i.e., Volmer-Tafel and Volmer-Heyrovsky) whereas, the planar-like nanoribbon configuration facilitates only Volmer-Heyrovsky reaction. In order to confirm that, such superior catalytic activity is originating from the conducting edge states (due to the topological insulating nature of LiMgAs), we investigated the catalytic activity along the middle regions of the nanoribbon. We found that, the superior catalytic activity is indeed originating due to the conducting edge states and that the results are not a numerical artifact.

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CHAPTER 6

Summary and Future Prospects

This chapter summarises the results and discussions done in previous chapters in the backdrop of the motivation and objectives presented at the onset of this thesis in chapter 1. We mention in brief the key and outstanding features of this thesis accompanied with emphasis and reiteration of the unconventional/exceptional results obtained from our first-principles investigations. Also we briefly discuss the future prospects and scope for further explorations which might branch-out from the results presented and discussed in this thesis along-side my plans to further explore and investigate topological materials.

The revelations discovered by Thouless, Kosterlitz and Haldane by the end of 19th century, gave birth to a new branch in condensed matter physics. By the start of 21st century, Kane and Mele extended the Haldane's approach to realise a more generalised picture. On extending the graphene model to bulk materials the field of topological insulators in bulk and low dimensional materials was established. These materials exhibit insulating nature in D dimensions and conducting nature in $(D-1)$ dimensions. This excited the scientific community due to numerous potential applications of such materials. For example, the conduction in $(D-1)$ dimensions are robust against material impurities and external perturbations such as stress or temperatures. This implied that, these conducting states would host dissipationless transport of Fermions robust against back-scattering. Such materials would be extremely useful in realising room temperature quantum computers (which are currently only operated under cryogenic conditions), spintronic materials, valleytronic materials, sensors, ultra-fast switches for memory devices etc. The numerous possibilities attracted us to explore the

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topological insulating phase in some bulk and low dimensional materials. Although, by the time we began our investigations using first-principles method, numerous materials in bulk as well as low dimensional phase were already explored either experimentally or theoretically. However, there was lots of scope to fill in the gap and also to generate material repository which would guide experimental explorations. With this motivation we streamlined the objectives mentioned in chapter 1 of this thesis.

By employing state-of-the-art density functional theory approach, we predicted novel bulk and low dimensional materials in this thesis. Also, we established a necessary and sufficient condition to realise a non-trivial bulk topological insulator. We proposed methods by which we can realise a topological insulator from a topological conductor in bulk materials. We established that, trivial bulk materials can be used to realise non-trivial low dimensional materials by imposing quantum confinement effects. To further enhance the topological insulating character in low dimensional materials we presented the orbital filtering effects which can be realised by performing partial or complete functionalization of two dimensional materials. Once we predicted the non-trivial materials in bulk and low dimensional phase, we also explored them for energy applications. We began with the application of bulk AuI in thermoelectrics and then we explored the low dimensional phase of AuI for catalysis. We finally proposed novel technique to realise a topological quantum catalyst from a two dimensional topological insulator. We summarise the results obtained in this thesis in brief detail below.

In **CHAPTER 3**, we presented our investigations of topological quantum phase transitions in bulk materials. We began with Half-Heusler compounds LiMgX ($X = \text{Bi, Sb, As}$); governed by $\bar{F}43m$ space group with face centered cubic structures. LiMgBi was found to be dynamically stable with a direct global gap in the electronic band structure. On applying volume expansion pressure, we observed that at a critical pressure of 4.5% LiMgBi undergoes a topological quantum phase transition governed by s - p orbital band inversions with, spin-orbit coupling interactions induced gap of 1.10 meV. The closing and opening of the band gap was verified by using hybrid functional approach apart from the generalised gradient approach. The non-trivial character was verified by computing the surface state spectra which exhibit conducting nature. Also, we computed the \mathbb{Z}_2 invariants which were $(\nu_0, \nu_1 \nu_2 \nu_3) = (1, 0 0 0)$ which indicated that, LiMgBi is a strong topological insulator. We then presented similar phase transitions in LiMgSb, however, we observed that although LiMgSb presented band gap closing and

reopening alongwith exchange of orbitals across Fermi level and conducting surface state spectra but, on computing the \mathbb{Z}_2 invariants we found it to be a trivial insulator. Similarly, LiMgAs which was another direct band gap semi-conductor was subjected to pressure. Similar to LiMgSb, this system also presented band gap closing and reopening with exchange of orbital characters across Fermi level and conducting surface state spectra, but on computing the \mathbb{Z}_2 invariants we found it to be a trivial insulator like LiMgSb. Although the site ‘X’ in LiMgX were replaced with members of pnictogen family but, we observed contradicting topological properties. With this we established the necessary and sufficient condition for realising a non-trivial topological insulator i.e., apart from band gap closing and reopening, orbital inversion across Fermi level and conducting surface state spectra, the system should *necessarily* exhibit non-trivial \mathbb{Z}_2 invariants. Further, since these systems (LiMgSb, and LiMgAs) presented topological phase transitions at very high pressures we proposed that, dimensionally engineered monolayers can be realised using these bulk materials to facilitate non-trivial topological quantum phase transitions at relatively lower pressures.

Another problem in the topological insulator LiMgBi was that, the conduction bands crossed the Fermi level during the topological phase transitions. We addressed this issue by breaking the cubic symmetry and converting the material from a topological conductor to a topological insulator. We presented this phenomena in binary zincblende compound AuI. Although the stability of such a compound has been debated but, on computing phonon dispersion curves, formation energy and elastic tensors we found that, AuI is dynamically, energetically and mechanically stable. We followed two approaches to realise non-trivial topological properties in this binary compound, (i) application of isotropic compression and (ii) application of uni-axial compressive pressure along [001] crystal direction. We observed semi-metal to topological conductor and topological insulator transitions respectively under the said approaches. We observed that, due to the bulk inversion asymmetry, AuI exhibits Dresselhaus-like band-spin splittings characterized by unconventional $s, p-d$ orbital band inversions. The non-trivial nature was confirmed by computing the conducting surface state spectra and the principle \mathbb{Z}_2 invariant which was $\nu_0 = 1$ (when cubic symmetry was retained and broken).

In **CHAPTER 4**, we presented our investigations on the dimensional engineering of non-trivial two dimensional topological insulator LiMgAs from trivial bulk parent. As expected, this system presented non-trivial topological quantum phase transitions at low

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pressure due to quantum confinement effects and large surface-volume ratio. The proposed monolayer of LiMgAs was found to be dynamically stable with absence of negative phonon frequencies in the entire Brillouin zone. Also, the non-trivial phase of LiMgAs monolayer exhibits unconventional Fermion velocities along different directions of the Brillouin zone. The non-trivial topological phase transition in this system is characterised by s - p orbital inversions across the Fermi level accompanying the inversion in band dispersions. This system is proposed to exhibit room temperature applications owing to large-gap induced by spin-orbit interactions. Also, we compared the band inversion strength which is stronger as compared to the bulk parent, indicating towards the underlying quantum confinement effects. We finally confirmed the non-trivial nature by computing the \mathbb{Z}_2 invariant which was $\nu = 1$ and edge state spectra indicating a conducting Dirac dispersion along the edge Brillouin zone path.

To further increase the non-trivial gap solely due to spin-orbit interactions i.e., without applying strain, we explored functionalization technique. We presented, elemental monolayers of Tellurium and Selenium for the first time. According to previous reports in literature, we too observed that, the free-standing elemental monolayers are dynamically unstable. However, on partially functionalizing these monolayers with oxygen and sulphur (since, they would form bonds due to mutually favourable electronic configurations) we observed that TeO, SeS and SeS were dynamically stable except TeS. These stable monolayers were then explored for their electronic properties and we found that both, TeO and SeS present a large-gap under the influence of spin-orbit interactions. On inclusion of spin-orbit interactions we observed s - p orbital inversions across the Fermi indicating towards potential non-trivial character of TeO and SeS. The effect was attributed to orbital filtering effects which saturate the dangle bonds (originating from the p_z -orbitals) in z -direction giving rise to extra degrees of freedom to the electrons. This was confirmed by plotting the π and σ orbital projected band structures. We performed in-depth analysis of TeO since it exhibited highest non-trivial gap under spin-orbit interactions of 0.365 eV. We presented the Berry curvature and spin-Berry curvature analysis of TeO in the non-trivial regime under the influence of spin-orbit interactions. From the analysis we observed that, TeO can be used for spintronic and valleytronic applications, due to the opposite Lorentz forces acting on the electrons which leads to the spin-charge accumulation along the edges. This was presented in terms of the spin-projected electronic band structure along the two valleys points in the Brillouin zone. The large-gap induced due

to spin-orbit interactions also leads to unconventionally high spin Hall conductivity in the global gap (which was observed to be superior to several other materials). From experimental perspective, we also presented the investigations of quantum well $h\text{BN}/\text{TeO}/h\text{BN}$ which was found to retain the large-gap due to spin-orbit interactions under a tensile strain of 14%. These computations were followed by computing the edge state spectra of TeO and SeS. Clearly, TeO and SeS presented Dirac dispersions along the edge brillouin zone path. Also, we presented that the spin channels along the edges of SeS traverse in opposite directions by plotting the edge spectra along the [100] and [010] crystal directions. Ultimately, we presented the \mathbb{Z}_2 invariant which was found to be $\nu = 1$ indicating that, the non-trivial characters are indeed topological in nature and that, TeO and SeS are two dimensional topological insulators.

Similar to the dimensional engineering of LiMgAs from bulk parent, we presented the dimensionally engineered AuI monolayer. We saw that, due to quantum confinement effects, the low dimensional phase exhibits a narrow gap as compared to the bulk parent which exhibits semi-metallic character. The ground state of this system was found to exhibit buckled structure governed by the $P3m1$ space group rather than $P6_3mmc$ space group. However, in the $P3m1$ phase, AuI monolayer presented a gap of 14.4 meV, from here we subjected the system to compressive and tensile pressures to mark the topological quantum phase transition boundaries. We found that, the lower boundary was at -2% and the upper boundary was at 4% , within this region, AuI presented non-trivial topological insulating phase in two different structural phases of $P3m1$ and $P6_3mmc$ with the non-trivial gap as high as 0.113 eV under spin-orbit interactions. The underlying mechanism was found to be unconventional $s, p-d$ orbital inversion mechanism alongwith the inverted band dispersions. Also, we presented the inversion mechanism in terms of the exchange of charge densities or electron localisation functions across the Fermi level. To ascertain that, the non-trivial nature persists at the pressure of 3% (where the spin-orbit interactions induced gap is 0.113 eV) we computed the slab band structures and the edge state spectra both of which clearly host the non-trivial Dirac like edge dispersion in the edge brillouin zone. Finally we present the \mathbb{Z}_2 invariant and find that it is $\nu = 1$ in the region of -2% to 4% strain.

Finally, in **CHAPTER 5**, we presented our computational results wherein, topological insulators were explored for potential energy applications such as, thermoelectrics and catalysis. We presented our computations of thermoelectric transport properties for bulk AuI due to the dense states across the Fermi level and the semi-metallic band dispersion. Due to semi-

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metallic nature, the electronic mobility was found to be high resulting in a high power factor. Also, we observed strong phonon-phonon scattering which lead to smaller lattice thermal conductivity. We employed the semi-classical Boltzmann transport equations to compute the thermoelectric transport coefficients. We explored the thermoelectric parameters at various temperatures and carrier concentrations. We found that, contrary to several thermoelectric materials which exhibit high figure of merit at higher temperatures, AuI exhibits excellent figure of merit of 0.55 at room temperature which is more useful from practical purposes.

We also presented our investigations on the catalytic activity of AuI monolayer towards hydrogen evolution reaction. The dimensionally engineered AuI monolayer exposes the basal plane containing Au which is a transition metal known for superior catalytic activities. We therefore presented the hydrogen evolution reactions along the basal plane of the two dimensional topological insulator AuI. The basal plane was preferred over the edge sites because, under pristine conditions (i.e., without any strain) the non-trivial gap was found to be 14.4 meV which is far less than the thermal energy at room temperature. Hence, the edge conducting states wont be prominent which implied that, there wont be significant difference in the catalytic response of the basal plane as compared to the edge plane. We presented various mechanisms by which a hydrogen evolution reaction could occur on the basal plane of two dimensional topological insulator AuI. Based on the adsorption energy and Gibb's free energy values, we conclude that, the basal plane of AuI favours Volmer-Heyrovsky over Volmer-Tafel reaction. Also, we found that, the preferred site of interaction would be over Au rather than I since at I the hydrogen atom interacts too strongly. We cofirmed the evolution of hydrogen molecule by plotting the charge density profiles in 3D.

Similarly, inspired by the latest developments in the field of topological quantum catalysis, we explored two dimensional LiMgAs for topological catalysis favouring hydrogen evolution reaction. We presented the transformation of the hexagonal unit cell into an orthorhombic unit celll by using a rotation transformation matrix. The stability of the proposed system was confirmed by computing ab-initio molecular dynamics simulations. We reiterated the, non-trivial topological quantum phase transitions by presenting the exchange of charge density profiles of bands near the Fermi level. Also, we presented the electronic slab band structure which indicated the edge Dirac semi-metallic nature. This was confirmed by plotting the edge charge densities in for the zig-zag and planar-like nanoribbon configurations wherein, we observed distinct egde charge accumulations. We begin with the computation of catalytic

activity on the basal plane of LiMgAs monolayer and found that the system would be inefficient due to large adsorption energies and Gibbs free energy. However, we observed that, the catalytic activity along the edges was excellent with Gibbs free energy as low as -0.02 eV. This places two dimensional topological insulator LiMgAs into the Sabartiers optimum i.e., near the top of the volcano plot with high exchange current densities. Also, we explored various mechanisms of hydrogen evolution reactions such as, Volmer, Volmer-Tafel and Volmer-Heyrovsky. Of the planar and zig-zag nanoribbon terminations, we found that, the zig-zag nanoribbon configuration facilitated both the mechanisms of hydrogen evolution reaction (i.e., Volmer-Tafel and Volmer-Heyrovsky) whereas, the planar-like nanoribbon configuration facilitates only Volmer-Heyrovsky reaction. In order to confirm that, such superior catalytic activity is originating from the conducting edge states (due to the topological insulating nature of LiMgAs), we investigated the catalytic activity along the middle regions of the nanoribbon. We found that, the superior catalytic activity is indeed originating due to the conducting edge states and that the results are not a numerical artifact.

With this, we conclude the findings presented in our thesis. We now briefly present some future prospects. The versatility of topological materials makes them materials of choice for various potential applications apart from countable few which were discussed in this thesis. Recently, topological semi-metals hosting Fermi arcs across the surfaces have gained a lot of attention. Also, topological superconductors have attained significant attention over the past few years due to the topologically protected superconducting character which would be robust against external perturbations. Apart from these usual proliferations, topological materials have also found applications in, photodetectors, high energy particle physics, at the interface of topological insulator and superconductor (governed by Majorana Fermions), magnetic devices, field-effect transistors, gas-sensors, bio-sensors, batteries, memory cells, photonics, topological quantum catalysis, Floquet topological insulators, interferometers, magnetic field detectors, photo-luminescence, lasers etc. This indicates that, the work presented in this thesis and the results obtained thereoff are timely. Hence, significantly contributing further research and development in the field of topological materials, inspiring experimental investigations.

APPENDIX A

Computational Details

A.1 Bulk Materials

LiMgBi

We performed density functional theory based *first-principles* calculations to investigate topological phase transitions under the application of pressure. For this purpose, we obtained crystallographic information for LiMgBi in $\bar{F}43m[216]$ space group from MaterialsProject repository. Optimization of lattice constant (a) was performed following the convergence test for total energy with respect to, wave function cut off and \mathbf{k} -mesh. We used norm-conserving pseudopotentials under generalized gradient approximation which considers $1s^1$, $3s^2$ and $6s^26p^3$ orbitals of Li, Mg and Bi respectively for calculations without considering spin-orbit interactions. The pseudopotential method is based on martins-troullier with exchange correlation of perdw-burke-ernzerhof functional type.^{2,4} For calculations under spin-orbit interactions we used, projector augmented wave sets with perdw-burke-ernzerhof exchange correlation which considers the contribution from core electrons giving rise to relativistic effects in our calculations.³ The optimization was performed by, finding a global minima in terms of the total energy of the system and then narrowing down (using bisection method) to a local minima with a constrain that, the total pressure on the atoms is 0.00 kbar. The converged value of plane wave kinetic energy cut-off for norm-conserving (projector augmented wave) pseudopotential and charge density for norm-conserving (projector augmented wave) pseudopotential are 50 Ry (90 Ry) and 200 Ry (360 Ry) respectively. A uniform monkhorst-pack grid for \mathbf{k} -points of $7 \times 7 \times 7$ was used in the self-consistent calculations for both norm-conserving and projector augmented wave pseudopotentials.⁷ For better prediction of energy band gap and in order to verify our generalized gradient

approximation results, we have repeated some of our calculations with state-of-the-art screened coulomb hybrid functional calculations based on Heyd-Scuseria-Ernzerhof functional in Vienna *ab initio* simulation package.^{5,6} The cut-off for the plane-wave basis expansion was taken as 500 eV. To sample the Brillouin zone we have used a Monkhorst-Pack grid of $6 \times 6 \times 6$ k -points. The convergence criterion of 0.01 eV/Å for Hellmann-Feynman forces and 10^{-6} eV for total energy were considered. Phonon calculations were performed using density functional perturbation theory.¹¹ For phonon calculations, we used $10 \times 10 \times 10$ \mathbf{q} -mesh which was followed by plotting the dynamical matrices in the entire Brillouin zone.

LiMgSb

We employed *first-principles* calculation using plane wave self consistent formulation implemented in Quantum ESPRESSO code.¹ We employed norm conserving generalized gradient approximation pseudopotentials (which utilize the, $1s^1$, $3s^2$ and $5s^25p^3$ orbital contributions from Li, Mg and Sb respectively) with Martins-Troullier method.^{2,4} The plane wave basis set was optimized by convergence method, the resulting kinetic energy cutoff was 90 Ry. The optimized k -mesh i.e., Monkhorst-Pack grid of $8 \times 8 \times 8$ was used.⁷ The optimization was confirmed by the threshold for total force on atoms of the order of 10^{-4} eV/Å with total stress on atoms 0.00 kbar.

LiMgAs

We performed electronic studies using density functional theory based *first-principles* calculations in Quantum ESPRESSO code which implements plane wave self consistent formulation. We employed norm conserving generalized gradient approximation pseudopotentials which utilize the, $1s^1$, $3s^2$ and $4s^24p^3$ orbital contributions from Li, Mg and As respectively. Martins-Troullier pseudopotential method is used with exchange correlation of Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof functional type.^{2,4} Projector augmented wave sets with Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof exchange correlation were used for spin-orbit interaction calculations since, it considers the relativistic effects arising from the core electrons.³ Lattice constant, wave function kinetic energy cut-off and k -mesh were optimized by performing convergence test with, the test condition of total pressure on atoms as 0.00 kbar. The wave function kinetic energy cut-off was obtained to be 90 Ry (90 Ry for projector augmented wave). Uniform momentum Monkhorst-Pack grid was used in the calculations with, $8 \times 8 \times 8$ ($8 \times 8 \times 8$ for projector

augmented wave).⁷ Structural stability was verified by calculating phonon dispersion curves using density functional perturbation theory.¹¹ A q -mesh of $6 \times 6 \times 6$ was used.

For all the compounds, with thorough qualitative analysis, we quantified our results by calculating the surface states and \mathbb{Z}_2 invariants using WannierTools which used the tight-binding model generated by Wannier90.^{8,9}

AuI

The electronic properties (electronic band structure, density of state and orbital projected density of states) were calculated using state-of-the-art density functional theory based *first-principles* method as implemented in the Quantum ESPRESSO code.¹ The scalar relativistic norm-conserving pseudopotentials are employed for the calculations with martin-troullier method to replace the core ionic potential and consider the electronic effect only due to the valence electrons.² In order to consider the spin-orbit interaction effects, full relativistic projector augmented wave sets were used to account for the effect of core electrons.³ These pseudopotentials were used with exchange-correlation functional of perdue-burke-ernzerhof type under the generalized gradient approximation.⁴ The system was optimized with proper convergence test using the bisection method to obtain the ground state of the system. Converged values of the plane wave kinetic energy cut-off of 80 Ry with a uniform monkhorst-pack grid for k -vectors of $9 \times 9 \times 9$ were used in the self-consistent calculations with convergence threshold of $<10^{-6}$ Ry.⁷ We generated the tight-binding model for AuI using the maximally localised wannier functions which was obtained by proper minimization of the spread function $\tilde{\Omega}$ using the Wannier90.⁸ The tight-binding model was then passed through the WannierTools code to characterize and further investigate the topological states.⁹ WannierTools was used to calculate the surface states and \mathbb{Z}_2 invariants with the help of iterative Green's function and wilson Loop calculations respectively.

For validating the mechanical stability of AuI, the second-order elastic stiffness tensor was computed within Lagrangian theory of elasticity as implemented in the ElaStic code.¹⁰ For calculating the elastic constants of the system, a set of deformations were imposed on the optimized ground-state crystal structure and all deformed structures were relaxed keeping tight convergence criteria. Followed by this, the second ordered partial derivative of the total energy (U) with respect to the Lagrangian strain were computed using equation A.1 below. Where, V_0 is the volume of ground state reference structure with U being the total energy of

the deformed structures, and η_α and η_β being the Lagrangian strains in Voigt notation.

$$C_{\alpha\beta} = \frac{1}{V_0} \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial \eta_\alpha \partial \eta_\beta} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

The dynamic stability was investigated by calculating the phonon dispersion curves and the phonon density of states. Density functional perturbation theory was used with q -mesh of $8 \times 8 \times 8$ and self-consistency threshold of $<10^{-14}$ Ry.¹¹ This was followed by plotting the dynamical matrices in the entire Brillouin zone. Followed by this, the thermoelectric efficiency zT of the material was evaluated using equation A.2. Where, the symbols S , σ and T represent the Seebeck co-efficient, electrical conductivity and temperature, respectively, and the terms κ_e and κ_l are the electronic and lattice (phonon) contributions to the thermal conductivity.

$$zT = \left(\frac{S^2 \sigma}{\kappa_e + \kappa_l} \right) T \quad (\text{A.2})$$

The Boltzmann transport theory as implemented in BoltzTraP package which has been utilized for computing the electronic contribution to the thermoelectric transport properties of AuI.¹² The thermoelectric parameters like S , σ , κ_e , power factor ($\text{PF} = S^2 \sigma$) and zT were computed as a function of the chemical potential, carrier concentration and temperature for assessing their effect on the thermoelectric performance of AuI. It is a known fact that, the solution obtained under semi-classical Boltzmann transport treatment yields relaxation time (τ) dependent σ and κ_e . Hence, for obtaining τ independent thermoelectric parameters, we have employed deformation potential theory that has been widely utilized for computing mobility (μ) and relaxation time (τ) of bulk as well as low dimensional materials. The deformation potential based mobility was calculated using equation A.3. Where, apart from the standard constants, the terms C^{3D} , m^* and E_1 represent the elastic constant, the carrier effective mass and the deformation potential respectively.

$$\mu = \frac{(8\pi)^{1/2} e \hbar^4 C^{3D}}{3(k_B T)^{3/2} (m^*)^{5/2} E_1^2} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

Besides computing the electronic thermoelectric parameters, the lattice thermal conductivity of the material plays a crucial role in determination of the overall zT . For accurate predictions of the lattice contribution to thermal conductivity requires the inclusion of anharmonicity. This can be done by incorporating third or higher order interatomic force constants.

The first step towards this requires the computation of the second order harmonic interatomic force constants, which in present case are calculated under density functional perturbation theory. Following this, we have utilized a complementary python script provided together with the ShengBTE package for creating supercell structures of size $3 \times 3 \times 3$ considering the fifth nearest neighbour atoms.¹³ In total 260 supercell structures were constructed and were considered for self-consistent relaxation. The outputs of these 260 structures together with the second order interatomic force constants were fed to the same python utility tool for generating third order anharmonic interatomic force constants. At the end, the third order interatomic force constants with appropriate input script were utilized to iteratively solve the Boltzmann transport equation for phonons to calculate the temperature dependent thermal conductivity and related transport properties as implemented in ShengBTE package.¹³

A.2 Low Dimensional Materials

LiMgAs Monolayer

We performed electronic studies using, density functional theory based *first-principles* calculations in Quantum ESPRESSO code which implements plane wave self consistent formulation.¹ We employed norm conserving generalized gradient approximation pseudopotentials which utilizes the, $1s^1$, $3s^2$ and $4s^2 4p^3$ orbital contributions from of Li, Mg and As respectively. Martins-troullier pseudopotential method is used with exchange correlation of perded-burke-ernzerhof functional type.^{2,4} Projector augmented wave sets with perded-burke-ernzerhof exchange correlation are used for spin-orbit interaction calculations since, it considers the relativistic effects arising from the core electrons.³ Lattice constant, wave function kinetic energy cut-off and k -mesh were optimized by performing convergence test with, the test condition of total pressure on atoms as 0.00 kbar. The wave function kinetic energy cut-off was obtained to be 50 Ry (80 Ry for projector augmented wave). Uniform momentum grid of monkhorst-pack type was used in the calculations with, $6 \times 6 \times 1$ ($8 \times 8 \times 1$ for projector augmented wave).⁷ Structural stability was verified by calculating phonon dispersion curves using density functional perturbation theory.¹¹ A q -mesh of $5 \times 5 \times 1$ was used. With thorough qualitative analysis, we quantified our results by calculating the \mathbb{Z}_2 invariant using Wannier90 around the wilson charge loops this was followed by the plotting edge state spectra in WannierTools.^{8,9}

Functionalized Tellurene and Selenene

We implemented *first-principles* based density functional theory in Quantum ESPRESSO package to obtain the ground state energy of the system (with a vacuum of $c = 25.00 \text{ \AA}$ along the [001] crystal direction to isolate the interactions between periodic images) under plane wave self consistent formulation and calculate the electronic band structures, density of states and orbital/elemental projected density of states.¹ We used, scalar-relativistic and norm conserving martins-troullier pseudopotentials for calculations without spin-orbit interactions and fully-relativistic projector augmented wave pseudopotentials (for calculations with spin-orbit interactions) under generalized gradient approximation with perdedw-burke-ernzerhof type of exchange-correlation functional in our calculations.²⁻⁴ The converged value of kinetic energy cutoff was 80 Ry and the corresponding uniform momentum monkhorst-pack grid was of $8 \times 8 \times 1$.⁷ The structures were fully relaxed with force convergence criteria of $< 10^{-6}$ a.u. The dynamic stability of the system was investigated in terms of phonon dispersion curves and phonon density of states under the density functional perturbation theory regime with a q -mesh of $5 \times 5 \times 1$.¹¹ We then projected the plane wave functions onto the maximally localized wannier functions (with convergence of the spread function) by using Wannier90 code to compute the quantum transport properties and create the tight-binding hamiltonian as an input for the WannierTools code.^{8,9} The spin Hall conductivity (SHC) ($\sigma_{xy}^{spinz}(\omega)$) was computed using the kubo-greenwood formula within the independent-particle approximation, and the *Berry* curvature ($\Omega_z(k)$) and k -resolved spin *Berry* curvature ($\Omega_{xy}^{spinz}(k)$) to understand the topological properties and the quantum transport phenomena. For this purpose, a dense k -mesh of $100 \times 100 \times 1$ was used; since large contributions of spin Berry curvatures occur in minute regions of k space which leads to slow convergence. We finally compute the \mathbb{Z}_2 invariant, Chern number (C) and edge states using the WannierTools code.⁹

Aul Monolayer

We performed state-of-the-art density functional theory based *first-principles* computations as implemented in Quantum ESPRESSO code under the plane wave self consistent formalism.¹ We used scalar relativistic norm conserving martins-troullier pseudopotentials under generalized gradient approximation with exchange correlation functional of perdedw-burke-ernzerhof type.^{2,4} For spin-orbit interaction calculations, full relativistic projector

augmented wave sets with perdue-burke-ernzerhof exchange correlation functional were used to account for the relativistic effects arising from the core electrons.³ The optimized kinetic energy cut-off and uniform monkhorst-pack momentum grid (k -mesh for brillouin zone sampling) used for unit cell calculations were 90 Ry and $10 \times 10 \times 1$ respectively.⁷ The dynamic stability of the system was confirmed by calculating the phonon dispersion curves using density functional perturbation theory with a q -mesh of $5 \times 5 \times 1$.¹¹ A vacuum of 25 Å was introduced along the [001] crystal direction in order to eliminate the interactions with the neighbouring periodic images. Ab-initio molecular dynamics simulations were performed for 3 picoseconds (3000 femtoseconds) at 300 K thermostat temperature to verify the structural stability. To investigate the catalytic properties a $3 \times 3 \times 1$ supercell was designed with kinetic energy cut off and k -mesh of 60 Ry and $5 \times 5 \times 1$ respectively. In order to consider the van der Waals effect, Grimme correlations were incorporated in our computations.¹⁴ These were followed by; computing \mathbb{Z}_2 invariant around the wilson loops, edge state spectrum and slab band structures using WannierTools (WT) which employs the tight binding model generated by Wannier90.^{8,9}

Topological Quantum Catalyst LiMgAs

We performed density functional theory based *first-principles* calculations using Quantum ESPRESSO.¹ For calculations without spin-orbit interactions, we used scalar-relativistic and norm-conserving martins-troullier pseudopotentials and for calculations with spin-orbit interactions, we used fully-relativistic projector augmented wave pseudopotentials.^{2,3} The generalized gradient approximation was implemented with perdue-burke-ernzerhof type of exchange-correlation functional.⁴ The hexagonal unit cell was transformed into an orthorhombic unit cell using the rotation matrix (\mathcal{R}) which transforms the hexagonal basis vector into orthorhombic basis vector. This orthorhombic unit cell was then transformed into nanoribbons (with ribbon width $N = 15$ to avoid edge-edge interactions) which are periodic along, (a) [100] and (b) [010] crystal directions with zig-zag and planar like edge terminations respectively. The corresponding uniform momentum monkhorst-pack grid (k -mesh) for brillouin zone sampling was set to be $1 \times 6 \times 1$ and $6 \times 1 \times 1$ respectively.⁷ A vacuum of 25 Å along the [001] direction and 17 Å along the aperiodic directions in the nanoribbon configurations were imposed to avoid interactions due to periodic images. We also performed the calculations with $3 \times 3 \times 1$ supercell of two dimensional LiMgAs (with

25 Å vacuum along the [001] crystal direction) with k -mesh for brillouin zone sampling as $6 \times 6 \times 1$. The optimized kinetic energy cutoff used in all the calculations was set to 60 Ry and the systems were relaxed with force convergence criteria of $< 10^{-6}$ a.u. Throughout the calculations, Grimme correlations were incorporated to address the van der Waals effects.¹⁴ From the perspective of stability and room temperature viability, we performed ab-initio molecular dynamics simulations for 3 picoseconds (3000 femtoseconds) with thermostat set at 300 K. We calculated the slab band structures using WannierTools wherein the exact tight-binding Hamiltonian generated by Wannier90 was implemented.^{8,9}

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APPENDIX B

List of Publications

B.1 Related to Thesis

1. "Volume expansive pressure (VEP) driven non-trivial topological phase transition in LiMgBi ",
Raghottam M Sattigeri et.al., *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, **22**, 4602-4609 (2020)
2. "A first-principles Investigation Of Topological Phase Transition In Half-Heusler LiMgSb Driven By Volume Expansive Pressure",
Raghottam M Sattigeri et.al., *AIP Conference Proceedings*, Vol. **2265**, No. 1, p. 030020 (2020)
3. "Towards the dimensional engineering of a strong Topological Insulator",
Raghottam M Sattigeri and Prafulla K Jha. *Sci. Rep.*, **11**(1), 1-10 (2021) (*Received full waiver*)
4. "Emergence of $-s, -p-d$ band inversion in zincblende gold iodide topological insulator and its thermoelectric properties",
Raghottam M Sattigeri et.al., *J. Condens. Matter Phys.*, **33**(15), 155402 (2021)
5. "Functionalized Tellurene; a candidate large-gap 2D Topological Insulator",
Raghottam M Sattigeri and Prafulla K Jha. *J. Condens. Matter Phys.*, **34**(8), 08LT01 (2021)
6. "Topological Insulating Phase In Two-Dimensional Selenene Sulphide: A DFT Study",
Raghottam M Sattigeri et.al., *Proceedings of the 65th DAE Solid State Physics Symposium*, **55**, 849-850 (2021)
7. "Investigation of Topological and Catalytic properties of Gold Iodide (AuI) monolayer: A Density Functional Theory Study",
Raghottam M Sattigeri et.al., *Phys. Status Solidi - Rapid Res. Lett.*, **16**(5), 2100657

(2022) (*Invited contribution to 15th anniversary edition of PSS-RRL; Cover-art selected as issue cover with full waiver.*)

8. "Two dimensional LiMgAs: A topological quantum catalyst for hydrogen evolution reaction",

Raghottam M Sattigeri et.al., *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, **121**, 123101 (2022)

B.2 Other than Thesis

1. "Underwater Nuclear Reactor Design (UNRD) for safe and clean energy production", **Raghottam M Sattigeri**, *Proceedings of the International Conference on High Energy Radiation and Applications (ICHERA)*, **RN: 49055122**, IAEA, International Nuclear Information System (2017)

2. "Action Potential: A Vortex Phenomena; Driving Membrane Oscillations", **Raghottam M Sattigeri**. *Front. Comput. Neurosci.* **14**:21 (2020) (*Received full waiver*)

3. "Superior Room-Temperature Ammonia Sensing Using a Hydrothermally Synthesized MoS₂/SnO₂ Composite", Sukhwinder Singh, **Raghottam M Sattigeri**, et.al., *ACS Omega*, **6**(17), 11602-11613 (2021)

4. "Strain Driven Electronic Topological Transition in Half-Heusler LiCdAs: A Cubic Symmetry Breaking Approach", Bhautik R Dhori, **Raghottam M Sattigeri**, et.al., *Proceedings of the 65th DAE Solid State Physics Symposium*, **55**, 849-850 (2021)

5. "A first-principles investigation of pressure induced topological phase transition in Half-Heusler AgSrBi", Bhautik R Dhori, **Raghottam M Sattigeri**, et.al., *Mater. Adv.*, **3**, 3938-3944 (2022)

6. "Defect Induced Optical Properties of Ar⁺ Irradiated MoS₂ and MoSe₂", Madhavi H. Dalsaniya, ..., **Raghottam M. Sattigeri**, et.al., *Available at SSRN*, **4078387** (2022)

Curriculum Vitae

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Education

Secondary Education - 86.91%, Maharashtra State Board (MSBSHSE)	- 2010
Higher Secondary Education - 56.76%, Gujarat State Board (GSHSEB)	- 2012
BSc (Hons) - Physics (8.29/10), The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda	- 2015
MSc (Nuclear Physics) - Physics (7.34/10), The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda	- 2017
PhD Physics - Department of Physics, Faculty of Science, The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda	2019 - 2022

Research Interests

- Materials design and modeling for various applications in 3D, 2D, 1D and 0D using Density Functional Theory.
- Investigation of Topological phases of matter (Topological Insulators, Semi-metals, Superconductors) using Density Functional Theory.
- Investigation of 2D van der Waal heterostructures as sensors and detectors using Density Functional Theory.
- Investigation of materials for energy storage and applications (for example: electro/photo-catalysis, hydrogen storage, thermoelectricity etc.) using Density Functional Theory.
- Application of machine learning and high-throughput approaches in materials design and prediction.

Publications and Proceedings

1. "Volume expansive pressure (VEP) driven non-trivial topological phase transition in LiMgBi", **Raghottam M Sattigeri** et.al., *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, **22**, 4602-4609 (2020)
2. "A first-principles Investigation Of Topological Phase Transition In Half-Heusler LiMgSb Driven By Volume Expansive Pressure", **Raghottam M Sattigeri** et.al., *AIP Conference Proceedings*, Vol. **2265**, No. 1, p. 030020 (2020)
3. "Towards the dimensional engineering of a strong Topological Insulator", **Raghottam M Sattigeri** and Prafulla K Jha. *Sci. Rep.*, **11**(1), 1-10 (2021) (Received full waiver)
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5. "Functionalized Tellurene; a candidate large-gap 2D Topological Insulator", **Raghottam M Sattigeri** and Prafulla K Jha. *J. Condens. Matter Phys.*, **34**(8), 08LT01 (2021)
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7. "Investigation of Topological and Catalytic properties of Gold Iodide (AuI) monolayer: A Density Functional Theory Study", **Raghottam M Sattigeri** et.al., *Phys. Status Solidi - Rapid Res. Lett.*, **16**(5), 2100657 (2022) (Invited contribution to 15th anniversary edition of PSS-RRL)
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Publications and Proceedings other than Thesis

1. "Underwater Nuclear Reactor Design (UNRD) for safe and clean energy production", **Raghottam M Sattigeri**, *Proceedings of the International Conference on High Energy Radiation and Applications (ICHERA)*, **RN: 49055122**, IAEA, International Nuclear Information System (2017)
2. "Action Potential: A Vortex Phenomena; Driving Membrane Oscillations", **Raghottam M Sattigeri**. *Front. Comput. Neurosci.* **14**:21 (2020) (Received full waiver)
3. "Superior Room-Temperature Ammonia Sensing Using a Hydrothermally Synthesized MoS₂/SnO₂ Composite",

Sukhwinder Singh, **Raghottam M Sattigeri**, et.al., *ACS Omega*, **6**(17), 11602-11613 (2021)

4. “*Strain Driven Electronic Topological Transition in Half-Heusler LiCdAs: A Cubic Symmetry Breaking Approach*”,
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5. “*A first-principles investigation of pressure induced topological phase transition in Half-Heusler AgSrBi*”,
Bhautik R Dhori, **Raghottam M Sattigeri**, et.al., *Mater. Adv.*, **3**, 3938-3944 (2022)
6. “*Defect Induced Optical Properties of Ar⁺ Irradiated MoS₂ and MoSe₂*”,
Madhavi H. Dalsaniya, ..., **Raghottam M. Sattigeri**, et.al., *Available at SSRN*, **4078387** (2022)

Experience

Teaching: 3 Years; **Research:** 4 Years

Employment

University: GSFC University (School of Science, School of Technology), Vadodara, Gujarat
Designation: *Student Counselor Physics* **Duration:** 2017 – 2018

University: Department of Physics, Faculty of Science,
The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda, Vadodara, Gujarat
Designation: *Temp. Teaching Assistant* **Duration:** 2018 – 2020

University: Centre for Incubation,
Office of Career Advancement for Students (OCAFS),
The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda, Vadodara, Gujarat
Designation: *Coordinator* **Duration:** 2018 – 2022

University: Department of Physics, Faculty of Science,
The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda, Vadodara, Gujarat
Designation: *Junior Research Fellow*
Funding Agency: UGC-DAE-CSR, Indore **Duration:** 2020 – 2022

Attributes/Skills

- Proficient with scientific codes such as, Quantum ESPRESSO, VASP, Wannier90 and WannierTools. Familiar with BoltzTrap, ShengBTE and ElaStic code.
- Proficient in scientific programming with fortran 90-95 and HPC systems.
- Proficient with machine learning technique, crystal graph convolutional neural network (CGCNN) and familiar with high-throughput DFT using AFLOW.
- Strong analytical ability, reasoning and communication skills.
- Ability to work with ease as an individual or as a member of team in multilingual and multicultural environment.

Awards

1. *Two Criterion Recognition Awards* for Literary Scientific work by NASA in the, Humans in Space Youth Art Competition, organised by Planetary Science Division – NASA, Universities Space Research Assoc. (USRA) and Institute of Aerospace Medicine – German Aerospace Center (DLR), 2012.
2. Received *two gold medals* in BSc Physics at the *64th Annual Convocation* of The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda.
3. Received *two awards* from the Faculty of Science, The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda, for *excellence and securing highest marks* in *TY BSc Physics* at University level.
4. Received *four awards* from the Faculty of Science, The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda, for *excellence and securing highest marks* in *MSc Physics* at University level.
5. Received a cash prize of Rs. 5,000/- for best proposal during the International Winter School 2018 organized at JNCASR, Bangalore, December 2018.
6. Received a cash prize of Rs. 1,000/- for best poster during the International Winter School 2020 organized virtually by JNCASR, Bangalore, December 2020.

Conference/Workshop attended and Posters presented

- Poster presented on, “*Role of Physics in Nerve Conduction, Electrochemistry and Future Prospects*” held on, 30th Sept 2014 at, DBT-MSUB-ILSPARE Programme, Faculty of Science, The M S University of Baroda, Vadodara.
- Poster presented on, “*Physics of visual cortex*” at, the Open House and Science Exhibition, held on 11th March 2015, organised by Department of Physics, Faculty of Science, The M S University of Baroda, Vadodara.
- Poster presented on, “*Underwater Nuclear Reactor Design (UNRD) for Safe and Clean Energy Production*” at, the 2nd International Conference on High Energy Radiation and Applications, held on 11th October 2017, organised by Department of Physics, Faculty of Science, The M S University of Baroda, Vadodara.
- Participated in *international workshop* on, “*Modern Biophysical Tools and Techniques*” during, December 2017 at, IIT Bombay, Sponsored by the Biophysical Society (USA).
- Attended *winter school* on, “*Modelling and Simulations of Materials for Energy and Environment*” during, 12-14 December 2018 at, JNCASR, Bangalore. Organized in cooperation with ICMS and KIST, Bangalore.
- Attended *64th DAE Solid State Physics Symposium* and presented a poster titled, “*A first-principles Investigation Of Topological Phase Transition In Half-Heusler LiMgSb Driven By Volume Expansive Pressure*”, 17-22 December 2019 at, IIT, Jodhpur.
- Attended *International Winter School 2020* and presented a poster titled, “*Topological Insulating Phase In Half-Heusler Compounds*”, 7-11 December 2020 organised virtually by, JNCASR, Bangalore.
- Attended *Thomas Young Center, Moiré-Twistronics workshop 2021* and presented a poster titled, “*Topological Insulating Phase In Some Bulk and Low Dimensional Materials*”, 9-13 August 2021 organised virtually by, University College of London, UK.
- Attended *65th DAE Solid State Physics Symposium* and presented a poster titled, “*Topological Insulating Phase In Two-Dimensional Selenene Sulphide: A DFT Study*”, 15-19 December 2021 at, DAE Convention Centre, Anushaktinagar, Mumbai.